

Retinal and neural stimulation with quantum dots based photovoltaic interfaces

by

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Koç University
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To My Family...

ABSTRACT

Retinal and neural stimulation with quantum dots based photovoltaic interfaces

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Electrical stimulation of neural tissues is the one of the emerging technological areas in medicine. Although several attempts from various research groups, neuro-electronic interface technologies are still in infancy period. Especially in neurodegenerative situations, such as retinitis pigmentosa and age-related macular degeneration, neural stimulation could be effective rehabilitation method. For retina, photovoltaic surfaces are the pioneer concepts for recovery of sensation. The institutes, which are working on retinal prostheses, currently exploiting various photoactive electrical surfaces to stimulate bipolar and ganglion cells in the retina. However, they fail to fulfill functions of retinal prosthesis due to bio-incompatibility, external energy source necessity, lack of flexibility and mobility of prosthesis. Therefore, there is enormous necessity for innovative biomaterials at retinal prosthesis production.

Quantum dot based photovoltaic devices are great candidates for nano-sized neural stimulators. Their working principle relies on photoelectric effect, which makes them possible replacement for rhodopsin based phototransduction mechanism in photoreceptor cells. For retinal implant production on flexible PET (polyethylene terephthalate) surface, various types of quantum dot-based photovoltaic interfaces could be used, such as Lead(II)sulfide (PbS), Aluminum antimonide (AlSb). The main concerns on these biointerfaces are biocompatibility and effective electrical charge capacity on neurons which induce action potential activity. Compared to other photoactive polymer-based interfaces in literature, quantum dots-based materials could induce photoelectrical neurostimulation under lower light intensities due to their nanocrystal content. Also compared to other silicon-based biointerfaces, they do not need an external energy source or complicated processor systems, thanks to the photo-capacitive current production.

The aim of the study is to investigate various types of quantum dots-based structures to produce effective photovoltaic interface for neural stimulation, which could be used as retinal prosthesis in the rats with retinal degeneration. For this purpose, different type quantum dots were examined with in vitro biocompatibility and electrophysiology experiments. Then, selected quantum dots based neural interfaces implanted to the subretinal spaces of the rats with and without retinal degeneration. After implantation, electrophysiology (VEP-EEG and ERG) and behavioral tests conducted to understand biocompatibility and recovery of visual sensation. After in vivo studies, the animals were euthanized and changes in the retina after implantations and photoelectrical stimulations were observed. By this way, both functional recovery of vision and the structural integrity of the different cell types in retina were demonstrated.

Different types of quantum dots-based interfaces induce action potentials in primary hippocampal neurons, which enables neuromodulation with biocompatible photoactive interfaces. In in vivo step, PbS and AlSb QDs based retinal prostheses also induce retinal stimulation with light pulses. Unfortunately, required light levels for neural stimulation with these devices are significantly higher than ocular safety limits. Also, both AlSb and PbS QDs based retinal prostheses induce gliosis and retinal damage in subretinal implantation area. Because of those reasons, further investigations are required for quantum dots based retinal stimulation systems.

ÖZETÇE

Kuantum nokta temelli fotovoltaiik arayüzlerle retinal ve nöral stimülasyon

Erdost Yıldız

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Nöral dokuların elektriksel uyarımı tıpta son zamanlarda en çok gelişen teknolojik alanlardandır. Çeşitli araştırma gruplarının birçok çalışmasına rağmen, nöro-elektronik arayüzler pratik uygulama için henüz emekleme aşamasındadır. Özellikle retinitis pigmentosa ve yaşa bağlı makula dejenerasyonu gibi nörodejeneratif durumlarda nöral stimülasyon etkili bir rehabilitasyon yöntemi olabilir. Bu nedenle retina için fotovoltaiik yüzeylerle görme duyusunun geri kazandırılması için gözde çalışma alanlarından. Retina protezleri üzerinde çalışan enstitüler, şu anda retinal bipolar ve gangliyon hücrelerini uyarmak için çeşitli fotoaktif elektriksel yüzeylerden yararlanmaktadır. Ancak biyoyumluluk problemleri, dış enerji kaynağı gerekliliği, protezin esnek ve harekete dayanıklı olmaması nedeniyle retina protezleri tam işlevlerini yerine getirememektedir. Bu nedenle retina protezi üretiminde yenilikçi biyomalzemelere büyük ihtiyaç duyulmaktadır.

Kuantum nokta tabanlı fotovoltaiik cihazlar, nano düzeyde nöral uyarım için harika adaylardır. Çalışma prensipleri, fotoreseptör hücrelerde rodopsin bazlı fototransdüksiyon mekanizmasının yerini almalarını mümkün kılan fotoelektrik etkiye dayanmaktadır. Esnek PET (polietilen tereftalat) yüzeyinde retina implant üretimi için, Kurşun(II)sülfür (PbS), Alüminyum antimonit (AlSb) gibi çeşitli kuantum nokta temelli fotovoltaiik arayüzler kullanılabilir. Bu biyo-arayüzlerin uygulamasında temel zorluklar, biyoyumluluk ve nöronlar üzerinde aksiyon potansiyeli aktivitesini indükleyecek elektriksel uyarım kapasitesidir. Literatürdeki diğer fotoaktif polimer bazlı arayüzlerle karşılaştırıldığında, kuantum nokta bazlı materyaller, nanokristal içerikleri nedeniyle daha düşük ışık yoğunlukları altında fotoelektrik nörostimülasyonu indükleyebilir. Ayrıca diğer silikon bazlı biyoarayüzlere kıyasla, fotokapasitif akım üretimi sayesinde harici bir enerji kaynağına veya karmaşık işlemci sistemlerine ihtiyaç duymazlar.

Tez çalışmamın amacı, retina dejenerasyonu olan sıçanlarda retina protezi olarak kullanılabilecek, nöral stimülasyon için etkili fotovoltaiik arayüz üretmek için çeşitli kuantum noktaları tabanlı yapıları araştırmaktır. Bu amaçla, in vitro biyoyumluluk ve elektrofizyoloji deneyleri ile farklı tipte kuantum noktaları incelenmiştir. Daha sonra, retina dejenerasyonlu ve sağlıklı sıçanların subretinal boşluklarına implante edilen kuantum nokta temelli nöral arayüzler, implantasyondan sonra, biyoyumluluğu ve görsel duyusunun iyileşmesini anlamak için elektrofizyoloji (VEP-EEG ve ERG) ve davranış testleri ile incelenmiştir. İn vivo çalışmalardan sonra ötenazi yapılan hayvanların retinalarında implantasyon ve fotoelektrik uyarım sonrası retinal değişiklikler gözlemlenmiştir. Bu sayede hem görmenin işlevsel olarak geri kazandırılması hem de retinadaki farklı hücre tiplerinin yapısal bütünlüğü incelenmiştir.

Farklı kuantum nokta temelli arayüzler, hipokampal nöronlarda aksiyon potansiyeli oluşturarak, biyoyumlu fotoaktif arayüzlerle nöromodülasyon yapılabileceğini göstermiştir. İn vivo aşamada, PbS ve AlSb kuantum nokta temelli retinal protezler, ışık uyarımı ile retinal stimülasyon yaratmıştır. Ancak, bu cihazlarla nöral stimülasyon için gerekli ışık seviyeleri, oküler güvenlik limitlerinden yüksektir. Buna ek olarak hem AlSb hem de PbS kuantum nokta temelli retinal protezlerin subretinal implantasyonu, gliosis ve retina hasarına neden olmaktadır. Bu nedenlerden dolayı, kuantum nokta temelli retinal stimülasyon sistemleri için daha fazla araştırma yapılması gerekmektedir.

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ABBREVIATIONS

aCSF	Artificial cerebrospinal fluid
AlSb	Aluminum Antimony
AMD	Age-Related Macular Degeneration
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
ATP	Adenosine Triphosphate
CD31	Platelet endothelial cell adhesion molecule
CNV	Choroidal Neovascularization
CTG	Cell Titer-Glo Assay
DA/HanRj	Dark Agouti Rat
DAPI	4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole
DME	Diabetic Macular Edema
DMEM	Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium
DMEM/F12	Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium/Nutrition Mixture F-12
DMSO	Dimethyl Sulfoxide
DR	Diabetic Retinopathy
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
EDS	Energy-dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy
EEG	Electroencephalogram
EGTA	Ethylene glycol-bis(β -aminoethyl ether)-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid
EMA	European Medicines Agency
ERG	Electroretinography
FBS	Fetal Bovine Serum
FDA	United States Food and Drug Administration
FIR	Finite Impulse Response
GA	Geographic Atrophy
HBSS	Hank's Balanced Saline Solution
HEPES	4-(2-hydroxyethyl)-1-piperazineethanesulfonic acid
ILM	Inner Limiting Membrane
InP	Indium Phosphate

ITO	Indium Tin Oxide
LCA	Leber Congenital Amaurosis
LED	Light-emitting diode
MTT	3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-Diphenyltetrazolium Bromide
NBM	Neurobasal Medium
NeuN	Hexaribonucleotide Binding Protein-3
NIR	Near Infrared Spectrum
OCT	Optimal cutting temperature compound
OLM	Outer Limiting Membrane
QDs	Quantum Dots
P3HT	Poly(3-hexylthiophene-2,5-diyl)
PbS	Lead Sulfate
PBS	Phosphate Buffered Saline
PC71BM	Pheynl-C71-butyric acid methyl ester
PCBM	Phenyl-C61-butyric acid methyl ester
PDL	Poly-D-Lysine
PDR	Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy
PED	Pigment Epithelial Detachment
PEDOT:PSS	Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) Polystyrene Sulfonate
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PFA	Paraformaldehyde
PKC- α	Protein kinase C alpha
PLL	Poly-L-Lysine
PTB7-Th	Poly[4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl)thiophen-2-yl)benzo[1,2-b;4,5-b']dithiophene-2,6-diyl-alt-(4-(2-ethylhexyl)-3-fluorothieno[3,4-b]thiophene-)-2-carboxylate-2-6-diyl)
RCS/Kyo	Royal College of Surgeons Rat
RGC	Retinal Ganglion Cell
RP	Retinitis Pigmentosa
RPE	Retinal Pigment Epithelium
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
TUNEL	Terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase dUTP nick end labeling
UV	Ultraviolet Spectrum

VEGF	Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor
VEP	Visual Evoked Potentials
WHO	World Health Organization
XRD	X-ray Crystallography
ZnO	Zinc Oxide
ZnS	Zinc Sulfate

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. General Information

Neural stimulation is a well-known effective physical treatment option for a wide range of neurological disorders. While number of clinical applications are relatively wide range, translational research about this topic is especially on novel materials in nanoscale. Nanoscale electronic structures have various advantages in neural stimulation applications, such as minimal invasiveness, highly increased spatial resolution, and possible cell specific stimulation ability (Wang & Guo, 2016). They could induce neural stimulation in four main modalities: photoelectrical (Airaghi Leccardi et al., 2020), photothermal (Yoo et al., 2019), magnetoelectrical (Kozielski et al., 2021) and acoustic (R. Guo et al., 2019). Each modalities have their own advantages and disadvantages. Currently, most common method for neural modulation is photoelectrical stimulation, which could be modulate much easier than other methods. Also, photoelectrical stimulation could be real-time recorded sensitively because it did not create electromagnetic noise compared to other methods (Barbruni et al., 2020). Long term effects of photoelectrical stimulation are also well-known because of other artificial light application studies on retina (Mattsson et al., 2012). Photoelectrical stimulation has more higher long term biocompatibility compared to photothermal, magnetoelectrical and acoustic applications (Zimmerman & Tian, 2018). With photoelectrical nanostructures, stimulating a relatively small tissue volume, which may improve selectivity of therapeutic stimuli, is possible, as an alternative to optogenetic applications. Current neuromodulation technology aims chronic stimulation without foreign body response in tissue, which limits ability of these devices for neural recording and

neurostimulation. To address the immune response problem, decreasing size and rigidity of the materials could be possible solution (Pancrazio et al., 2017).

For photoelectrical therapy, the retina is a favorable tissue for biomedical application. The retina is light sensitive part of the eye, converts light into electrical signals that are transferred to upper visual pathways to create images. Neural part of the retina consists of five layers of neural cells from inside to outside; ganglion cell layer, inner plexiform layer, inner nuclear layer, outer plexiform layer, and outer nuclear layer. These layers limited with inner limiting membrane (ILM) and outer limiting membrane (OLM) while supported by Müller glial cells.(Werner & Chalupa, 2004)

Three main neural cell types are responsible from phototransduction of light in retina: Photoreceptor cells, bipolar cells, and ganglion cells. Beside these, horizontal and amacrine cells assists phototransduction, but their principal tasks are light adaptation and preprocessing of image in the retina. Emitted light from photoreceptor cells transferred to ganglion cells via bipolar cells. Two type of photoreceptor cells are responsible in different light conditions: rod type photoreceptors at low-light levels from 10^{-6} to 10^{-2} cd/m^2 (scotopic vision) and cone type photoreceptors in day light conditions from 10 to 10^8 cd/m^2 (photopic vision). Between 10^{-2} and 10 cd/m^2 , both photoreceptor types are active for mesopic vision (Kandel et al., 2012). Possible disruptions in phototransduction pathways in any level of retina could lead to an irreversible loss in the visual sensation. The most common mechanism which irreversibly damages phototransduction in retina is photoreceptor cell death because of retinal degenerative processes or metabolic disorder related conditions (Bourne et al., 2012).

Retinal degeneration, which is the leading etiology of irreversible blindness worldwide, is primarily characterized by the dysfunctional or degenerated photoreceptors that impairs the ability of the retina to process visible light. Various research groups are working on rehabilitation of the retina in retinal degenerative diseases via different approaches. Three main approaches were emphasized

currently in studies on restoration of vision in retina: electrical stimulation methods, optogenetic modifications, and stem cell based therapies (Yue et al., 2016).

1.1.1. Retinal Degenerative Diseases

Retinal degenerative diseases are the most common reasons of irreversible legal blindness all over the world. Around 350 million people suffer from retinal degenerative diseases all around the world. The most frequent retinal degenerative disease is age-related macular degeneration (AMD) with 196 million patients and it is followed by diabetic retinopathy and retinitis pigmentosa (WHO, 2019). Around one-third of the population is diagnosed with diabetes, with one-tenth having vision-threatening disease course which includes diabetic macular edema (DME) or proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) (Ting et al., 2016). Retinitis Pigmentosa (RP) is a hereditary retinopathy that affects about 2.5 million people worldwide. It is characterized with progressive loss of rods and cones and causes severe visual dysfunction and eventual blindness in bilateral eyes. In addition to more than 3000 genetic mutations from about 70 genes, a wide genetic overlap with other types of retinal dystrophies has been reported with RP. This diversity of genetic pathophysiology makes treatment extremely challenging (Dias et al., 2018). Each retinal degenerative disorder starts with different pathophysiology and eventually all of them leads to photoreceptor cell degeneration and irreversible vision loss.

Age-Related Macular Degeneration

Age-related macular degeneration, leads loss of vision by three pathophysiology (Schachat et al., 2017):

- Choroidal neovascularization (CNV); which leads to outgrow of blood vessels through Bruch's membrane. In neovascular phase of AMD, choroidal neovascularization breaks through to the neural retina, leaking fluid, lipids, and blood, and leading to fibrous scarring.
- Pigment epithelium detachment (PED); accumulation of fluid between retinal pigment epithelium and Bruch's membrane induces loss of perfusion in retina.

- Geographic Atrophy (GA); which is loss of RPE and photoreceptor cells, leads to progressive atrophy of the retinal pigment epithelium, choriocapillaris, and photoreceptors irreversibly (Lim et al., 2012).

These three pathophysiological results of AMD were not treatable via medical or surgical interventions. After late stages of AMD, “wet” AMD (AMD with CNV) and “late dry” AMD (AMD with GA) damage on the photoreceptor layer of the retina is reversible. Even after latest advances in medical interventions, pharmacological therapy only delays progression of AMD (Luu & Palczewski, 2018).

Gene therapies for AMD are also emerging in recent years. Safety of the subretinal administration of the rAAV.sFLT-1, which is the recombinant adeno-associated viral vector encoding soluble vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) receptor-1, have observed in early results of clinical trials in neovascular age-related macular degeneration patients (Rakoczy et al., 2015). Addition to recent gene therapy studies, stem-cell-based therapies are also investigated in treatment of advanced AMD, especially in AMD with geographic atrophy (da Cruz et al., 2018).

On the other hand, the research on visual rehabilitation implants in AMD patients were accelerated in recent years. While low-vision magnifiers and intraocular implants made easier activities of daily living of AMD patients, innovative retinal prostheses could replace retina for basic visual functions (Spooner et al., 2018). Currently, two commercial devices have been tested in multiple human clinical trials: the Argus II electronic epiretinal device (Second Sight Medical Products, CA, USA) and the Alpha-IMS electronic subretinal device (Retina Implant AG, Germany) (Yue et al., 2016). In addition, PRIMA near-infrared subretinal photovoltaic retinal prosthesis (Pixium Vision, France) have tested in a preliminary clinical trial for visual rehabilitation of AMD (Palanker et al., 2020). These devices were firstly designed for patients with retinitis pigmentosa, and they also could be useful for advanced AMD cases. The retinal prostheses provide sensation of light, recognition of large objects, improved visual functionality and even recovery of reading ability with visual aids (Mitchell et al., 2018).

Diabetic Retinopathy

Diabetes mellitus is not just an endocrine disease but also multiorgan disease, which affects especially ocular structures (Yıldız et al., 2020). The most affected part of the eye during the diabetes mellitus pathogenesis is retina. Diabetic retinopathy has two stages: non-proliferative and proliferative. Early changes during the non-proliferative stage of the retinopathy have insignificant effects on vision of patients but severity of non-proliferative components of diabetic retinopathy predict further progression of proliferative stage of the diabetic retinopathy. During non-proliferative stage, capillary nonperfusion and leakages occurs and these events leads to extensive edema and inflammation in retina, which leads to neurodegeneration (Tang & Kern, 2011). In early stage of DR, retinal microaneurysms commonly occur and these microaneurysms are the sum of localized weaknesses in the retinal vessels, blood pressure disturbances, and glial destruction (Kern, 2007).

Increase in retinal neovascular events and visual impairments indicate advanced stages of the diabetic retinopathy, which named as proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR). The pathogenesis for diabetic retinopathy related visual impairment includes vitreous hemorrhage, tractional retinal detachment, fibrovascular epiretinal membrane, and macular edema. Neovascularization process in the retina leads to loss of capillary perfusion, extensive ischemia, and lastly irreversible neurodegeneration. Although there are various pharmacological and surgical interventions for diabetic retinopathy, currently none of them could reverse the damage made by proliferative stage of DR (Danis & Davis, 2008). Because of the lack of macula in the most of experimental animal models, studying on diabetic neovascularization and diabetic macular edema (DME) is problematic (Tang & Kern, 2011).

Although the prevalence of diabetic retinopathy increase, thanks to the new treatment options, e.g., VEGF, photocoagulation, the managements of PDR and DME significantly improved. On the other hand, rehabilitation of vision after long term proliferative diabetic retinopathy is still important problem to solve. Even

neovascular coupling of neural retinae have recovered, neurodegeneration persists. Because of this, new therapeutic approaches should adopt more holistic, translational and interdisciplinary approach to tailor appropriate treatments of various pathologies in diabetic retinopathy (Duh et al., 2017).

Retinitis Pigmentosa

Retinitis pigmentosa is a group of rare, genetic retinal dystrophies which leads to loss of photoreceptor cells. RP patients firstly start to lose their night vision and peripheral vision. It affects 1 in 4000 people in average for worldwide, but in some communities its prevalence increase up to 1 in 750 people (Jonas et al., 2010). It affects mostly young adults, the age of onset is 35 years. Currently, no medical or surgical treatment for retinitis pigmentosa, except some single gene related forms (Verbakel et al., 2018).

In most cases of RP, initial retinal degeneration starts with rod photoreceptors and degeneration of cone photoreceptors follows, due to the co-dependence between rods and cones (Hamel, 2006). Because rods are concentrated in the peripheral retina, peripheral vision deteriorate in early RP stages, which creates tunnel vision in the patients (Cuenca et al., 2014). Retinitis pigmentosa could be divided into three stages: initial, intermediate, and advanced stages. Initial stage of RP, characterized by night blindness, which occurs due to rod dysfunction, during early adolescence. These symptoms occur mostly in dim light and the diagnosis is difficult to establish, if there is no family history. In the intermediate stage, night blindness became evident, it creates difficulties in driving and walking. At this stage, RP could be clinically diagnosed via fundus examination, which shows retinal pigment deposits and retinal atrophic areas. In visual field test, constricted visual field of the patient could be quantified. At the last stage, which is advanced stage, patients also lose their daylight vision because of the loss of both rod and cone photoreceptors. In fundus examination, widespread pigment deposits, retinal vessel attenuation, RPE atrophy, and choriocapillaris loss could be seen (Hartong et al., 2006).

The genetic basis of retinitis pigmentosa is highly complex and heterogeneous. It shares complex gene mutation background with other inherited retinal dystrophies, such as cone-rod dystrophy, congenital stationary night blindness, and Leber congenital amaurosis (LCA). This similar genetic backgrounds of RP and other hereditary retinal dystrophies suggests that there are fundamental changes in the underlying cellular and genetic mechanisms, despite their diverse clinical presentations. Currently, more than 70 genes have been identified to be associated with RP (Daiger et al., 1998). The major causative genes are Rho, RPRF, PRPH2, RP1, IMPDH1 and PRPF8 for autosomal dominant RP; USH2A, ABCA4, PDE6A, PDE6B and RPE65 for autosomal recessive RP; RPGR and RP1 for X-linked RP (Kannabiran, 2008). Because of the diverse genetic background of the retinitis pigmentosa patients, emerging genetic therapies to the RP, could not treat most of the patients (Dias et al., 2018).

Various types of the innovative therapy options are becoming available to restore visual sensation or stop the progressive loss of vision caused by RP. Most of the therapeutic strategies are being designed to slow down the retinal degenerative processes, to treat intraocular complications, and to reduce the impact of blindness. Main approaches to treat RP are gene therapy, pharmacological therapy, retinal transplantation, dietary supplements, stem cell therapy, and retinal prostheses. Currently, only retinal prostheses are clinically available treatment method for rescue of vision in RP patients and novel retinal implant prototypes are emerging by help of recent advancements in nanotechnology and material science (Musarella & MacDonald, 2011).

1.1.2. Retinal Prostheses

As we mentioned above, retinal diseases are leading cause of blindness all around the world. Among the degenerative diseases of the retina, retinitis pigmentosa (RP) and age-related macular degeneration (AMD) are the most common causes of blindness. There is no certain pharmacological treatment that can even prevent progression of these diseases. Instead of these treatments, most of the recent studies are focusing on providing visual rehabilitation via stimulation of the inner retinal

layers with the help of photosensitive retinal prostheses. Promising results for various retinal prosthesis prototypes are obtained in preclinical studies (Abdallah et al., 2018; Gekeler et al., 2018; J. F. Maya-Vetencourt et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2018). Inorganic microelectrodes and photovoltaic devices are used in many RP patients, while new generation retinal prostheses such as organic-based photo-switches and conjugated polymers continue to develop more tissue-compatible systems.

History

The concept of phosphene was discovered firstly in 1929 by the German neurologist Otfried Foerster, which was described as a visual percept created by the electrical stimulation of visual pathways (Towle et al., 2020). After Foerster's the discovery by stimulating the visual cortex, Tassicker drafted the first prototype of a retinal stimulation system in 1956 (Dowling, 2009). However, research and development studies for retinal prostheses literally began in the 1980s. Clinical studies of Humayun et al. found that subjects with both normal and impaired vision had phosphene perception by cortical electrical stimulation (Chader et al., 2009; Fernandes et al., 2012). They also found that threshold values of electrical stimulation on the visually impaired subjects were significantly higher than healthy subjects.

The first clinical application of retinal prosthesis was initiated by Second Sight Medical Products for phase I studies of Argus I retinal prosthesis. Nine years later, Argus II, successfully implanted in 30 retinitis pigmentosa patients and approved by European Medicines Agency (EMA) for clinical usage in Europe. At 2013, Argus II was the first retinal prosthesis system to receive Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approval for advanced stages of retinitis pigmentosa (Ahuja & Behrend, 2013; Caspi et al., 2016; da Cruz et al., 2013; da Cruz et al., 2016; Ghodasra et al., 2016; Gregori et al., 2018; Humayun et al., 2009; Olmos de Koo & Gregori, 2016). Nowadays, there are more than 20 clinical research groups, which working for the development of retinal stimulation devices in all around the world.

Basic Concepts and Designs for Retinal Prostheses

Although visual prostheses could be produced for any part of the visual pathways, the retina is the most appropriate target for the treatment of external retinal diseases due to easy access, pre-processing intervention, and linear neural architecture of intact neural processing units (Loizos et al., 2018). The prototypes of retinal prostheses are generally classified according to the position to where they are implanted: epiretinal, subretinal and suprachoroidal. Each type of subretinal prosthesis has pros and cons because of their implantation area and working principles (Bertschinger et al., 2008).

The main principle of the operation of the retinal stimulation systems is to create neuro-electrical interface between neurons and electrodes of the implant. In epiretinal approach, contacting cell type is RGCs, because of that, frequency-based modulation is the main neuromodulation mechanism. On the other hand, for subretinal and suprachoroidal approach, main target cell type is bipolar cells, which could be modulated via intensity of electrical stimulus (Weiland & Humayun, 2014). Epiretinal prostheses are easily implantable and low-risk prostheses for retinal detachment, while subretinal implants can benefit from the intact middle retinal layer, which includes neural processing layers of amacrine, horizontal and bipolar cells (Ho et al., 2015). Suprachoroidal implants are also easy to implant, and they benefit from presence of bipolar cell layer, but they need higher electrical stimulation potentials because of the resistance of sclera.

Common electronic structures for the retinal electrical stimulation are micro-photodiode and micro-electrode arrays in retinal prostheses. While micro-photodiodes generate electricity from the photons that come into the eye (Benav et al., 2010; Chow et al., 2002; Peachey & Chow, 1999), microelectrodes generate stimuli with help of camera, processor and transmission units (Linderholm et al., 2013). Advantages of micro-photodiodes are their independence from external cameras, processors or transmitters and usage of natural light impingement on retina for production of electrical stimuli (Schubert et al., 1999). On the other hand, micro-electrodes can produce stronger electrical impulses and innovative light processing

algorithms can improve contrast, edge detection and other features of the visual processing (Lee et al., 2009).

Noticeable examples of epiretinal prostheses are FDA/EMA approved Second Sight Medical Products patented Argus II (Schaffrath et al., 2019), Pixium Vision patented IMI (Hornig et al., 2007), and intraocular EPIRET3 prosthesis (Menzel-Severing et al., 2012). While Argus II is commercially available for RP patients, IMI and EPIRET3 were still evaluated in clinical trials. Their main advantage is being able to use direct internal stimulation on axons of retinal ganglion cells (RGCs), which make possible remodeling of internal retinal circuit after photoreceptor degeneration. But all these devices require an external video camera device to produce an image on the retina (da Cruz et al., 2013; Ho et al., 2015).

Suprachoroidal prostheses locate between choroid and sclera. In comparison with other types of retinal prostheses, suprachoroidal prostheses are relatively distant from the retina, which decrease their stimulation efficiency. There are two types of suprachoroidal prostheses: Semi-chronic suprachoroidal transscleral (STS) prosthesis (Fujikado, 2017) and Bionic Vision Australia (BVA) Consortium patented BVA prosthesis (Abbott et al., 2018). Each of these prosthesis prototypes has lesser number of electrodes compared to other types of retinal implants.

In other respects, subretinal implants interact better with preserved inner retinal layers and do not impair natural eye-head coordination. Examples of subretinal implants are Optobionics patented ASR (Chow et al., 2004), Retinal Implant AG patented Alpha IMS (Daschner et al., 2018), and Pixium Vision patented PRIMA (Palanker et al., 2019), and Boston Retinal Implant Project (Kelly & Rizzo, 2017). Clinically approved Alpha IMS, which is directly sensitive to light, additionally require a wired power supply and processor for image reconstruction. Latest example of the subretinal prosthesis, which is NIR light powered PRIMA retinal prosthesis, which consist of photodiode chips connected to stimulating electrodes, convert light energy to electrical stimulation and stimulate the bipolar cell layer (Chuang et al., 2014; Smith et al., 2015). Even PRIMA receives both power and visual input support via infrared light amplification on the prosthesis, it requires an

external camera on glasses, that converts the natural image to infrared light gradient (Flores et al., 2019). However, both of these systems also have problems in electrical stimulation of retinal tissue due to remodeling, fibrosis, and gliosis in advanced stages of the retinal degenerative diseases (Joseph et al., 2021).

The main disadvantages of first-generation retinal implants can be summarized as biocompatibility problems, visual field limitations, high impedance levels and heat generation. These systems, which also require external camera systems, cause difficulties in stimulating the appropriate retinal area due to saccadic movements of the head and eye (Zrenner, 2002). Because of these reasons, the use of new generation organic implants is increasing rapidly. Although they could not achieve electrical efficiency levels of silicone-based systems, they are providing very high tissue compatibility and can be implantable to all types of surfaces, due to their carbon based structure (José Fernando Maya-Vetencourt et al., 2017). Additionally, their production is easy and inexpensive compared to silicon-based counterparts.

Organic electronic devices offer highly promising results for various applications in different living tissues (J. F. Maya-Vetencourt et al., 2017). Especially, semiconductor polymer-neuron interfaces operate as photosensors-activators that trigger activation in the inner retinal layers to induce photoelectrical stimulation of the retina. Even in nanoparticle levels, they could induce retinal electrical stimulation in daylight settings (Maya-Vetencourt et al., 2020). Organic electronic devices lead to the emergence of a new field of bioelectronics, which includes integrable and interacting conjugated polymers, organic prostheses, and (a)biotic interfaces on living tissues. These devices are likely to be used in the future for retinal stimulation systems as well as other applications based on neural stimulation with light.

Current Developments in Retinal Stimulation

The field of retinal prostheses has developed rapidly over the past three decades, and advances have been significantly affecting clinical applications. In this period, they moved from theoretical concepts to the three commercially available products for

retinal stimulation. Unfortunately, because of commercial and economic challenges, two manufacturers with the largest patient base, Retina Implant AG and Second Sight Medical Products, have recently withdrawn from commercial retinal prosthesis market. Despite the difficult path to commercial viability of these products, over 500 researchers worldwide are working on retinal stimulation technologies and prototypes of retinal implants continue to be refined and commercialized (Bloch et al., 2019).

There are main challenges ahead; next generation retinal stimulation systems should provide better visual outcomes, higher functionality, and better biocompatibility requirements from previous retinal prostheses. For these aims, the challenges should be addressed in several ways. Firstly, hardware development should focus on decreasing pixel size of the electrodes with novel materials, which will allow reduced perceptual electrical thresholds. Biomimetic, soft, and organic semiconductors could be useful to embedding electrical unit on the retina. Secondly, software improvements should be focused on advanced visual processing algorithms and should facilitate multimodalities for visual information acquisition and transmission. Simplifying natural visual scene with edge detection algorithms will provide better functional outcomes with the current resolution limitations of retinal prostheses (Weiland et al., 2012).

Addition to the electrical rescue of visual sensation of the retina, neuroprotective effect of electrical stimulation should be included to the development processes of the retinal prostheses. In their previous studies, the scientists affiliated with Retina Implant AG develop trans-corneal electrical stimulation (TES), OkuStim, as a potential inducer of upregulation of growth factors and protection of neural retinal cells in RP patients (Schatz et al., 2011). Like OkuStim, other research groups are also investigating electrode arrays for the neuroprotective application. For example, Abbott et al. observed chronic electrical stimulation via microelectrode arrays with low level electrical amplitude preserves photoreceptor function in P23H rats (Abbott et al., 2019).

Third future road for retinal prostheses could be combination electronic devices with other therapy options, such as stem cell and gene therapies. Especially, pluripotent stem cell derived or embryonic neural stem cell derived retinal cell transplantations could be augmented with electrical stimulation systems (Ayton et al., 2020). Positively regulatory effects of chronic electrical stimulation on these types of transplanted cells have been observed in various in vivo studies (Manthey et al., 2017).

In recent years, many research groups have been working on the electrical stimulation of the residual neural networks in the degenerated layers of the unhealthy retina of animal models of RP with retinal prostheses to restore visual function. Number of studies will increase in near future, because of advancements in electronics and material science. However, the most of retinal prosthetic products are still encountering with biocompatibility, complex production, and operational problems. Furthermore, cable connection of the intraocular components of retinal stimulation devices with an external input receiver, processer unit, power supply, or camera is uncomfortable conditions for the patients (Dagnelie, 2012). Newly developed retinal prostheses with photovoltaic interfaces are outstanding devices designed to avoid these limitations. Conjugated polymer-based subretinal implants are becoming more advantageous than conventional retinal prostheses, which mentioned above, with the help of their various features; multiple photostimulation mechanisms, high biocompatibility, mechanical compatibility, and light sensitivity thresholds in daylight conditions (Chenais et al., 2021; Ho et al., 2019).

1.1.3. Neuro-Electronic Interfaces

Electrical stimulation of neurons and recording of neural activity are emerging concepts for bioelectronic interfaces. Neuro-electrical interfaces are basis of novel chronic implants for not only retina, but also central nervous system, spinal cord, sensory systems, and muscles (Hong & Lieber, 2019). Since Hodgkin & Huxley showed action potential generation in neurons, understanding the electrochemical mechanisms which underlay in the behavior of neural systems is important part of the neuroscientific studies. For recording purpose, microelectrodes are most used

interfaces. On the other hand, semiconductor materials which support charge injection by capacitive, pseudocapacitive, and faradaic approaches are great tools for neural stimulation (Han et al., 2020). These semiconductor materials include both organic and inorganic structures, such as titanium nitride, platinum, and iridium oxide (Lawand et al., 2012). Even there are various electrode types are available, variations in neural recording and stimulation persists due to changes in the tissue encapsulating the electrode, degradation of electrode materials, or excitability changes in the neural tissue (S. F. Cogan, 2008).

Molecular responses against neural electronic interfaces are associated with plasticity which driven by complex immune regulation of the neural tissue. These mechanisms and outcome of extrinsic or intrinsic changes in cellular activity are significantly dependent on structure, material, and stimulation type of the electrodes. Especially because of implantation injury, immediate early gene changes drive rapid and transient response in microglia, astrocytes, oligodendrocytes, and neurons, which initiate foreign body response on the implants (Carnicer-Lombarte et al., 2021). Addition to the inflammatory cellular response, this genetic control mechanisms leads to distinct neuronal depolarization patterns which interrupt efficient electrical modulation of the electronic implants. Microglia driven immune response disrupt blood brain barrier, decrease excitability of neurons and leads to fibrosis and gliosis around the implants (Gulino et al., 2019). While neuro-electronic interfaces to modulate neural activity have existed for decades, these complex interactions between neural activity and cellular behavior shows the importance and clinical necessity of production of new methods to affect all these pathological processes synergistically (Hogan et al., 2020).

Despite of the limitations in the clinical applications, neural recording and stimulation technologies have contributed considerably to neuroscience by enabling the extracellular detection and creation of local electrical fields and high-frequency action potentials of single neurons in various tissues (Wellman et al., 2018). Current limitations of neural electronic interfaces, like low interface multiplexity, irreversible chronic immune response and long-term instability of the implants, drives research groups to produce novel neural interface technologies and the fine

tuning of microfabrication of existent technologies to produce high-density electronics (Ray et al., 2019). For this purpose, three types of tissue-interface integration should be achieved: cellular, biomechanical, and electrophysiological (Hong & Lieber, 2019). For cellular integration, non-immunogenic materials or coatings should be used, such as carbon nanotubes (Fairfield, 2018). For biomechanical integration, the materials have similar bending stiffness and Young's moduli with neural tissue should be used for the neural prostheses (Lacour et al., 2016). Lastly, for functional integration of bioelectrical interfaces, electrical stimulation and recording profile of the neural interfaces should be investigated in detail before implantation for any electrophysiological mismatch (Jiang et al., 2018).

Current approach for the design of neural electronic interfaces is mimicking biology of the neural tissue to increase biocompatibility and functionality of the semiconductor materials (Chen et al., 2017). These strategies include designing a stimuli-responsive materials with dynamic stiffness range for easy insertion and superior compression to reduce trauma related tissue response (Sadler et al., 2016). From this perspective, implementing bioinspired neuro-electronic interfaces will increase success of the neural recording and stimulation strategies in forthcoming years (Yang et al., 2019).

As an utmost aim of the neural prostheses, physical treatments of neurological disorders require various strategies to manipulate electrophysiological dynamics of the nervous system with high spatial and temporal precision. Excitability of neurons could be useful only in precise long-term neuromodulation, which should mimic dysfunctional neural structure in the patients with neurological disorders. If it creates localized thermal and electrochemical damage on specific neurons, which will lead to unprecedented neural disorders in tissue stage (Im & Kim, 2020). Beside electrical stimulation, optogenetic, near infrared driven, ultrasonic and magnetic stimulation methods are also alternative modalities for the stimulation and recording in neural structures. However, each of these methods requires nano-scale refinement of electronic structures. The nano-scale refinement of electronic structures will increase spatial and temporal resolution, increase biocompatibility and in vivo functionality. For these reasons, nanoparticle actuators are novel frontier for non-

genetic neurostimulation. Only way to induce cellular stimulation with high spatial and temporal resolution is nanoparticle-based semiconductor structures, which could form active interfaces with neurons without requirement of external energy source or microprocessors (Benfenati & Lanzani, 2021). Unfortunately, clinical applications of nanoparticles require various detailed pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic investigation in in vitro, ex vivo, and in vivo settings. Especially passage through the blood brain barrier, activation capacity on specific neuron types and safe delivery and removal of the nanoparticles via peripheral administration are significant challenges for prospective nanoparticle based physical therapy options of neurological diseases (Anselmo & Mitragotri, 2016).

1.1.4. Quantum Dots based Neurointerfaces

Semiconducting nanoparticles, more commonly known as quantum dots, possess unique size and shape dependent optoelectronic properties (Jacak et al., 2013). In recent years, their unique properties have attracted significant attention in the biomedical field for real-time tissue imaging (Michalet et al., 2005), diagnostics (Jin & Hildebrandt, 2012), theranostics (Li et al., 2019), and drug delivery (Zrazhevskiy et al., 2010), among many other non-medical areas. The optical properties of quantum dots-based interfaces could be changed by size and composition of quantum dots. Their intense brightness, resistance to photobleaching, multiplexing capacity, and high surface-to-volume ratio make them excellent candidates for novel neuro-electronic applications (Wagner et al., 2019). They could also induce neuron like response in specific types of photostimulation (Wang et al., 2019). Their neural stimulation capacity in daylight settings observed in various studies (Bahmani-Jalali, Mohammadi Aria, et al., 2018; Bahmani Jalali et al., 2019). Thanks to the tunable band gap gradients of QDs, they could induce bioelectrical stimulation of neurons with light impulses. Also, quantum confinement effect, high photostability, visible light spectrum absorption of QDs increase their neural electronic stimulation capacity (Pappas et al., 2007). Because of these qualifications, they could be new generation nanoparticles for the neural interfaces.

1.2. Hypothesis and Aims

In this thesis, the author focuses on the investigation of novel quantum dots based retinal prostheses in in vitro neural cell cultures and rats with retinal dystrophy. The retina has selected for in vivo target of the quantum dots based neural interfaces due to it is the neural surface that is often affected by many clinical conditions, such as diabetes mellitus, retinitis pigmentosa, hypertension. Although it is damaged by different pathological mechanisms, the result of its damage is identical, irreversible destruction of the photoreceptor cells. Even many research groups are trying to develop novel retinal prostheses as a solution to the loss of photoreceptor cells in the retina, they cannot produce adequate retinal prosthesis due to biocompatibility, external energy, flexibility, and saccadic movement problems. In this study, with the help of the flexible polyethylene terephthalate (PET) surface with quantum dots based photovoltaic unit, a novel prototype of a retinal prosthesis could be produced. By this way, both biologically safe, stable, and flexible retinal prosthesis without a requirement for an external energy source could be producible. In this study, in vivo and in vitro biocompatibility of quantum dots based retinal prostheses are the focus of interest.

1.2.1. Main Purpose

In this study, both PbS quantum dots and AlSb nanocrystals based retinal prostheses are the subjects of in vivo applications. Additionally, InP quantum dots-based interfaces and modified PbS quantum dots-based interfaces (PTB7-Th:PC71BM) were investigated in in vitro settings. Retinal prosthesis samples produce on ZnO with a thickness of approximately 40 nm by sol-gel method on the ITO (indium tin oxide) coated structure on biocompatible and flexible PET (polyethylene terephthalate) as substrates (Seitz et al., 1998). Then, P3HT:PCBM conjugate polymers prepared with quantum dots mixture on ZnO. In current literature, the closest study to this study is published by Maya-Vetencourt et al. by using PEDOT: PSS and P3HT on silk fibroin substrates (J. F. Maya-Vetencourt et al., 2017), but it is still questionable how this structure works as stated in this article. In the proposed structure based on PbS has strong capacitive current, which could induce neural

action potential in daylight conditions, thanks to the effective absorption of the quantum dots. The main purpose of the study is to test the quantum dots-based retinal prostheses, on in vivo neural cell culture, retinas of healthy (DA/HanRj) and retinal dystrophic rats (RCS/Kyo) to demonstrate biocompatibility, stability, photosensitivity, photoelectrical capacity, and neural functionality of the devices. For this purpose, in both in vitro and in vivo settings, toxicity assays, immunofluorescence staining, and electrophysiological measurements has been applied.

1.2.2. Specific Aims

While main goal of the study is the development of innovative interfaces based on semiconductor quantum dots to provide wireless, light-induced retinal stimulation at in vivo settings, other specific aims of the thesis are summarized as follows:

- Commercially available retinal stimulation devices are based on active faradaic electrodes, which require external power supplies. In the quantum dots based retinal stimulation devices, which are photovoltaic semiconductor interfaces, are passive capacitive electrodes. They work via light falling on the retina, without a need for any external power supply.
- Although several research groups are working on different types of photoconductors, there are no research group working on the quantum dots-based neural interfaces. This study will be first thesis on biocompatible retinal prosthesis based on quantum dots technology.
- Thanks to the high quantum yield and confinement effect of quantum dots-based interfaces, this retinal prosthesis prototype possibly will work under daylight settings.
- This study also will compare different types of quantum dots-based interfaces and similar structures. Comparison of various types of QDs based structures

will give an insight about semiconductor neuro-electronic interfaces in biomedical applications.

- Both AlSb nanocrystal and PbS QDs based neural interfaces will be compared in vivo settings. Also modified PbS QDs and InP QDs-based neural interfaces will be compared with other mentioned structures to understand in vivo biocompatibility and functionality of these neuro-electronic interfaces. By this way, the possibility of quantum dots-based retinal implant prototypes has investigated in in vivo settings for the first time.
- Photovoltaic and photoconductive multiplex interfaces allow the incorporation of quantum dots into the photoelectrode structure, which help to develop biocompatible, non-toxic, flexible, and stable microelectrodes. Under the daylight, these photoelectrodes could depolarize neural membrane to produce an extracellular current that could modulate action potential generation in retinal neurons.

Chapter 2

MATERIALS AND METHODS

During the investigation of neural and retinal stimulation with QDs based interfaces, the workflow diagram, which is as below, followed:

Figure 2.1: General workflow for the investigation of the neural and retinal stimulation with QDs based interfaces. Fabrication and characterization of QDs based interfaces (top left), in vitro biocompatibility experiments (top right), in vitro electrophysiology measurements (bottom left), and in vivo biocompatibility and electrophysiology experiments (bottom right).

2.1. Fabrication and Characterization of QDs based Interfaces

To produce retinal and neural interfaces for the experiments, various types of quantum dots and P3HT:PCBM conjugate polymers will be coated on the ITO (indium tin oxide) coated structure on biocompatible and flexible PET (polyethylene terephthalate) substrates by sol-gel method (Seitz et al., 1998).

Synthesis of PbS Quantum Dots based Interfaces

To remove unwanted media, 1-Octadecine (ODE) is heated to 80°C under vacuum for 24 hours in a volume of 10 ml (Barkhouse et al., 2011). Subsequently, Bis(trimethylsilyl)sulfide (TMS) is added to ODE and a mixture of oleic acid, lead oxide (PbO) and ODE as a separate mixture will be heated under vacuum at 95°C for 16 hours and it will then be placed under Argon. The temperature of this mixture will be raised to 125°C and the TMS/ODE mixture will be injected. After injection, the temperature will be reduced to 95°C and the vial will be allowed to gradually cool to 36°C. After synthesis of quantum dots, the nanocrystals will be precipitated by centrifugation with distilled acetone. After discarding the supernatant, the precipitate will be redispersed in toluene. The nanocrystals will again be precipitated under centrifugation with acetone, dried and finally dispersed in toluene. The PbS nanocrystals will then be precipitated with methanol and the supernatant removed and dried under vacuum. It will then be redispersed in toluene.

Since the produced photoelectrodes will be implanted into the retina with a certain curvature, the substrate structure will be advantageous to be flexible. Therefore, ITO (indium tin oxide) on biocompatible and flexible PET (polyethylene terephthalate) will be used as substrate (Figure 2.2) (Seitz et al., 1998). 40 nm zinc oxide (ZnO) structure will be coated on this structure using sol-gel method. For this purpose, the ITO coated glass will be coated with 96% 2-methoxyethanol and 4% ethanolamine spin in zinc acetate solution (Hau et al., 2008). Then, the ZnO sol-gel films will be heat-treated to 250 °C for 5 minutes to crystallize the film. For the active layer in which the light will be absorbed effectively, a triple hybrid mixture will be obtained by adding 6% by weight of PbS core type nanocrystals in the binary mixture of P3HT:PCBM. Similar to

P3HT:PCBM, PTB7-Th:PC71BM will be mixed with PbS core type nanocrystals. This triple mixture will be formed by spinning on 40 nm ZnO at 2000 rpm. The final film will be kept at 155 °C to ensure that the formed film is fully cured. Light will be absorbed effectively by PbS nanocrystals, and P3HT and PCBM molecules will separate the current into electrons, will create an effective capacitive current.

Figure 2.2: PET/ITO/ZnO/P3HT:PbS QDs:PCBM based retinal prosthesis in macro-scale (left), micro-scale (middle), and nano-scale with energy bandwidths (right).

Synthesis of ALSb Nanocrystal based Interfaces

$\text{Sb}[\text{N}(\text{Si}(\text{Me})_3)_2]_3$ was synthesized by the metathesis reaction between SbCl_3 and $\text{LiN}(\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_3)_2$. 38 mmol $\text{LiN}(\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_3)_2$ were dissolved in 80 mL of diethyl ether in the dark and cooled down to 0 °C. 13 mmol SbCl_3 dissolved in the mixture of 2 mL of THF, and 8 mL of diethyl ether was slowly added to the main reaction flask. The resulting white turbid solution was stirred for 12 hours, centrifuged to remove LiCl , and filtered through a 0.45 μm PTFE filter. After the removal of the solvents under vacuum, the residue was dissolved in hexane, filtered through a 0.45 μm PTFE filter again, and dried under vacuum. A yellow solid product was obtained after the complete removal of hexane. The reaction yield was ~85%. The product was dispersed in 22 mL of toluene (0.5 mmol/ml) and stored under an inert atmosphere in the dark at -40 °C. Synthesis of ALSb QDs. First, 0.16 mmol AlCl_3 , 300 μL (0.16 mmol) $\text{Sb}[\text{N}(\text{Si}(\text{Me})_3)_2]_3$, and 640 μL TOP were mixed in the glovebox. Then, 1 mL of 1 M LiEt_3BH solution and 2.4 mL of OAM were mixed and added into the main reaction flask. The color of the solution became dark immediately after the injection. The solution was heated to 280 °C, kept for 20 min, and then cooled down to room temperature. 1 mL OA was added to the solution to neutralize the excessive super hydride and attach oleate ligands to the ALSb surface. Then, the solution was centrifuged at 5 °C at 5000 rpm for 10 times to separate

QDs from the impurities. Finally, to collect the QDs, ethanol/acetone (1:1) was added to the QDs solution, centrifuged at 9000 rpm, and dispersed in hexane for further characterization. Multiple-sized QDs were provided by taking three aliquots at different reaction times of 1, 3, and 20 minutes (Bahmani-Jalali et al., 2019).

Synthesis of InP QDs based Interfaces

Indium phosphate/ Zinc sulfate quantum dots were synthesized by hot injection procedure. For the core synthesis, firstly, 56 mg stearic acid (SA), 86 mg zinc undecylenate and 96 mg hexadecylamine (HDA) were mixed in a three-neck flask with 6 ml 1-Octadecene (ODE). Afterwards 44 mg indium chloride (InCl_3) into the solution in nitrogen atmosphere. The solution was heated to 120 °C and evacuated 20 minutes to provide oxygen and water-free reaction medium. Then, the solution was refilled with a nitrogen atmosphere and heated to 230 °C. Then, 1 ml of Tris(trimethylsilyl) phosphine $\text{P}(\text{TMS})_3$ stock solution was injected to the solution, and it was kept at 230 °C 20 minutes. Before the shelling process, the solution was cooled down to room temperature and half of the solution was taken and labeled as core solution. For preparing InP/ZnS at room temperature, 54 mg zinc diethyldithiocarbamate and 2 ml ODE were added into the solution, respectively. After that, the solution was heated up to 180 °C and stirred 30 minutes. The solution was cooled down to room temperature and purified by washing toluene and ethanol. At the final stage, QDs were redispersed in toluene (Bahmani-Jalali, Melikov, et al., 2018).

For synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles, tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH) dissolved in ethanol was slowly added to the solution of zinc acetate dihydrate dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). After 1h stirring at room temperature, the solution was washed twice and dispersed in ethanol at a concentration of 50 mg/ml. The ITO coated glass substrates were first cleaned by sonicating in detergent solution, deionized water, acetone, and isopropanol consecutively for 15 minutes each. The cleaned substrates were applied 15 min of UV ozone treatment before moving to layer depositions. Titanium dioxide layer on ITO was formed using a TiO_2 paste via doctor blading followed by annealing at 400 °C for 1 hour. ZnO layer was deposited by spin-coating the 50 mg/ml ZnO nanoparticles solution at 2000 rpm and baked at 100 °C for 30

minutes. The InP/ZnS core/shell QDs film was formed by spin coating its 60 mg/ml solution in toluene at 2000 rpm. For multilayer coating, each layer was treated with 3-mercaptopropionic acid in methanol and then rinsed with methanol, both spin-cast at 2000 rpm, before moving to the coating of next QDs layer. After the multilayer coating, the QD film was baked at 100 °C for 30 min (Karatum et al., 2019).

Characterization of QDs based Interfaces

For characterization, optical absorption spectrum and photoluminescence radiation spectrum will be measured with FLS1000 Spectrometer (Edinburgh Instruments) located in Koç University Surface Research Laboratories (KUYTAM). Microstructural and morphological characterizations of the sample were performed using Zeiss Ultra Plus field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) equipped with energy dispersive X-Ray spectrometer (EDS).

2.2. In vitro Biocompatibility and Electrophysiology Experiments

2.2.1. Primary Neural Cell Isolations

Ethical Statement

All experimental procedures have been approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committees of Koç University (for Wistar Albino rat embryos, Approval No: 2019.HADYEK.023; for Dark Agouti & RCS/Kyo adult rats, Approval No: 2018.HADYEK.018; For Wistar Albino adult rats, Approval No: 2020.HADYEK.017) according to Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on Protection of Animals Used for Scientific Purposes and the Republic of Turkey 5199 Animal Protection Law, Article 9 and 17 (Appendix 1).

Primary Neuron Isolation

Due to the difficulty of retinal ganglion cell culture, hippocampal neurons have selected as in vitro neural model for photostimulation with retinal prosthesis (Meyer-Franke et

al., 1995). Hippocampal regions were extracted from decapitated E15-E18 Wistar Albino rats and were placed immediately in ice-cold Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS, Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA). The hippocampi were incubated in 0.25% Trypsin-EDTA solution (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA) with 2% DNase-I supplement (NeoFroxx, Einhausen, Germany) for 20 minutes in a 37 °C incubator. Then the cells were centrifuged, and the supernatant was changed with Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium/Nutrient Mixture F-12 (DMEM/F12 Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Heat Inactivated, GE Healthcare, IL, USA) and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA). DMEM/F12 was removed and Neurobasal Medium (NBM, Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA) supplemented with B27, L-glutamine, β -mercaptoethanol, glutamate (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA) was added to the cell pellet. The cells were triturated and were passed through a 70 μ m cell strainer. The homogenous cell solution was seeded in poly-D-lysine (PDL, Sigma-Aldrich, MO, USA) coated substrates. After 3-days incubation of cells on substrates in a 37 °C incubator with 5% carbon dioxide, the media of the cells on substrates were changed with NBM supplemented with cytosine arabinoside (Sigma-Aldrich, MO, USA) to inhibit growth of glial cells. After 24-hour incubation with cytosine arabinoside, the media were changed with NBM and the substrates with the hippocampal neurons used for experiments.

Primary Astrocyte and Microglia Isolation

The cortical tissues were extracted from decapitated E15-E18 Wistar Albino rats and were placed immediately in ice-cold HEPES buffered DMEM. The cortices were incubated in 0.25% Trypsin-EDTA solution (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA) with 2% DNase-I supplement (NeoFroxx, Einhausen, Germany) for 25 minutes in a 37 °C incubator. Then the cells were centrifuged, and the supernatant was changed with DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS and 1% penicillin/streptomycin. Then cell suspension filtered through 120 μ m and 45 μ m nylon mesh filters, respectively. After filtration, cell suspension seeded to 250 ml non-coated culture flasks in 10 ml DMEM with FBS. The cells incubated at 37°C, 5% CO₂, and changed their medium at Day 3. At day 6, cell culture medium changed again, and the flasks shook overnight at 80 rpm

in room temperature. The detached cells taken to the other tube and centrifuged and seeded with 10 ml DMEM with FBS for microglia culture. The attached cells were washed with phosphate buffered saline (PBS, Gibco, MA, USA) one time and added 10 ml DMEM with FBS on attached cells in flask for astrocyte culture. For both astrocyte and microglia cell cultures, cells have cultured at 37°C, 5% CO₂ until reach to confluency. After confluency, the cells trypsinized and seeded to poly-d-lysine (PDL, Sigma-Aldrich, MO, USA) coated flasks in DMEM with FBS (Appendix 2).

2.2.2. *In vitro* Toxicity Assays

In this study, the author has used two different types of in vitro cytotoxicity assay: 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay, which shows mitochondrial activity via NAD(P)H-dependent cellular oxidoreductase enzyme presence, and CellTiter-Glo (CTG) assay, which shows presence of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) in metabolically active cells.

MTT Toxicity Assay

To investigate cell viability and cell proliferation of primary neurons and primary astrocytes on our biointerfaces, MTT viability assay is used. The growth medium was prepared using Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium with 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum and antibiotics. MTT cell viability assay (ab211091, Abcam, Cambridge, UK) was utilized to evaluate biocompatibility of our biointerface. The devices were sterilized first by cleaning with 70% ethanol followed by air-drying. The surface was further sterilized under UV irradiation for 30 min. The substrates were placed in 6-well plates. Primary neurons were seeded (5×10^5 cells per well) on the substrates in DMEM with 10% FBS and after 48 hours of incubation, the medium was replaced with 1 mL of MTT solution (5 mg/mL in PBS, pH = 7.4) and 4 mL of DMEM mixture per well. Concurrently, primary astrocytes were seeded (2.5×10^5 cells per well) on the substrates in DMEM with 10% FBS and after 72 hours of incubation, which is the sufficient time to induce innate immune response, the medium was replaced with 1 mL of MTT solution (5 mg/mL in PBS, pH = 7.4) and 4 mL of DMEM mixture per well. Then, for an additional 4 hours, the cells were incubated at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ atmosphere. The

medium was vacuumed from each well and substrates were transferred to an empty 6-well plate. In each well, 1:1 mixture of DMSO and ethanol was added to dissolve the formazan crystals. The solution was transferred to a 96-well plate and the absorbance was measured at 600 nm (for background) and at 690 nm (for absorbance) with Synergy H1 Microplate Reader (Bio-Tek Instruments, VT, USA). The relative cell viability was calculated as follows: $\text{viability} = (\text{OD}_{\text{sample}}/\text{OD}_{\text{control}}) \times 100$. The optical density (OD) of the sample was obtained from the cells grown on a photoelectrode, and the OD of control was obtained from the cells grown on the ITO substrates.

CTG Toxicity Assay

Primary neurons are seeded on the samples and incubated at 37 °C for two days in a complete Neurobasal Medium for 1 h at 37 °C, 5% CO₂. The relative viabilities of cells are detected by CellTiter-Glo® Luminescent Cell Viability Assay (Promega, Mannheim, Germany) which is a method used for detecting the number of viable cells depending on the amount of ATP in alive cells. Briefly, at the end of 1 h treatment of Ruthenium, the equal volume of CellTiter-Glo® Reagent to treatment medium was added in each well. To improve cell lysis, plate was put on orbital shaker for 2 min then allowed for 10 minutes at room temperature to stabilize luminescence signals. After incubation, cell viability was measured with a luminometer. As a background control, luminescence signals from only cell culture medium were measured. The relative cell viability is determined by comparing with the untreated control group.

2.2.3. Immunofluorescence Staining Technique

The interfaces placed on 6-well culture dishes (Corning, NY, USA). 5×10^5 primary neurons in 2 ml plating NBM seeded to each well with QDs samples ($n = 3$). After seeding, neurons incubated for 24 hours in 37 °C 5% CO₂ incubator. For cell fixation, primary neural cells on QD samples treated with 4% paraformaldehyde for 20 minutes. After three times washes with PBS, the samples incubated with 0.1% TritonX-100 in PBS for 8 minutes. Then the samples incubated with Superblock (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA) for 10 minutes at room temperature and incubated with 1:200 diluted anti-NeuN primary antibody (ab177487; Abcam, MA, USA) in blocking

solution at 4 °C for cell cytoskeleton staining. After overnight incubation with primary antibody, cells washed with PBS three times and incubated with 1:200 diluted anti-rabbit FITC-conjugated secondary antibody (ab6717; Abcam, MA, USA) in PBS for 90 minutes at 37 °C. Afterward the samples washed three times with PBS, counterstained with 406-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) in mounting medium for staining of nuclei and sealed. All immunofluorescence images of samples taken with confocal microscope (DMi 8 SP8; Leica, Wetzlar, Germany). Maximum projection images and 3D videos of the neurons on samples reconstructed with LAS-X software (Leica, Wetzlar, Germany).

2.2.4. Whole Cell Patch Clamp Technique

Experiments were performed by the EPC 800 patch clamp amplifier (HEKA Elektronik GmbH, Pfalz, Germany). The AISb integrated and control devices were cleaned with 70% ethanol solution and incubated for 3 days in DI water. The pulled patch pipettes of 4-6 M Ω were utilized to carry out the whole-cell patch clamp experiment. Extracellular medium (modified aCSF) was prepared as mentioned in the photocurrent measurement section. The internal cellular medium was prepared by mixing 140 mM KCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM HEPES, 10 mM ethylene glycol-bis(β -aminoethyl ether)-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid (EGTA), 2 mM Mg-ATP in water and the pH was calibrated to 7.2-7.3 using 1 M KOH. Patch pipettes were filled with the intracellular solution to achieve the whole-cell patch. A digital camera integrated Olympus T2 upright microscope was used to patch and monitor the cells. The blue LED (M450LP1, Thorlabs Inc, NJ, USA) was used as the light source. The LED system was driven by DC2200 - High-Power 1-Channel LED Driver with Pulse Modulation (Thorlabs Inc, NJ, USA). The solutions will be used in whole cell patch clamp technique have described below:

Extracellular Solution (Artificial Cerebrospinal Fluid, aCSF): 140 mM NaCl, 3 mM KCl, 1 mM MgCl₂, 2 mM CaCl₂, 10 mM HEPES, 10 mM Glucose. Osmolarity adjusted to 290 mOsm and pH adjusted to 7.4 with NaOH.

Intracellular Solution (ICS): 140 mM KCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM HEPES, 10 mM EGTA, 2 mM Mg-ATP. Osmolarity adjusted to 270 mOsm and pH adjusted to 7.3 with KOH.

2.3. *In vivo Toxicity, Electrophysiology, and Behavioral Tests*

The retinal prostheses were placed in subretinal areas of rats with retinal dystrophy under the anesthesia. Then retinal implantation procedure applied to the control group to establish a sham group, except for retinal implant placement (J. F. Maya-Vetencourt et al., 2017). After implantation operation, daily follow-up performed, and anti-inflammatory and anti-infection treatments applied for potential post-operative inflammation and local infections.

Behavioral tests were performed on retinal dystrophy and control groups after retinal implant operation to measure the effectiveness of the retinal prostheses. During behavioral tests, the light/dark room test, and the Y-shaped conditional maze, performed to understand visual perception of rats (M. Davies et al., 2007; G. T. Prusky et al., 2002). After these tests, electroretinogram (ERG) and visual evoked potential related electroencephalography from the visual cortex (VEP-EEG) of rats have measured under anesthesia (Christine T. Nguyen et al., 2016).

Figure 2.3: Immunofluorescence images of 3 weeks old Dark Agouti (a) and RCS/Kyo (b) rat retinas. The retinas stained with DAPI (blue), a nucleus marker, NeuN (green), neural cell marker, and rhodopsin (red), a photoreceptor cell marker.

2.3.1. *Selection of Animal Models*

The rat experiments contain behavioral and electrophysiological examination for retinal implants on rat model of retinitis pigmentosa. RCS/Kyo rats have selected as retinitis

pigmentosa rat model in the experiments. In RCS/Kyo rats, MERTK (-/-) mutation leads to absence of MER receptor tyrosine kinase protein. Absence of MER receptor tyrosine kinase inhibits phagocytosis in RPE. Consequently, increased number of apoptotic cells in subretinal space leads to complete photoreceptor cell death at 3 weeks of age (Figure 2.3) (D’Cruz et al., 2000). Dark Agouti (DA/HanRj) rats used as a control counterpart strain with a good visual acuity (G. T. Prusky et al., 2002). RCS/Kyo rats from NBRP (Kyoto, Japan) are used as rat model of retinitis pigmentosa and Dark Agouti from Janvier Labs (Le Genest Saint Isle, France) were selected as non-transgenic equivalent with high visual perception for RCS/Kyo rats. The rats passed from physical examinations for visual and behavioral tasks before experiments starts (Figure 2.4). After 2 months inhabitation period behavioral experiments started. Schema of experiments is as below:

Figure 2.4: Time Schedule of In vivo Behavioral, Electrophysiological and Biocompatibility Experiments for Retinal Prostheses.

2.3.2. Implantation of Retinal Prostheses

Figure 2.5: Subretinal implantation Operation for the Retinal Prostheses. Dimensions of the retinal implant (top left). Position of rat during the subretinal implantation operation. Injection of physiological saline between retina and retinal pigment epithelium (bottom left) and implantation of retinal prosthesis in the subretinal space (bottom right).

The biointerface embedded on PET with 1 mm x 1.5 mm x 50 μm dimensions and sterilized with H_2O_2 plasma sterilizer (STERRAD 100NX Sterilization System, Advanced Sterilization Products, CA, USA). Surgical procedures were carried out in a sterile room by using an ophthalmic surgical microscope. Three-month-old male rats were injected meloxicam (1 mg/kg) for analgesia and anaesthetized with intraperitoneal injection of xylazine (5 mg/kg) and ketamine (33 mg/kg). After induction of anesthesia, the ocular surface was irrigated with 0.5% povidone iodine solution following

anesthesia. A 2-mm wide limbal-based conjunctival flap was created 2 mm posterior to the temporal limbus in the right eye of the rat. Tenon's capsule was dissected with blunt tipped 10 mm Westcott scissors. A 1.5-mm wide lamellar incision through the sclera and the choroid was made with a straight 20G MVR blade by carefully avoiding visible major vessels and the lateral rectus muscle on the incision area. The lamellar incision was halted when subretinal space was reached by remarking the transparent retinal tissue. The temporal location of the incision according to the posterior pole of the eye was checked with indirect ophthalmoscopy through a 90-diopter fundus lens (Volk, OH, USA). Physiological saline solution was gently injected into the subretinal space to detach the neurosensorial retina with an angled blunt tipped 30G Rycroft anterior chamber cannula. The implant was inserted into the subretinal space by slide-manuevering through the incision with the biointerface facing the retina (Figure 2.5). The positioning of the implant between optic nerve and the incision site, and the proper reflection of the biointerface was checked with indirect ophthalmoscopy (Omega 500, Heine GmbH, Gliching, Germany). The edges of the sclerotomy and conjunctiva were sutured separately with an absorbable 8-0 vicryl suture. At the end of the surgery, a final indirect ophthalmoscopy was performed to evaluate the positioning of the implant (Figure 2.6).

Figure 2.6: In vivo observation of the localization of the subretinal implants. Foveal localization (left), adjacent to optic nerve (middle), and sub-RPE localization (right).

2.3.3. Electrophysiological Examinations

Electroretinography (ERG)

The electroretinogram (ERG) is the summed, time-varied potential of the retina which have a repeatable waveform to a light stimulation (Hanitzsch, 1993; Quintana et al., 2016). It is a noninvasive technique that allows the assessment of functional integrity of the retina. The ERG recordings are biopotentials acquired in the corneal surface as a response of retinal tissue against controlled light stimuli. The signals recorded in ERG are affected due to morphology in the presence of pathologies and are used to evaluate the integrity of the different retinal cell types (Quintana et al., 2016). ERG responses are recorded with an active extracellular electrode usually positioned either on the cornea, in the vitreous, or at different levels inside the retina.

In ERG, electrical signals that are produced due to light stimulus will flow through two principles, via local and remote pathways. The electrical current triggered by light stimulus in a local pathway flows through entirely within the retina, whereas the current flowing through remote pathway through the vitreous and anterior ocular tissue and returns to the retina through the sclera, the choroid, and the retinal pigment epithelium layer (Perlman, 2015).

ERG measurements affected by deepness of anesthesia, as the level of anesthesia was deepened, gradual removal of the different components could be observed. Each component of ERG contributes to form the waveforms of the recordings and they are associated with certain patterns on ERG. For example, the negative a-wave is the leading edge of the negative P-III component; the positive b-wave reflects the summation of P-II and P-III, whereas the slow c-wave is the summation of P-I and P-II (Perlman, 2015). The ERG recordings have different components of waveforms which each corresponds to a characteristics of signal response within retinal layer. In a dark-adapted environment, progressively changing layer of ERG can be identified from different portions of the waveform (Perlman, 2015). The components of the ERG waveform have been distinguished and related to the sequence of neuronal activation in

the retina, irregularities in characteristic waveform can be associated with different pathologies in the related retinal cell layers.

The earliest signal is generated by the initial changes in the stacked membranous photopigment molecules of the photoreceptors due to the physiological changes caused by the action of the light also called early receptor potential. This is reflected on ERG as a positive R_1 deflection followed by a negative R_2 deflection. Following the early receptor potential deflections, again rod- and cone-type photoreceptors contribute a cornea-negative waveform called a-wave (Perlman, 2015). The succeeding waveform is the cornea-positive b-wave. It is indicated that the b-wave originates in retinal cells that are post-synaptic to the photoreceptors. This waveform is attributed to change in the transmembrane potential of Müller glia cells which is influenced by changes in the extracellular potassium. Yet, these cells are glial cells and have no synaptic connection to the retinal cells. Therefore, Müller glia cell potential changes are not directly light induced. the b-wave of the ERG is a result of the light-evoked depolarization of the ON bipolar neurons (Stockton & Slaughter, 1989). In addition, the ganglion cell action pulse is associated with b-wave (Bui & Fortune, 2004). The consequence of these events is to bring about a Müller glia cell response. And it is the latter that is the source of the b-wave. Müller glia cells can contribute to a b-wave from either cone or rod receptors separately (Perlman, 2015). The c-wave is generated by the retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) as a consequence of interaction with the rods (Noell, 1954).

The oscillatory potentials are small amplitude waves that appear in the light-adapted b-wave (Gauvin et al., 2016). Although they are known to be generated in the inner retinal layer and require a bright stimulus, the exact cellular origin of oscillating potentials and the significance of each wave is unknown. In some studies, it has been suggested that they would represent inner retinal potentials generated by neuronal interactions that might involve bipolar, amacrine, and/or ganglion cells (Heynen et al., 1985; Wachtmeister, 1986; Yonemura & Kawasaki, 1979).

Visual Evoked Potential (VEP) - Electroencephalography (EEG)

The term visually evoked potential (VEP) refers to electrical potentials recorded from visual cortex that have been extracted from the electroencephalogram (EEG) by signal averaging. VEPs are used to quantify the functional integrity of the optic nerves, pathways to the visual cortex of the brain, and occipital cortex in clinical context (Creel, 2019). A VEP can often be seen in the background EEG recorded from the occipital scalp following a flash of light. This technique of extracting a relevant signal from random noise is one of the oldest applications of computer technology and is based upon adding the electrical activity for set-time periods, called signal averaging (Creel, 2019).

EEG waveforms may be characterized based on their location, amplitude, frequency, morphology, continuity, synchrony, symmetry, and reactivity. However, the most frequently used method to classify EEG waveforms is by its frequency. EEG waves are named based on their frequency range using Greek numerals. The most commonly studied waveforms include delta (0.5 to 4Hz); theta (4 to 7Hz); alpha (8 to 12Hz); sigma (12 to 16Hz) and beta (13 to 30Hz) (Nayak & Anilkumar, 2020). In rats, the aim is to investigate the integrity of the visual pathway through measuring the signal transmission via VEP-EEG on visual cortex.

Subjects with the normal visual acuity produces similar evoked potentials using pattern reversal stimulus. There is a prominent negative component at peak time of about 75 ms (N1), a larger amplitude positive component at about 100 ms (P1 or P100), and a more variable negative component at about 140ms (N2). The major component of the VEP is the large positive wave peaking at about 100ms (Creel, 2019). It is not possible to attribute different components of the VEP to specific cell classes, thus changes anywhere along the visual pathway could affect the VEP waveform through interpretations of variations due to different pathologies along the visual pathway. Nevertheless, the VEP is a useful non-invasive measure of visual performance and visual pathway integrity (Christine T Nguyen et al., 2016).

Detailed Simultaneous VEP-EEG and ERG Measurement Procedure

VEP-EEG and ERG data collected by using AcqKnowledge software of BIOPAC MP160 data acquisition and analysis platform. Before starting to collect data, VEP-EEG and ERG recording parameters are set for the data acquisition and Use a dim test-flash to assess whether electrode placement is satisfactory (Christine T Nguyen et al., 2016). ERS100C amplifier unit (BIOPAC, CA, USA) have used in 20000x gain, 3.0 kHz low pass filter, 1.0 Hz high pass filter settings. As signal range obtained in both ERG and VEP-EEG has a very low amplitude, signal amplification for ERG and VEP-EEG with setting a signal gain parameter for the better resolution of recording is recommended to set between 5000x and 50000x. Conventional bandwidth of the clinical EEG focuses on the analysis of waveforms ranging from 0.5Hz to 70Hz (Nayak & Anilkumar, 2020). A low-frequency filter setting higher than 1 Hz should not be used routinely to attenuate slow-wave artifacts in the record. Vital information may be lost when pathologic activity in the delta range is present. Similarly, a setting lower than 70 Hz for the high-frequency filters can change spikes and other pathologic discharges into unrecognizable forms and can cause muscle artifact to resemble spikes. Sampling rate for both ERG and VEP-EEG are set to be 4 kHz over a 650 ms and 10 kHz over a 250 ms recording window, respectively. Additionally, 10 ms of delay can be added before actual recording starts. Band-pass filtering is set to 3-3,000 Hz for ERG and VEP-EEG recordings. Once everything is set for the data acquisition, signals are collected over a range of luminous flashes to elicit different waveforms of the ERG using a light stimulant (Christine T Nguyen et al., 2016). For example, as rod photoreceptors elicits voltage response under dim light conditions, to obtain rod b-wave response on ERG, light stimulants with lower energy intensities are used.

Alligator clip attached silver wire-loops are used as electrode leads. ERG negative electrodes that forming a small loop to gently contact the rat cornea, which are positioned to lightly touch the central corneal surface using a micromanipulator attached to a stereotaxic arm. Likewise, loop-shaped silver wire retinal positive electrode is inserted through slightly popping the rat's eye out and placed on retinal region at the back of the orbital space. During the time the rat is anesthetized, the eye is treated with 0.5% tropicamide, 25 mg/ml phenylephrine and 1% cyclopentolate as mydriatic agents.

Additionally, 0.5% proparacaine, viscous carbomer gel and electrolyte gel applied to enable conductivity of eye surface without drying and pain.

Before getting started with permanent electrode implantation on rat's visual cortex, appropriate anesthesia agent with an intraperitoneal injection is applied. Scalp of the rat shaved in the surgical area and rat placed on thermal pad to preserve physiological temperature and avoid hypothermia. Determination of the localization for the visual cortex in rat brain made with the help of the rat brain stereotaxic atlas (Paxinos & Watson, 2006). The center of V1 area have selected as recording place for permanent screw electrodes. To expose skull, operator used aseptic procedure tools to make a longitudinal skin incision on the midline of the head skin and carefully, drill small burr holes manually using a micro hand drill at 7 mm behind the bregma and 3 mm lateral to the midline. Implantation of screw electrodes is done through drilling the skull into the cortex, touching the cortex to a depth of approximately 0.5 mm. Each EEG electrode only yields voltage information about the difference of electrical activity between two positions on the cortex, it is important to obtain the difference between the electric potentials in its correct location and in the location of the reference electrode where the electric potential near the reference electrode is neutral (Lei & Liao, 2017). The implantation of a reference screw electrode has done in the midline 3 mm rostral to the bregma. Dental cement applied to close the open skull and fix the screws. To place grounding electrode, one electrode inserted in 2-5 mm of the ground needle electrode subcutaneously into the tail of rat. The primary purpose of the ground is to prevent power line noise from interfering with the small biopotential signals of interest (Creel, 2019). To alleviate background noise that interfere the data collection, a Faraday cage has placed in a way to cover experimental setup.

For flicker light application for the ERG and VEP-EEG, the light intensity on corneal surface of the rat is $500 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$. Wavelength spectrum peak values for the light sources as below (Figure 2.7):

- White LED = 590 nm
- Green LED = 530 nm
- Blue LED = 455 nm

Figure 2.7: Spectrums of the light sources, white (left), green (middle), blue (right).

In brief, rats anesthetized with isoflurane after general examination. After the behavioral tests, visual evoked potentials (VEP-EEG) measured with electroretinography (ERG), for this reason electrodes inserted into the rat's visual cortex and retina with the aid of a stereotaxic frame. During this procedure, VEP-EEG alligator electrodes attached to previously placed chronic VEP-EEG implants and ERG alligator electrodes connected to custom-made silver loops in cornea and retina of rat. During the measurement, the eyes of the rat will be kept open with the help of silver loops and kept wet with the mentioned gel mixture. During all anesthesia, the body temperature of the animal will be kept at 37 °C with the help of an electric blanket. The condition and wound healing of the animals undergoing ERG and VEP measurements monitored postoperatively daily and systemic Meloxicam as an analgesic and systemic Oxytetracycline as an antibiotic given daily after invasive operations.

During procedure for VEP-EEG and ERG, custom-made the ERG active/inactive and VEP-EEG active/inactive electrodes by attaching silver wire and an alligator clip to an electrode lead, respectively. For the 4 custom-made electrodes, the male end from the electrode lead extension cut. 1 cm of the outer polytetrafluoroethylene insulation coating removed with a scalpel blade to ensure the inner wire is not damaged. The ERG inactive electrodes prepared by cutting a 70 mm length of silver wire (0.3 mm thickness) and formed a loop ~ 8 mm in diameter to encircle the rat eye. A uniform circle prepared by shaping the loop on a 1 ml pipette tip. VEP-EEG inactive electrodes pre-fashioned by cutting a 70 mm length of silver and formed an ellipse ~8 mm in lengthwise diameter to hook onto rat incisors. The ERG active electrodes pre-fashioned by cutting a 30 mm length of silver wire and formed a small loop to gently contact the rat cornea (~1-2 mm in diameter). Electrodes (2 ERG active, 2 ERG inactive, 1 VEP

inactive) securely attached to the electrode lead by entwining the silver with the exposed inner wire. Excess exposed metal insulated with masking tape to reduce photovoltaic artifacts. On the ERG inactive electrodes, a small piece of hook-and-loop fastener ($\sim 5 \text{ mm} \times 20 \text{ mm}$) stuck to the masking tape to enable stable attachment to the rodent neck strap. Alligator clips attached to the inner wire of the electrode leads to make the VEP active electrodes. Prior to recordings, the exposed surfaces of the silver wires (i.e., the inactive ring and active tip) electroplated with chloride using a 9V DC source for 20 sec to improve signal conduction. The silver tip of the ERG electrode wire, which is acting as the anode of a primary cell, immersed into normal saline; the other end of this electrode wire connected to the positive terminal of a 9V battery. Cathode wire connected to the negative terminal of the battery and immerse the other end into saline as well. After 20 seconds, system disconnected and observed to the silver tip of the ERG electrode wire was coated evenly in white color. As an important point, new ERG electrodes prepared for each experimental session (up to 8 hours) to ensure patency of the chloride coating.

Wavelength (nm)	Light Intensity ($\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$)	Light Duration (ms)	Frequency (Hz)
590 (White)*	500 *	500	20
530 (Green)	250	200	10
455 (Blue)	125	100 *	5
	62.5	50	2
	31.2	20	1 *
	15.6	10	0.5
	7.8	5	
	3.9	2	
	1.9	1	

Table 2.1: Dim Light Stimulation Parameters for ERG and VEP-EEG Measurements

The rats prior to recordings dark adapted in a dark room. Near infrared red light, with the help of dim red light-emitting diode (LED; $17.4 \text{ cd}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$, $\lambda \text{ max} = 600 \text{ nm}$), used for illumination of the system (Figure 2.8), because it is invisible to retinas of rats. Rats anesthetized by intraperitoneal injection of ketamine/xylazine (60:5 mg/kg) solution. To confirm the depth of anesthesia, paw pinch reflex has checked. To maintain sedation, additional doses administered after 50 minutes if it is necessary. For additional topical anesthesia, one drop of 0.5% proxymetacaine and carbomer gel applied to each eye and

opposite eye closed with aluminum foil to decrease drying. For pupil dilation, mixture of mentioned mydriatics applied to each eye.

Light Power (mA)	Light Intensity (mW/cm²)	Light Duration (ms)	Frequency (Hz)
2000	672	500	20
1500	336	200	10
1000	168	100 *	5
500	84	50	2
300 *	50 *	20	1 *
200	33	10	0.5
150	25		0.2
100	16		0.1
75	12.5		
50	8		
25	4		
10	1.6		
5	0.8		

Table 2.2: Bright Light Stimulation Parameters for ERG and VEP-EEG Measurements

The rat placed on the VEP-EEG and ERG platform in front of the light source in the Faraday cage. The heating platform attached to the Faraday cage has been used to maintain body temperature. The rat secured with stereotaxic frame and placed firmly but not tightly with strips. The inactive VEP-EEG electrode hooked around bottom incisors of anesthetized rat. the ERG inactive electrodes placed by encircling the scleral ring non-invasively around the eye's equator. Same procedures applied for the contralateral eye. The VEP-EEG active electrodes placed by attaching alligator clips to stainless-steel screws pre-implanted on the skull. A small drop of 1% carboxymethylcellulose sodium added on cornea prior to placement of the ERG active electrode to improve signal quality. The viscose fluid also helps maintain corneal hydration throughout experimentation to minimize the formation of desiccation-type cataract in rodents. Also, a small drop of 1% carboxymethylcellulose sodium placed on the lower incisors to improve contact of the VEP inactive electrode and thus signal quality. The ERG active electrodes touched lightly to the central corneal surface by using a micromanipulator attached to a stereotaxic arm. 2-5 mm of the ground needle electrode inserted subcutaneously into the rat tail. Light source aligned to the level of

the rat's eye and ensured the rat's eye receive even illumination from the light source. The faraday cage closed to reduce extraneous noise.

Figure 2.8: VEP-EEG and ERG acquisition settings to record visual evoked retinal and cortical responses.

A dim flash ($-0.52 \log \text{ cd.s/m}^2$) has used to assess whether electrode placement is satisfactory. Under control conditions, this resulted in an ERG amplitude of $\sim 800 \mu\text{V}$ and an inter-eye variability is no greater than 10%. Following the pretest, animals additionally waited 10 minutes in complete darkness prior to recording. Flashes of light stimuli managed according to parameters which mentioned above (Table 2.1. and Table 2.2) by using a collimated LED light source whilst collecting ERG and VEP-EEG signals simultaneously over a ~ 500 msec time window. During ERG and VEP-EEG data collection, light flashes given from dimmer to brighter light levels in order to maintain enough dark adaptation for waveforms. Signals over a range of luminous energies collected to elicit STR, b-wave and a/b-wave waveforms of the ERG. Signals averaged at the dimmer light levels, at least 20 repeats, and less at the brighter luminous energies one time. The inter-stimulus interval gradually lengthened from 1 to 180 seconds from dimmest to the brightest light level. To isolate the ERG rod and cone responses, a paired-flash paradigm utilized, which initiates four flashes at $1.52 \log \text{ cd.s/m}^2$ with a 500 msec inter-stimulus interval in-between. The cone waveform (3rd or 4th flash) digitally subtracted from the mixed waveform (1st flash) to derive the putative rod response. Average 20 repeats at the brighter luminous energies (i.e., -0.52 to $1.52 \log \text{ cd.s/m}^2$, 5 seconds inter-stimulus interval) recorded for the VEP-EEG

signals. The first flash in this sequence returns the conventional dark-adapted ERG response. Between light stimulations, 1-3 min for re-adaptation period waited after (20) VEP-EEG sweeps and before the next brighter ERG steps, depending on the light intensities.

2.3.4. Behavioral Tests

The rats trained and acclimated to dark-light room and conditional Y-shaped mazes for the experiments. Animals trained in 10 minutes sessions for every two days in previous one month. These sessions created a baseline for further tasks and eliminate stress factor for the animals.

Pupillary Light Reflex Measurement

Pupillary light responses of rats have recorded with video camera after short time light stimulation. Both direct and indirect pupillary response to light will be recorded before and after retinal implant operations. Percentages of pupilar area changes calculated after light stimulation in normal and retinal degenerated animals.

Dark-Light Room Test

The dark-light room test is a light-driven behavioral analysis based on the innate aversion of nocturnal rodents to brightly illuminated areas. The dark-light room test used as an index of light sensitivity in rats. The dark-light room setup contains two-compartment box, which have a 'light' compartment and a 'dark' compartment communicating through a small door and positioned in an experimental room kept under dark conditions. After 30 minutes dark adaptation period, animals introduced to the 'light' compartment and illumination with a 5-lux intensity was applied. 6 minutes video recordings were performed to monitor the latency of escape from the 'light' room and the percentage of time spent in each compartment (Figure 2.9). The number of transitions between the two compartments was also monitored and used as an index of light-independent motor activity (Glen T Prusky et al., 2002).

Figure 2.9: Aerial view of the dark-light room setup during the experiments with (a) normal and (b) blind animals.

Y-Shaped Conditional Maze Test

A Y-shaped plexiglass maze with flat black walls used for the behavioral analysis. Main purpose of the test is understanding visual aided learning behavior in rodents. For the test, visual aided behavioral conditioning, animals introduced with maze repeatedly. Then, they are conditioned to select specific object with food award. In this setup, animals starved 12 hours prior to test and introduced with black and white 5x5x5 cm cubes as novel objects. If they selected white cube during the test, they awarded with food. Food driven behavior of rats directly paired with the location of a specific visual cue in animals with normal vision. They could easily distinguish visual cues before

entering one of the two arms - the length of the divider and size of the visual cue selected accordingly.

In the pre-training phase of the experiment, visual cue placed randomly in each arm of the maze. The food introduced if animal selected right object in any arm of the maze. On their first week trials, animals were removed from their holding cage and released into the maze facing the arms to explore. Upon being released, animals usually walked directly forward, explored both arms, and then climbed upon the cubes. They could remain on or beside the cube for a few seconds and were then returned to their cages.

Figure 2.10: Aerial view of the conditional Y-maze test during the experiments with (a) normal and (b) blind animals.

On the next week trials, the location of the cubes was switched to minimize other disturbing factors. After this routine was repeated a few times, the release distance from the arms was increased gradually until the animals could walk reliably to the arms from a release point at the end of the maze. In the training phase of the experiment, the alternating pattern of the white cube location was substituted in left (L) or right (R)

arms, in LLRLRR sequence. Using this sequence, however, mitigates side biases in animal's responses when a stimulus is displayed three or more times on the same side in succession. On all trials, animals were required to touch any of the cubes until they touched them. If animals walked to the white cube without entering other arm, the trial was considered correct. If they walked into the arm with the black cube, the trial was recorded as an error. Following an incorrect choice, the rats were immediately required to run another trial. Once animals achieved near-perfect performance (80%) in the training phase, testing for visual aided behavioral conditioning began. A LRLRLRR trial-by-trial schedule was used to place the cubes. Throughout testing, animals were released from the end of the maze opposite the cubes and allowed to select a cube for food award (Figure 2.10). After trials covering approximately 50% of the animal's projected range to threshold were completed, the minimum number of trials was increased to three, and then again increased to four around 3/4 of the projected range (Moira Davies et al., 2007).

2.3.5. Immunofluorescence Staining of Retinal Tissues

After the behavioral tests and VEP-EEG/ERG recordings, retinas of the rats removed and fixated after euthanasia. Then the retinal tissues preserved on slides via cryosection, and slides stained with retina-specific cell markers (Johansson et al., 2010). By this way, effects of the retinal prostheses demonstrated, and which cell groups were affected in the retina, because of retinal prosthesis implantation.

Retina Specific Immunofluorescence Staining

Following VEP-EEG measurement, euthanasia of animals made with CO₂ exposure under isoflurane anesthesia. Subsequently, the status of the retinal implant and surrounding tissue examined histopathologically in postmortem-enucleated rat eyes. While RCS/Kyo rats underwent retinal implant operations, sham group also operated except the retinal implant placement. After that, dark-light room and conditional Y-maze tests made between 2. and 4. weeks after operation. After the VEP-EEG and ERG measurements were performed in both groups, the rats euthanized by inhalation of CO₂ and the retinas examined histopathologically in postmortem enucleated rats' eyes.

The eyes enucleated and incubated in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) overnight for fixation. After 4% PFA incubation, the retinal tissues moved to 10%, 20%, 30% sucrose solutions everyday respectively to create osmotic balance. After 30% sucrose solution incubation, tissues moved to optimal cutting temperature (OCT) component and frozen at -80 °C. The frozen tissues cryosectioned for immunofluorescence staining and attached to polysine adhesion slides.

After three washes with PBS, the cells were incubated with 0.1% TritonX-100 in PBS for 8 min. The cells were incubated with Superblock (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA) for 10 minutes at room temperature and then overnight at 4°C with the primary antibodies (Abcam, MA, USA) at optimal dilutions in blocking solution. After three washes with PBS, cells were incubated with the fluorochrome conjugated secondary antibodies (Abcam, MA, USA) for 90 minutes at 37 °C, then washed, counterstained with 406-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) and mounted. Primary antibodies which were used in retina immunofluorescence staining as mentioned below:

- Anti-NeuN antibody: Neural nucleus marker
- Anti-GFAP antibody: Glial cell marker
- Anti-Rhodopsin antibody: Photoreceptor cell marker
- Anti-Glutamine Synthetase antibody: Retinal Müller cell marker
- Anti-Cytokeratin-18 antibody: Retinal pigment epithelium marker
- Anti-CD31 antibody: Retinal endothelial cell marker
- Anti-PKC- α antibody: Retinal bipolar cell marker

TUNEL Staining of The Retinal Tissues

Enucleated eyes incubated in 4% paraformaldehyde solution overnight. Then incubated for 24 hours in 10%, 20% and 30% sucrose solutions, respectively. After that, the eyes were frozen in tissue embedding medium for cryosection. Then, eyes were sectioned 20 μm in cryostat (CM1950, Leica, Wetzlar, Germany). And stained with TUNEL assay kit (ab66110, Abcam, Cambridge, UK) according to manufacturer's protocol. Retinas were counter-stained with DAPI for visualization of nuclei. Finally,

immunofluorescence imaging of tissues has done using confocal fluorescence microscope (TCS SP8 DLS, Leica, Wetzlar, Germany).

2.3.6. Quantification of Results and Statistical Analysis

The analyses of the in vitro biocompatibility, electrophysiology, immunofluorescence imaging, behavioral tests and VEP-EEG/ERG measurements made via MATLAB (MathWorks, MA, USA) and Prism (GraphPad, CA, USA) software. For statistical significance comparison of two groups, Student's T test applied and the difference with p-value under 0.05 has considered as statistically significant. For comparison of multiple groups, one-way ANOVA applied and the p-value under 0.05 considered statistically significant during multiple comparisons. Addition to the multiple comparison, the differences between time points were compared with two-way ANOVA. Prior to animal experiments, power analysis has used to calculate number of animals for each group. In the VEP-EEG and ERG data, the light intensity and color and the electrophysiological timing, magnitude, duration, slope and sensitivity to color and intensity of the neural response in the retina and visual cortex examined. VEP-EEG and ERG data acquisition sample rate was 10000 samples for seconds and it decreased to 1000 to better data analysis. Also, low pass FIR applied for noise reduction. For the dark light room test in the behavioral observations, the time spent in the two rooms and the number of transitions between the rooms analyzed. On the other hand, the selection rate of correct visual cue and the time spent in the maze analyzed in the visual cued Y-shaped maze.

2.4. Simulation of Artificial Visual Perception

In advance of in vivo experiments in retinal degenerated and normal rats, ocular safety limits calculated and required light stimulus amplitude calculated. Also, possible phosphene production simulated with the help of Python based *pulse2percept* toolbox.

2.4.1. Ocular Safety Calculations

Three types of damage could affect the retina after photostimulation: thermal, thermoacoustic, and photochemical damage (Delori et al., 2007). While thermal damage occurs long duration of light stimuli ($\sim 20 \mu\text{s}$), thermoacoustic damage could be occurred even shorter durations ($\sim 1 \text{ ns}$). On the other hand, photochemical could be occur in longer terms in daylight conditions because of photo-oxidative mechanisms. Although biocompatibility of retinal prostheses has shown with in vitro experiments, its functionality limited by the light intensity limits of ocular safety guidelines (Yan et al., 2016). For long term pulsed light stimulation, maximum permissible chronic radiant exposure is limited with light exposure limits for thermal and photochemical damages. While light exposure limit for photochemical damage is 54 mW/cm^2 , prepared QDs based interfaces could work under 10 mW/cm^2 , significantly dimmer light conditions than the ocular safety limits.

Even under ocular safety limits, Class-I (Noell et al., 1966) and Class-II (Ham et al., 1976) damages could negatively affect the retina. While Class-I damage occurs in long durations of white light under 10 W/m^2 intensity, because of photoreceptor and RPE damage, Class-II damage occur in short term light pulses by creating melanolipofucsin in RPE layer (Mattsson et al., 2012). Both types of damages should be considered during production and design of retinal prostheses.

2.4.2. Simulation of Photoelectrical Retinal Stimulation

For simulation of visual percept in proposed retinal prostheses, Python based *pulse2percept* toolbox used in simulation step. The *pulse2percept* project examines trade-off between optimizing for computational performance and ease of use in retinal prosthesis systems. It is organized as a standard Python package, which consists following primary modules: top-level application programming interface (*api*), implants library (*implants*), retina environment (*retina*), stimuli configurations (*stimuli*), example files (*files*), and other utilities (*utils*) (Beyeler et al., 2017).

Figure 2.11: Visual percept comparison for commercially available Argus-II retinal prosthesis system (b) and proposed QDs based planar retinal prosthesis system (c). Visualization of the image by normal eye could be seen in (a).

For stimulation experiments, minimum size of electrodes assumed as a single point (*PointSource*) and number of pixels calculated in μm^2 area of the subretinal prosthesis. Subretinal localization of the retinal prosthesis increases resolution of the visual percept, which also ignores ganglion neuron axons related transmission noise in epiretinal prostheses. Axonal streaks significantly decreased and non-sensory gaps between phosphenes significantly reduced compared to Argus-II retinal prosthesis with 60 electrodes (Figure 2.11).

Chapter 3

RESULTS

3.1. PbS QDs based Neural Interface

3.1.1. In vitro Experiment Results

Production of Quantum Dots based Neural Interfaces

ITO/ZnO/P3HT:PbS QDs:PCBM structure produced by spin coating. ITO coated glass and PET samples were cleaned via sonication for 15 minutes in 2% Hellmanex III solution, distilled water, acetone and isopropyl, respectively. Then, they dried in 50 °C oven for 30 minutes. Synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles made with a homogeneous ZnO solution was obtained by mixing sonication at 55 °C for 15 minutes by mixing 219.3 mg of zinc acetate and 73 mg of ethanolamine in 2 ml of 2-methoxy ethanol. Before coating with ZnO, UV light and ozone applied to the devices for 15 minutes to ensure that hydrophilic and clean surface. 50 µl ZnO solution dropped to the sample and the samples spined at 2000 rpm. The sample was then annealed at 250 °C for 15 minutes for 40 nm ZnO layer thickness. After that, 6% 4 nm diameter PbS core type nanocrystals added to P3HT: PCBM (1:1) and a triple hybrid mixture was obtained. This P3HT:PbS QDs:PCBM active layer was spun at 2000 rpm and coated on ITO/ZnO layer. The coated samples were annealed at 155 °C for 15 minutes.

Surface Characterization of the Neural Interfaces

Scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM/EDS) results of the samples showed a homogenous distribution of the larger agglomerations with an approximate average size of 200-300 nm and the EDS results indicated presence of oxygen and carbon. As the core precursor for PbS was coated with oleic acid, presence of carbon and oxygen peaks are expected, however this oxygen can also be related to very low amount of surface oxidation taking place, as a result of nanoscale size of the particles.

Figure 3.1: X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD) peaks (red) show similar pattern with ICDD database information for peaks (blue) of PbS quantum dots.

Figure 3.2: SEM (top) and EDS (bottom) results for ITO/ZnO/P3HT:PbS QDs:PCBM interface.

Figure 3.3: Calculations of the size of agglomerations in SEM images of ITO/ZnO/P3HT:PbS QDs:PCBM interface.

Photocurrent Measurements

Photocurrent tests were carried out after production of the ITO/ZnO/PCBM:PbS QDs:P3HT structure to show the best performance parameters. Photostimulation was performed in patch clamp system with an Olympus T2 upright microscope. An extracellular patch clamp amplifier and acquisition system (EPC800, HEKA Electronics, Reutlingen, Germany) was used for photocurrent measurements. A power meter (843-R, Newport, CA, USA) was used to measure the light power on the interface. The illumination was focused on the PCBM:PbS QDs:P3HT coating in the water immersion target at 40x magnification with 0.8 W, UPlanFI FN 26.5 objective. The photocurrent started with a negative capacitive, followed by a very low incremental faradaic contribution compared to the capacitive effect (Figure 3.4). It is important that the produced device shows high capacitive property, since it is known that the capacitive current is the safe path for photostimulation of neural cells. The main reason for the high safety of capacitive current is not caused by electron transfer to the solution, but by the ossification of the ionic double layer at the electrolyte-electrode interface. In addition, the negative start of the first response has met with the *in vivo* expectations due to the previously described architecture of the device.

Photocurrent measurements were made with an electrophysiology system amplifier operated in a voltage patch clamp mode with a capillary pipette positioned closer than 1 μm to the electrode surface. The electrode was immersed in the artificial cerebrospinal fluid to make an accurate characterization in the cellular environment. Capillary glasses, which contains electrodes, filled with a standard solution containing 140 mM NaCl, 10 mM KCl, 5 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM HEPES, 0.5 mM EGTA and 0.5 mM ATP, and the pH was adjusted by using KOH to 7.3. The standard extracellular solution contains 28 mM NaCl, 5 mM KCl, 1 mM MgCl₂, 2.5 mM CaCl₂ and the pH was adjusted to 7.4 with NaOH. We characterized the photoelectrodes we produced under 20 mW/cm² and 50 ms blue light (455 nm) and with the capacitive current of ~ 3.4 nA, high and safe photocurrent values were produced to meet the *in vivo* expectations (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4: The photocurrent measurement of ITO/ZnO/P3HT:PbS QDs:PCBM based interface.

MTT Toxicity Assay Results

The biocompatibility of the device was tested with MTT toxicity assay. Both SH-SY5Y cells and primary hippocampal neurons used for the biocompatibility assay of ITO/ZnO/PCBM:PbS QDs:P3HT interface, and the metabolic activity of cells was examined and compared with the reference device, which is ITO coated glass. The results of the MTT assay on SH-SY5Y are shown in Figure 3.5. The results of MTT biocompatibility assay on primary hippocampal neurons are shown in Figure 3.8. As seen in the results, the cell viability in SH-SY5Y cells on the interface is at the same level as the reference device ITO coated glass. This interface has not any significant effect on cell viability, which shows the interfaces are biocompatible. Even there are

small decrease at viability of primary hippocampal neurons on the interface, the interface is still biocompatible for primary neurons.

Figure 3.5: MTT toxicity assay results in SH-SY5Y for ITO/ZnO/PCBM:PbS QDs: P3HT and ITO, as control (n=3). There is no statistically significant difference between groups (ns: no significance).

Figure 3.6: Phase contrast microscopy image of primary hippocampal neurons on ITO/ZnO/PCBM:PbS QDs: P3HT neural interface.

Figure 3.7: Immunofluorescence images of primary neurons on ITO/ZnO/PCBM:PbS QDs: P3HT interfaces.

Along with toxicity assays, primary hippocampal neurons were observed on the interface with the help of phase contrast microscopy and immunofluorescence imaging. Primary hippocampal neurons were stained with NeuN, which is neuron specific nucleus marker and DAPI, which is nucleus marker. In these observations, both neural morphology and characterization were not affected from the interface (Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.8: MTT toxicity assay results for primary hippocampal neurons on ITO/ZnO/PCBM:PbS QDs: P3HT based interfaces (n=4).

Whole Cell Patch Clamp Electrophysiology Results

The voltage clamp and current clamp measurements on neurons were measured under giga-sealed condition with capillary pipettes (4-8 M Ω) on heated pad for whole cell patch clamp measurements. Capillary glass pipette with electrodes contains intracellular solution, which contains 140 mM NaCl, 10 mM KCl, 5 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM HEPES, 0.5 mM EGTA and 0.5 mM ATP to mimic intracellular fluid and pH adjusted to 7.3 by using KOH. The modified artificial cerebrospinal fluid contains 128 mM NaCl, 5 mM KCl, 1 mM MgCl₂, 2.5 mM CaCl₂, and pH adjusted to 7.4 with NaOH. During whole cell patch clamp electrophysiology of SH-SY5Y cells, approximately 21 mV depolarization was observed on the neural membrane under 20 mW/cm² and 10 ms blue light (455 nm) (Figure 3.9). The reason for not seeing an action potential in these cells is the undifferentiated cell usage. For this reason, current and voltage levels were estimated to achieve the action potentials in these cells, according to previous literature.

In next step, primary hippocampal neurons have used for action potential propagation with the interface.

Figure 3.9: Whole cell patch-clamp results for ITO/ZnO/PCBM:PbS QDs:P3HT substrate on SH-SY5Y cells. 20 mW/cm² luminous intensity with 1 Hz for 10 ms pulse length creates 21 mV depolarization on cell membrane.

For stimulation of primary hippocampal neurons, 20 mW/cm² light intensity blue light (455 nm) has used. Three different frequency (ON-OFF time ratio) modulation have used: 5 ms ON / 0.1 ms OFF, 10 ms ON / 0.1 ms OFF, and 15 ms ON / 0.1 ms OFF stimulation durations. Average succeed action potential voltage increase is 68 mV for primary neurons (n = 10). With the increase of ON time in the light stimulation, number of succeed action potential propagation increased (Figure 3.10).

Figure 3.10: Whole-cell patch clamp results for primary hippocampal neurons on PbS QDs based neural interface. In different light stimulation durations (5, 10, and 15 ms), action potential generation in hippocampal neurons observed (right). Membrane potential change with and without photostimulation is significantly different (left) ($n=10$, *** $p<0.001$).

Primary hippocampal neurons, which were extracted from decapitated E15-E17 Wistar Albino rats, have been used in whole cell patch clamp experiments. Both current clamp and voltage clamp modes have been used for whole cell patch clamp electrophysiology. The light pulses were illuminated from the top of the surface of the interface and the matured primary hippocampal cells on the interface were seeded separately to avoid spontaneous action potential activity. As a control experiment, primary hippocampal neurons cultured on glass with ITO coating and the light illumination applied on the cells, which shows no neural activity. It confirms that the photostimulation of neurons alone does not show any spontaneous activity. The electron hole accumulation leads to a displacement current with a direction on neural membrane, which leads to initial depolarization in primary hippocampal neurons. Above 5 ms ON time light stimulation as square waveform creates neuromodulation and the action potential generation. The burst light pulses in daylight conditions generate repetitive action potentials in different ON/OFF time conditions, such as 5/0.1 ms, 10/0.1 ms, and 15/0.1 ms light stimulation settings. This action potential generation by the weak light intensities could be useful for the retinal prostheses based photovoltaic photoelectrodes (Srivastava et al., 2020).

Figure 3.11: Photocurrent measurements of the retinal interface before and after plasma sterilization with ethylene oxide.

3.1.2. *In vivo* Experiment Results

After *in vitro* experiments made, for *in vivo* biocompatibility, electrophysiology, behavioral and immunohistochemistry experiments, the devices implanted to the subretinal spaces of the rats.

Preparation of Retinal Interfaces for Implantation

Retinal prostheses prepared as explained above and were sterilized with ethylene oxide before implantation. Sterilization method was applied with ethylene oxide gas in sterilization unit. Photocurrent measurements before and after sterilization are shown in Figure 3.11. As shown in the figure, there are no capacitive current difference was observed between the photocurrent measurements before and after sterilization.

Dark Agouti - PbS

Figure 3.12: *In vivo* images of Dark Agouti (DA/HanRj) rat retinas, before and after implantation of PbS QDs based retinal prostheses.

Determination of Retinal Implantation Area

After the optimization of the sterilization process, 1.0 mm x 1.5 mm x 50 μm PET surfaces, which form the infrastructure of the retinal prostheses, are placed in the retina for optimization of the retinal implantation operation. It has been shown that, fovea of the retina is easily reachable via subretinal way (Figure 3.12 and 3.13).

RCS/Kyo - PbS

Figure 3.13: In vivo images of RCS/Kyo rat retinas, before and after implantation of PbS QDs based retinal prostheses.

In vivo Observation of the Retinal Implants

Most of the retinal prostheses placed on subretinal space. Only one retinal prosthesis placed under RPE. Two of the retinal prostheses also create retinal tearing, which were recovered by themselves during follow-up period. During the subretinal implantation procedure, vitreous opacities occurred because of the anesthetic mixture, ketamine and xylazine. Also, one of the animals had vitreous bleeding during the operation, but it did not leave any chronic residual in intraocular space.

Behavioral Test Results

Figure 3.14: Dark light room experiment results for Dark Agouti (DA/HanRj) rats. Latency for escape from light compartment (left) and the time spent in the light compartment measured and compared with other groups (right).

Firstly, retinal prostheses implanted to the healthy rats, to how its biocompatibility and non-neurotoxicity on the retinas. In dim red-light conditions, both latency and time percentage in light room increased significantly for rats with healthy retinas. During bright light conditions the rats from all groups showed dark orientated behavior, which leads to decreased time in light room and decreased latency time in light room (Figure 3.14).

In also RCS/Kyo rat groups, similar results with DA/HanRj rats have found. The rats with retinal prostheses intentionally decrease their time in light compartment compared to control group of RCS/Kyo rats (Figure 3.37). Unfortunately, the rats with retinal prosthesis did not show increased success in Y-shaped conditional maze with a help of

visual cue. They did not show any sign of behavioral learning with visual cues. These results indicate the PbS QDs based retinal prosthesis has possible impact on visual perception, but this impact could not directly show because of increased variability between animals. Because of this, visual perception of rats should be investigated with electrophysiological settings.

Electrophysiology Results

Figure 3.15: Electretinography results of the DA/HanRj rats under white light (590 nm) pulsed stimulation with 1 Hz, 500 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$, 1/10 ON time ratio.

After behavioral tests, simultaneous electretinography and visually evoked potential-electroencephalogram applied to the rats. For these measurements, chronic EEG implants were placed on both visual cortex and bregma of the rats. By this way, synchronized ERG and VEP-EEG recordings were taken.

In DA/HanRj control group, synchronous healthy ERG and VEP-EEG responses recorded. Average total amplitude (a wave + b wave) for ERG was calculated as 116.40 μV ($n = 14$) and average total amplitude for VEP-EEG was calculated as 123.50 μV (n

= 20). In both VEP-EEG and ERG signals, after the noise reduction both a and b waves

could be seen as shown in Figure 3.18.

Figure 3.16: Electroretinography results of the DA/HanRj rats under blue light (455 nm) pulsed stimulation with 1 Hz, $500 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$, 1/10 ON time ratio.

Figure 3.17: Electoretinography results of the DA/HanRj rats under green light (530 nm) pulsed stimulation with 1 Hz, 500 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$, 1/10 ON time ratio.

Figure 3.18: Synchronous VEP-EEG and ERG response after 100 ms, 500 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ white light stimulus.

During VEP-EEG and ERG recordings, light wavelength, frequency, intensity, and stimulus duration have changed as mentioned in Table 2.1. While sole green light stimulus leads to higher amplitude and lower latency in both ERG and VEP-EEG signals, blue light driven signals occurred later and lower than white light induced VEP-EEG and ERG signals (Figure 3.19 and Figure 3.20).

Figure 3.19: Comparison of ERG responses in DA/HanRj rats under lights with different wavelengths. Peak wavelengths for each light source are 590 nm for white, 455 nm for blue, and 530 nm for green.

Figure 3.20: Comparison of VEP-EEG responses in DA/HanRj rats under lights with different wavelengths. Peak wavelengths for each light source are 590 nm for white, 455 nm for blue, and 530 nm for green.

After light wavelength modulation, light intensity modulation on VEP-EEG and ERG measurements applied. Above $32 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ light intensity, both in VEP-EEG and ERG responses were started to be visible. Above $250 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ light intensity, early receptor potential (ERP) could be seen in ERG, which indicates full ERG response potential achieved in this intensity (Figure 3.21). Because of these observations, $500 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ light intensity have selected for further VEP-EEG and ERG experiments.

In next step, the effect of the light stimulus duration measured on ERG recordings of healthy rats. In 500 ms ON / 500 ms OFF time and 200 ms ON / 800 ms OFF time conditions, the retinas created also additional response at the end of light stimuli, which could interfere with next ERG response in pulsed light response recordings. Under 50

ms light stimulus duration, b wave of the ERG response did not fully evoke, because of short duration (Figure 3.22).

Figure 3.21: Average ERG responses of the healthy rat retinas under various white light flash intensities.

Figure 3.22: Average ERG responses of the healthy rat retinas under various white light flash durations.

Figure 3.23: Average ERG responses of the healthy rat retinas under various white light frequencies.

Lastly, frequency of the light stimuli has changed to optimize ERG responses of pulsed light stimulation. Above 2 Hz frequency, total ERG amplitude significantly reduced. Because of this, 1 Hz frequency have selected for ERG measurements.

In RCS/Kyo rats, 1 Hz, 100 ms ON time, $500 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ light has used for ERG measurements. In none of the rats with PbS QDs based retinal implant, ERG response initiated (Figure 3.24). Due to non-responsiveness of the retinas of RCS/Kyo rats, light stimulation amplitude increased up to $50 \text{ mW}/\text{cm}^2$ light intensity for a single light pulse. In this high intensity light stimulation, ERG response observed above $8 \text{ mW}/\text{cm}^2$ light

stimulation. Unfortunately, light stimulation pulses above 1 mW/cm^2 lead to Class-I damage in retina, even in very short durations.

Figure 3.24: Comparison of average ERG responses in RCS/Kyo rat retinas with PbS QDs retinal implants under lights with different wavelengths. Peak wavelengths for each light source are 590 nm for white, 455 nm for blue, and 530 nm for green.

Ex vivo Observation of the Retinal Implants

Figure 3.25: (a) In vivo view of a photovoltaic subretinal implant with indirect ophthalmoscope, (b) Ex vivo sectional view of the same subretinal implant with hematoxylin & eosin staining.

Figure 3.26: Ex vivo eyecups of RCS/Kyo rats after subretinal implantation of PbS QDs retinal prosthesis. The positions of the implants could be seen.

Figure 3.27: Photocurrent results of capacitive electrical charges produced by PbS QDs based retinal prostheses before and after subretinal implantation.

Photocurrents of PbS QDs based retinal prostheses measured before and after subretinal implantation. Capacitive electrical charge capacity of PbS QDs based retinal prosthesis decreased by 35% percentage after 10 weeks period in subretinal space (Figure 3.27).

Figure 3.28: Immunofluorescence image of the whole-mount retina on PbS QDs based retinal prosthesis. In immunofluorescence staining, red fluorochrome stained CD31, endothelial cell marker. Green fluorochrome stained NeuN, neural cell marker. Blue fluorochrome stained DAPI, nucleus marker. The surface of the retinal prosthesis could be seen because of the same excitation wavelength of PbS QDs with DAPI.

After behavioral and electrophysiological tests, the animals euthanized, and retinal tissues fixated for further processes. After the fixation, the eyecups with the retinal prostheses observed and damaged photoactive surfaces of the retinal prostheses could be seen (Figure 3.26).

Figure 3.29: Immunofluorescence images of the retinal sections of DA/HanRj and RCS/Kyo rats with and without the retinal prosthesis. The retinas stained with DAPI (blue), a nucleus marker, and PKC- α (green), a bipolar cell marker.

In hematoxylin eosin staining, implantation injury related gliosis observed under the subretinal prosthesis, which could decrease functionality of the retinal prosthesis (Figure 3.25). The retinas with retinal prostheses observed with immunofluorescence imaging as whole mount and sections. In whole mount immunofluorescence staining of the retina, both decrease in number of ganglion cells and disruption in retinal vessels could be observed (Figure 3.28).

In immunofluorescence images of the retinal sections, disruptions of retinas clearly visible. In PKC- α staining samples, gliosis under retinal prosthesis, disconnection between bipolar and ganglion cells, and attachment of bipolar cells on photoactive layer of the retinal prosthesis were observed (Figure 3.29). In rhodopsin & NeuN co-staining samples, decrease in number of ganglion cells, disruption in photoreceptor cell layer and laceration of the retina were observed (Figure 3.30). In all

immunofluorescence staining samples, photoactive layer of the retinal prosthesis could be seen, because of matching excitation wavelength with fluorochromes.

Figure 3.30: Immunofluorescence images of the retinal tissue sections of DA/HanRj and RCS/Kyo rats with and without the retinal prosthesis. The retinas stained with DAPI (blue), a nucleus marker, NeuN (green), neural cell marker, and rhodopsin (red), a photoreceptor cell marker.

3.2. AlSb Nanocrystal based Interfaces

3.2.1. In vitro Experiment Results

ITO/ZnO/P3HT/AlSb QDs interfaces were produced according to previously mentioned protocol in the methods section. After production of AlSb nanocrystal-based interface, surface characterization and photocurrent measurement were made, then the interfaces were sterilized for in vitro biocompatibility and electrophysiology tests.

Figure 3.31: MTT toxicity assay results for primary hippocampal neurons on aluminum antimonide nanocrystal-based interface (n = 4). There is no statistically significant difference between groups (ns: no significance).

In vitro Biocompatibility Results

Cell biocompatibility tests for ALSb QDs based interface made by using 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide (MTT) cell viability assay kit. The primary hippocampal neurons were cultured on the biointerface, and control samples did not show significant difference to each other (Figure 3.31). Addition to toxicity assay, primary hippocampal neurons on the biointerface stained with DAPI, filamentous actin, which cytoskeleton marker, and NeuN, which is specific neural nucleus marker, in immunofluorescence staining. Primary hippocampal neurons on ALSb QDs based interface did not show any significant negative change in characterization and morphology of the neurons (Figure 3.32).

In vitro Electrophysiology Results

Action potential propagation ability of the biointerface measured with the primary hippocampal neurons cultured on glass:ITO/ZnO/P3HT/ALSb NC biointerface, and glass:ITO/ZnO/P3HT, which is a sample device and glass:ITO, which is a control sample. During whole cell patch clamp measurements, primary hippocampal neurons attached to the biointerfaces, and the IV curves of the neurons measured under dark conditions.

The light stimulation in patch clamp experiments made as light pulse trains of 20 ms, 50 mW/cm², 445 nm blue LED illumination with different frequencies (1, 2, 5, 10, and 20 Hz). In all frequencies, action potential induced in >90% success rate, except 20 Hz, which reduces to ~73% action potential success rate (n = 20). Calculated the latency of spike peak was 16.70 ± 0.478 ms, as mean with standard deviation, over the neurons on the ALSb QDs based biointerface. Also, the mean latency jitter was 1.748 ± 0.120 ms (n = 20) (Figure 3.33).

Beside action potential activity, resting membrane potentials of the primary hippocampal neurons on the interfaces measured before and after photo-stimulation. Resting membrane potential of primary hippocampal neurons did not change after

photostimulation in all groups ($p = 0.1822$, $n = 20$). Resolution of the interface measured with 1 Hz, 20 ms, 50 mW/cm², 445 nm, ~600 μm diameter blue LED light pulses and neural activity was recorded while moving the illumination spot away from the neuron ($n = 4$). At 225 μm away from the neuron, successful spike rate of the biointerface reduces to 50%. At 325 μm , there is no successful action potential propagation on the neuron. At 775 μm away from the neuron, the biointerface did not induce any membrane potential change. The temperature change after long term photostimulation of the biointerface is 0.364 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is negligible in terms of photothermal and photochemical damage.

Figure 3.32: Immunofluorescence staining of primary hippocampal neurons on AlSb QDs based interfaces and control samples. Primary hippocampal neurons stained with

immunofluorescence antibodies; DAPI (blue), a nucleus marker, NeuN (red), a neural nucleus marker, and F-Actin (green), a cytoskeleton marker.

Figure 3.33: Whole cell patch clamp results for AISb nanocrystal-based interfaces. (a) Schema of the patch clamp system. (b) Action potential activity in the neurons on AISb QDs based interfaces in different light frequencies, 1, 2, 5, 10, 20 Hz. (c) Example action potential in the neuron on AISb QDs based interface. (d) Resting membrane potential changes after stimulation in ITO control and AISb nanocrystal-based interface. (e) Latency and jitter measurements in the neurons on the biointerface. (f) Action potential success of the biointerface in different light stimulation frequencies (Han et al., 2021).

3.2.2. *In vivo* Experiment Results

After *in vitro* experiments, the AISb nanocrystal-based interfaces on PET implanted to the subretinal area of the DA/HanRj and RCS/Kyo rats for *in vivo* biocompatibility, electrophysiology, behavioral and immunohistochemistry experiments.

In vivo Observation of the Retinal Implants

The AISb QDs based interfaces were implanted to the retinas of the DA/HanRj, as a control group, and RCS/Kyo rats. After one week recovery period from the operation, behavioral and electrophysiological experiments were conducted.

Dark Agouti - AISb

Figure 3.34: In vivo images of Dark Agouti (DA/HanRj) rat retinas, before and after implantation of AISb nanocrystal based retinal prostheses.

RCS/Kyo - AISb

Figure 3.35: In vivo images of RCS/Kyo rat retinas, before and after implantation of AISb nanocrystal based retinal prostheses.

Figure 3.36: Retinal fundus photographs of rats with subretinal implants. Fundus photographs taken with help of indirect ophthalmoscope (Omega 500, Heine GmbH, Gliching, Germany) and 90D fundoscopy lens (Volk, OH, USA) after subretinal implantation operation of the biointerface. The biointerface could be seen with yellow reflection on the temporal side of central retinal artery (scale bars: 1 mm).

Similar to the PbS QDs based interfaces, the AISb nanocrystal-based interfaces coated on the 1.0 mm x 1.5 mm x 50 μm PET surfaces, sterilized and implanted to the rat retinas via subretinal way (Figure 3.36).

Majority of the retinal interfaces placed on subretinal space (Figure 3.34 and 3.35). Only one of the AISb QDs based retinal prosthesis placed under RPE. Two of the AISb QDs based retinal prostheses create retinal laceration. Luckily, the retinal lacerations recovered spontaneously during the follow-up period. During the subretinal implantation procedure, vitreous haze occurred due to the anesthetic mixture, ketamine and xylazine. Also, one of the animals had vitreous bleeding during the operation, but it did not leave any chronic residual in intraocular space after recovery period.

Behavioral Test Results

Figure 3.37: Behavioral test results of RCS/Kyo and DA/HanRj rats. Success rate(%) in conditional Y-maze test (top) and spent time (%) in light compartment of dark-light room test (bottom). * $p < 0.05$.

In dim red-light conditions, both latency and time percentage in light room increased significantly for rats with healthy retinas. During bright light conditions, the rats from all groups showed dark orientated behavior, which leads to decreased time in light room and decreased latency time in light room (Figure 3.37).

In also RCS/Kyo rat groups, similar results with DA/HanRj rats have found. The rats with retinal prostheses spent less time in light compartment compared to control group of RCS/Kyo rats (Figure 3.37). Unfortunately, the rats with retinal prosthesis did not show increased success in Y-shaped conditional maze with a help of visual cue. They did not show any sign of behavioral learning with visual cues. These results indicate the AISb nanocrystal based retinal prostheses have a possible impact on visual sensation, but this impact could not directly show because of high variation among the animals.

Electrophysiology Results

Figure 3.38: Average total ERG response of the retinas of DA/HanRj rats with the different retinal prostheses in different light stimulation frequencies. * $p < 0.05$.

Figure 3.39: Total ERG amplitude changes in DA/HanRj rat retinas with different types of the retinal prostheses. *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure 3.40: Comparison of average ERG responses in RCS/Kyo rat retinas with AISb nanocrystal based retinal interfaces under lights with different wavelengths. Peak wavelengths for each light source are 590 nm for white, 455 nm for blue, and 530 nm for green.

Figure 3.41: Average ERG responses of the RCS/Kyo rat retinas with retinal prostheses in high power light pulse stimulation. The red dashed line shows, definite light intensity limit (10 mW/cm^2) for light induced class-II damage in retina.

In DA/HanRj rats, average ERG response did not decrease in the rat retinas with AlSb QDs based retinal interface, while average ERG response of the rat retinas with PbS QDs based retinal prostheses (Figure 3.39). Also in different frequencies, retinal responses of the DA/HanRj rat retinas with different retinal prostheses observed. While total ERG amplitudes in DA/HanRj rat retinas with PbS QDs based retinal interfaces significantly decrease in all light stimulation frequencies, except 10 Hz, AlSb QDs based retinal interfaces in DA/HanRj rat retinas did not decrease until 5 Hz and 10 Hz frequencies (Figure 3.38).

In RCS/Kyo rats, 1 Hz, 100 ms ON time, $500 \mu\text{W/cm}^2$ light has used for ERG measurements. In none of the rats with AlSb nanocrystal based retinal implant, ERG response was initiated (Figure 3.40). Due to non-responsiveness of the retinas of RCS/Kyo rats, light intensity for pulsed stimulation increased up to 50 mW/cm^2 for a single light pulse. In this high intensity light stimulation, ERG response observed above 8 mW/cm^2 light stimulation (Figure 3.41). But light stimulation pulses above 10

mW/cm^2 , which is a definitive limit for class-II damage in retina, could lead to photothermal damage in retina, even in a single pulse.

Ex vivo Observation of the Retinal Implants

Figure 3.42: Ex vivo eyecups of RCS/Kyo rats after subretinal implantation of AISb nanocrystal based retinal prostheses.

After behavioral and electrophysiological tests, the rats euthanized, and retinal tissues fixated for the further processes. After the fixation, the eyecups with the AISb nanocrystal based retinal prostheses observed and damaged photoactive surfaces of the retinal prostheses could be seen in Figure 3.42.

After fixation and freezing of the retinal tissues, the retinas sectioned in $20\ \mu\text{m}$ thickness, then they stained with TUNEL cytotoxicity assay and DAPI nuclear dye (Figure 3.43). In none of the healthy animals with the retinal prosthesis, cytotoxic changes observed in retinas of the rats after the retinal prosthesis implantation. The implants could not be seen because of the fixation method of the retinas.

Figure 3.43: TUNEL cytotoxicity assay results with DAPI staining of rat retinas with retinal prostheses.

3.3. Other Candidates

3.3.1. InP QDs based Interfaces

Indium phosphide (InP) QDs are light tunable in all visible range and biocompatible semiconductor nanomaterials, which is used for various biomedical applications (Devatha et al., 2017).

In vitro Biocompatibility Results

Although the biocompatibility of InP QDs based interfaces were studied in detail, the biocompatibility of these biointerfaces should be investigated on primary hippocampal neurons. The biocompatibility of InP QDs based interfaces investigated with MTT toxicity assay and immunofluorescence imaging.

Figure 3.44: MTT toxicity assay results on primary hippocampal neurons for indium phosphide QDs/ZnO (I) and Indium phosphide/ZnS QDs/ TiO₂ (II) based interfaces. There is no statistically significant difference between groups (ns: no significance).

The cytotoxic effect of the InP QDs based biointerfaces on primary hippocampal neurons were assessed after 48 hours incubation and they did not show any negative effect on cell viability (Figure 3.44). In addition, primary hippocampal neurons seeded on the InP QDs based interfaces, and incubated up to 14 days. After Day-14, characterization and morphology of primary hippocampal neurons compared with the primary hippocampal neurons in Day 0. For the comparison of characterization and morphology of the primary hippocampal neurons, immunofluorescence staining made with F-actin, NeuN and DAPI dyes. The biointerfaces did not affect cell viability, morphology, and characterization in the primary hippocampal neurons at both Day-0 and Day-14 incubation periods (Figure 3.45). These findings also support the results of cytotoxicity assay.

Figure 3.45: Immunofluorescence images of the primary hippocampal neurons on InP QDs based interfaces in day 0 and day 14 incubations. Primary hippocampal neurons

stained with immunofluorescence antibodies; DAPI (blue), a nucleus marker, NeuN (red), a neural nucleus marker, and F-Actin (green), a cytoskeleton marker.

In vitro Electrophysiology Results

In vitro whole cell patch clamp experiments with the InP QDs based interfaces (type I and II) made to understand light-induced neurostimulation capacity of the interfaces. Blue light (445 nm) with 2 mW/mm² has used for the light stimulation experiments. The cell membrane changes in the primary hippocampal neurons on the interfaces measured with whole cell patch clamp system. While InP QDs/ZnO based interfaces (I) induce hyperpolarization, InP/ZnS QDs/TiO₂ induce depolarization on primary hippocampal neurons and these depolarizations induce action potential in neural membranes (Figure 3.46). ITO surface acts as return electrode in both structures.

In whole cell patch clamp experiments, when both InP QDs based structures stimulated with 10 ms blue light pulses, they initiate voltage changes in cell membrane in opposite directions. While type I device hyperpolarizes the cell membrane, type II device depolarizes the membrane and evokes action potential in the primary hippocampal neurons. Hyperpolarization capacity of type I devices increase with duration of the light stimuli, indicated as 24 ± 3 mV for 10 ms, 34 ± 4 mV for 50 ms, and 45 ± 6 mV for 200 ms ($n = 6$). This electrical behavior of the device favorable for other neurostimulation application, which indicates resistive coupling, similar to iridium oxide electrodes. Also, type II biointerfaces, which could induce and modulate action potentials with initial depolarization on the membrane, could create reproducible action potential trains with 10 ms light pulses at 1 Hz, 2 Hz and 5 Hz frequencies over 85% success rate (Figure 3.46). Along with depolarization capacity of the interfaces, also hyperpolarization capacity of the interfaces will be helpful for the retinal prosthesis, to mimic lateral inhibition in bipolar cell to create phosphene production and to simulate ON/OFF bipolar and ganglion cell networks (Wei, 2018).

Figure 3.46: Whole cell patch clamp results for InP QDs based interfaces. While type II InP QDs based interface leads to depolarization, type I InP QDs based interface leads to hyperpolarization in neural membrane potential of primary hippocampal neurons. (a) Schema of the whole cell patch clamp setup. (b) Example action depolarization and hyperpolarization dynamics on the neural membrane after light stimulation of both types of InP QD based interfaces. (c) Depolarizations of the neural membrane after light stimulation of type I InP QDs based interfaces. (d) Action potential generation of the primary hippocampal neurons after light stimulation of type II InP QDs based interfaces. (e) Success rate of action potential propagation of type II InP QDs in different light stimulation frequencies (Karatum et al., 2021).

3.3.2. PTB7-Th:PC71BM based Interfaces

The PTB7-Th:PC71BM based interfaces are high open circuit photovoltaic interfaces, which were used in solar cells and could be possible useful in photostimulation of neural tissues, if its biocompatibility and in vitro functionality investigated (Srivastava et al., 2021).

In vitro Biocompatibility and Electrophysiology Results

Before investigation of electrophysiological behavior of the neurons under light induced stimulation with the PTB7-Th:PC71BM device, the primary hippocampal neurons observed in phase contrast microscopy for cytotoxicity and biocompatibility (Figure 3.47). The primary hippocampal neurons live on the photovoltaic surface up to 14 days without any negative change in neural morphology. The primary hippocampal neurons examined in whole cell patch clamp system for photovoltaic stimulation of action potential generation on neural membrane. The average resting cell membrane potential of the primary hippocampal neurons is -78 mV ($n = 12$).

Figure 3.47: Phase contrast microscopy image of the primary hippocampal neurons on the PTB7-Th:PC71BM based interface. Scale bar is 200 μ m.

20 mW/cm², 455 nm, 1/0.1 ms pulsed light stimulation applied on the biointerface with the primary hippocampal neurons. When light stimulation applied on the interface, membrane potential of the primary hippocampal neurons increased significantly (n = 10, p < 0.001) (Figure 3.48). Individual action potentials after capacitive currents after pulsed light stimulation could be observed for each neuron (Figure 3.49).

Figure 3.48: Membrane potential change comparison between ON and OFF conditions in pulsed light stimulation on primary hippocampal neurons on the interface. “***” indicates that p-value for difference is lower than 0.001 (n = 10).

The primary hippocampal neurons showed increased number of action potentials and action potential amplitude was ~65 mV in the range of 45–80 mV compared to control group. Because of fast capacitive response of the biointerface in low intensity (20 mW/cm²), short light pulses (50 μs), repetitive induction of voltage gated sodium channels on the neural membrane leads to action potential generation. The fast repetitive light induced activation of PTB7-Th:PC71BM based interface could be helpful for further retinal prosthesis prototypes.

Figure 3.49: Generated action potentials by PTB7-Th:PC71BM based interface on primary hippocampal neurons with pulsed light stimulation (n = 10).

Chapter 4

DISCUSSION

Human vision is one of the unique abilities in the all-animal kingdom. We are highly dependent to vision for our self-perception, social life, and all everyday activities. It provides the highest amount of information from the external environment, compared to other senses. We are highly depending on it for our every act. Thanks to our retinas, we could effortlessly convert light rays from the environment to visual information. Complex integration of photoreceptor, bipolar and ganglion cells in the retina creates natural visual processing unit prior to the central nervous system (Covey & Walsh, 2001). Unfortunately, a few of the neurodegenerative diseases leads to loss of function in this complex integrative information processor unit, the retina. Commonly loss of photoreceptor cell population caused by age-related macular degeneration (AMD), diabetic retinopathy, and retinitis pigmentosa (RP). Only AMD affects more than 300 million people in the world (Mitchell et al., 2018).

Currently, there is no conventional treatment to recover photoreceptor loss. Pharmacological and physical therapies could slow down the photoreceptor cell death, but they could not reverse the photoreceptor loss. Gene therapy and transplantation of stem cell derived photoreceptor cells could be future directions but none of them rescue the visual sensation for all retinal degenerated patients. Optogenetics methods could be useful for genetical modifications on the degenerative retinas with a viral vector transfection of opsin proteins (Deisseroth, 2011), but there are significant

concerns about toxicity and safety of this therapy in clinical application (Busskamp et al., 2012).

Retinal prostheses, Argus II (Second Sight Medical Products, USA) and Alpha-IMS (Retina Implant AG, Germany), are the only clinically approved therapy options for functional loss of the photoreceptor cells. While Alpha-IMS implanted subretinal space in the RP patients (Stingl et al., 2015), Argus II system placed on epiretinal surface of the retina, adjacent to the ganglion neurons (Luo & Da Cruz, 2016). These prostheses allow patients to distinguish light and dark conditions and even in some patients, they help to large object recognition. But even in highest pixel densities in these retinal prostheses, the visual acuity of the patients is still below 20/200, which is legal blindness limit (Stingl et al., 2013). Main concern for the visual acuity is uncontrolled current spread from pixel electrodes in the retinal prostheses. This situation leads to activation of lateral neurons and reduces phosphene generation resolution in retina (Goetz & Palanker, 2016). Also, dependency to outer energy source, processor, and camera decrease its functionality and compatibility in patients.

As a novel subretinal prosthesis candidate in clinical trials, the PRIMA subretinal prosthesis (Pixium Vision, France) uses direct photovoltaic conversion of near infrared light into neuro-electronic stimulus (Palanker et al., 2020). By this way, PRIMA eliminates the requirement of power supply and outer connections and ease subretinal implantation procedure (Lorach et al., 2015). To increase its resolution, PRIMA uses solid multiple well based structure for directional current production. But this structure leads to the complete degeneration of the residual healthy photoreceptor cells in the implantation area (Prévot et al., 2020). Additionally, thickness of silicon structures did not fit to the natural curvature of the retina for proper visualization of the environment, which disarrange the large-field visual perception. Lastly, these silicon structures are limited for minimization, because of microfabrication limits of silicon and metal combination structures (Huang et al., 2020).

Because of these limitations, novel semiconductor nanomaterials should be investigated for both neural and retinal stimulation. Currently, p-i-n silicon diode structures are investigated to decrease electrode size (Jiang et al., 2018). But decrease in the size of the diode leads to a decrease in capacitive component of the electrical stimulus and increases on the thermal and faradaic components of the electrical stimulation (Jiang et al., 2018). This situation creates important problems for biocompatibility of the confined nanoscale electrodes in biomedical applications. Also, P3HT polymeric nanoparticles are investigated for the retinal stimulation. In this studies, the capacitive electrical stimulation mechanism is hypothesized, but not quantitatively demonstrated (Maya-Vetencourt et al., 2020). Lack of the return electrode, current drive without confinement, and increased oxidative stress are also important problems for these structures (Manfredi et al., 2019).

In this thesis, I have focused on retinal prosthesis applications for quantum dots-based interfaces. They could induce action potentials in primary hippocampal neurons, which enables biocompatible neuromodulation with photostimulation of these interfaces. In next phase, PbS and AlSb QDs based retinal prostheses also induce retinal stimulation with photostimulation. Unfortunately, required light levels for neural stimulation are significantly higher than ocular safety limits. Also, both AlSb and PbS QDs based retinal prostheses induce gliosis and retinal damage in subretinal implantation area.

In this study, mentioned challenges and concerns in previous studies on retinal stimulation systems were addressed. Quantum dots-based interfaces enable more precise spatial confinement, high tunability for light spectrum, and better biocompatibility for neural stimulation. Especially PbS and AlSb QDs based photovoltaic structures were focused on in this study. Although precise neuromodulation ability and increased biocompatibility observed in in vitro settings, they could not rescue functional visual perception in the degenerated retinas within ocular safety limits. For the failure of these quantum dots-based structures, three main

concerns should be addressed: aspects of biocompatibility, mechanisms of neural stimulation, and production of a precise visual percept. After these concerns addressed, alternative quantum dots-based structures, such as InP QDs and PTB7-Th:PC71BM based interfaces, could be used in retinal stimulation systems.

4.1. Aspects of Biocompatibility

Even in most of the biomaterial and neural interface studies, cell viability, cytotoxicity, and cell morphology were investigated, other cellular parameters, such as inflammation, fibrosis, foreign body response and oxidative stress, mostly ignored. This ignorance creates enormous burden and unfulfillable challenges for preclinical and clinical investigators (Benfenati & Lanzani, 2021). This innovative gap between laboratory and clinics became more visible in recent years, because of the increased innovative rate in science and technology. Especially nanoparticle-tissue interactions came into one of the highly interested topics in biomedical and material sciences (Verma & Stellacci, 2010). Chemistry of the surface, electrical structure, hydrophilicity, roughness, stability, elasticity, bending stiffness, size and shape of nanoparticles are significant factors for cell-nanoparticle integration in biomedical applications (Li et al., 2017). Especially in neural tissue, such as retina, foreign body response to the interfaces leads to immediate rejection and unresolvable dysfunction of the implant and creates continuous progressive inflammation, gliosis, and fibrosis in the implantation area (Kozai et al., 2015). Even incredibly optimistic in vitro experimental results did not bring good in vivo results in its train. Micro-scale systems, over-monitoring, low variability, and single cell-based approaches creates false transability hopes during in vitro investigations (Ungerleider & Christman, 2014). Because of these reasons, novel biointerfaces should be investigated with suspicion in both in vivo and novel in vitro models, such as organoids. Especially for the neural interfaces, multicellular central nervous system models should be used to observe foreign body response, which driven by microglia and astrocytes in extracellular matrix (Gulino et al., 2019).

Figure 4.1: Different cell behaviors of primary astrocytes in biocompatible surfaces with different young's moduli: (a) Poly-d-lysine (~ 0.12 MPa) and (b) polystyrene (~ 3.2 GPa). Cell cytoskeletons stained with anti-vimentin antibody (purple) and nuclei stained with DAPI (blue).

Even all other properties of biomaterials are in the range of biocompatibility, only high bending stiffness could lead to inflammation, gliosis, and fibrosis reactions, because of impaired microglia and astrocyte behavior (Figure 4.1). Neural stimulation systems are mostly stiffer than other biomaterials, because of their semiconductive structure. Because of this, not only neural cell response but also responses of glia, microglia, and astrocytes to the neural interfaces should be examined and long-term biocompatibility of the interfaces should be optimized by changing the nanoparticle surface characteristics and structure (Moshayedi et al., 2014).

Figure 4.2: Immunofluorescence staining of astrocytes on ITO and PEDOT:PSS based interfaces. Green indicates F-actin, a cytoskeleton marker, red indicates GFAP, a glial cell marker, purple indicates vimentin, a glial cell marker, and blue indicates DAPI, a nucleus marker (Han et al., 2020).

Figure 4.3: MTT toxicity assay results for primary astrocytes on PEDOT:PSS based interfaces (n = 4).

In the study of Han et al, they investigated star-like morphological response of the astrocytes for neural interface, which also significantly affect functionality of the neuro-electronic interface via foreign body response (Figure 4.2) (Han et al., 2020). In this thesis, investigation of device biocompatibility on different types of neuroglial cells is major deficit in experimental design. In further studies, investigation of astrocyte and microglia behavior on neural interfaces should be one of the essential biocompatibility assays for neural compatibility of the device.

Chronic inflammatory cascades could be started by implantation damage or blood vessel ruptures in the implantation area (Jorfi et al., 2014). Continuous inflammation or blood penentrance to the neural tissue will create neurotoxic environment around the interface. Furthermore, displaced neurons and glia cells along the insertion path will be damaged or killed, which will lead to synaptic dysregulations and disintegrations in targeted region. While microglia in the activated state able to release a variety of soluble pro-inflammatory and cytotoxic factors, such as nitric oxide, reactive nitrogen species, and reactive oxygen species (Alvarez et al., 2013). This cascade will also lead

to increased cellular oxidative damage, which will significantly more affect degeneration-sensitive neurons. Besides, microglia originated pro-inflammatory factors disrupts tight junctions in blood brain barrier and also will affect neural extracellular matrix circulation. These consequences of electrode implantation operation will lead to early inflammatory activation and may contribute to the unreliable functionality of the neural interface (Lotti et al., 2017).

After implantation damage to the tissue, excessive electrical stimulation made by the prostheses also will induce pro-inflammatory cascades repeatedly. Together with late inflammatory response of the microglia and macrophages, astrocytes and fibroblasts will start to accumulate around the neural interface. After weeks, they will create dense encapsulation layer and electrical stimulation capacity of the device will be lost slowly (Carnicer-Lombarte et al., 2021). Encapsulation of the interface will interfere neural communication, increase the electrical impedance and increase the distance between neurons and active surface (Gulino et al., 2019). Additionally, against to possible implant related infections antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory coating for neural prostheses could reduce tissue response in implantation area (Golabchi et al., 2019).

In a nutshell, chronic neuroinflammation, neural tissue loss, increased blood-brain barrier permeability, and fibrous encapsulation of the neural interfaces certainly affects functionality and biocompatibility of the devices. In both in vitro and in vivo settings, biomedical investigation of the neural interfaces should include innovative multicellular models, which will demonstrate all aspects of the neural tissue-interface integration (Hermann & Capadona, 2018).

4.2. On Mechanisms of Neural Stimulation

Eighty years ago, discovery of Hodgkin and Huxley opens the gates of voltage sensitive sodium channels in neurons (Barnett & Larkman, 2007). The action potential generation is the fundamental step of neuromodulation. For neural stimulation, faradaic or capacitive charge injection materials are in use. While faradaic

charge injection induce electron flow from interface to tissue, or otherwise, capacitive charging creates double layer ion-electron charge separation, which leads to biphasic electrical behavior in the tissue-interface junction (Stuart F Cogan, 2008).

In this study, different types of photo-capacitive current generation methods observed in quantum dots based neural interfaces. While PbS QDs based structure uses weak repetitive capacitive currents to induce action potential (Srivastava et al., 2020), AlSb nanocrystal-based structures have used significantly higher capacitive charges to increase success rate in action potential generation (Han et al., 2020). In addition to these interfaces, InP QDs based interfaces could induce both depolarization and hyperpolarization with changing multiplex structure, which based on the quantum dots and semiconductor polymers (Karatum et al., 2021).

In company with direct effects of electrical stimulation on neurons, neural regenerative properties of the electrical stimulation is one of the most studied feature in neuroscience (Zhang et al., 2021). Remodeling of the neurofilaments and increase of gene expressions which responsible from neural regeneration are main revealed mechanisms of neural regeneration via electrical stimulation (Al-Majed et al., 2004). Electrical stimulation of neurons with conductive scaffolds also increase neural differentiation markers, such as microtubule-associated protein-2 and neuron-specific class III beta-tubulin (Zhu et al., 2018). Du et al. shows similar neurofilament differentiation effect of electrical stimulation on both in vitro and in vivo models (Du et al., 2018). Electrical stimulation following application of neural stem cells in rat with sciatic nerve injury, induce neural regeneration and functional recovery of sciatic nerve. Neural regenerative effect of electrical stimulation is not limited with motor neurons, increased regeneration, and functionality in neural retina after electrical stimulation has been showed in various studies (Tandon et al., 2013; Yu et al., 2020). In near future, stem-cell based neural regenerative treatment with help of fine adjusted the state-of-art nanomaterial based photovoltaic devices for retinal and motor neural diseases could be a practical option in the clinics (Chen et al., 2019; Manthey et al., 2017).

Extracellular electrical stimulation of neurons must be a reversible activation of ion channels, especially Na^+ and K^+ channels. To avoid chemical and thermal damages of electrochemistry and electroporation, the electrical stimulation must be as weak as possible. For the successful action potential generation, interface should adhere geometry of the cell and should be in direct connection with sodium channels. Neuromodulation should be made via weak repetitive capacitive stimuli instead of faradaic or electrothermal stimuli. For highly integrated biointerfaces, an insulating and biocompatible passive layer is essential (Schoen & Fromherz, 2008). When considered from this point of view, the quantum dots based photovoltaic interfaces are great candidates for innovative photoelectrical stimulation systems. For various types of neuro-electronic interfaces, different types of electrical stimulation strategies should be investigated in further studies.

4.3. From Action Potential to Visual Percept

Not only induction of action potentials but also modulation of action potentials via membrane potential shifts is required for the neural stimulation systems. For retinal stimulation, two different approaches have been used for neuromodulation: charge dependent modulation and frequency dependent modulation. In retina bipolar cells act as electrical analog unit, because of their receptor potential based activity, and ganglion cells behave as electrical digital unit, as ON and OFF states, which leads to frequency based electrical transmission in optic nerve (Eickenscheidt et al., 2012). While current subretinal prosthesis systems are using electrical charge dependent modulation of bipolar neurons (Flores et al., 2019), epiretinal prostheses are dependent to frequency driven ganglion cell activity (Chenais et al., 2021). These two very different approaches have been used in all commercial retinal stimulation systems. taken in the design of these two devices. The Argus II uses an external camera with an image processor to convert an image into electrical impulses for ganglion cell stimulation, whereas the Alpha-IMS directly senses intraocular light and converts it to electrical energy using an amplifier and contrast unit to control the intensity of the stimulation.

As an epiretinal stimulation system, the next generation Argus device are covering 4° of visual field with theoretical maximum resolution with 240 retinal electrodes and 60 cortical electrodes. On the other hand, Alpha-IMS subretinal prosthesis system has 1500 electrodes, which cover smaller visual field of 10° × 10° with higher theoretical resolution (0.5°). In favor of Alpha-IMS, subretinal prostheses were not affected from saccadic eye movements, compared to epiretinal prostheses (Mills et al., 2017).

As a third way, several new technologies have emerged in the suprachoroidal retinal stimulation systems, such as the first 3D electrodes designed to achieve closer interaction with the retina (Bendali et al., 2015). This approach could compensate the loss of spatial resolution and high stimulation thresholds by reducing distance to target neurons. As another approach, hexagonal arrays could be useful to produce electrode grid on retinal prosthesis systems (Zhao et al., 2011). The hexagonal arrays could use concentric return electrodes for multiple active electrodes, which will ease the electrical stimulation of the retinal neurons. Addition to these approaches, improvements in micro electromechanics systems (MEMS), 3D printing and nanofabrication will bring new opportunities for retinal stimulation systems (Bareket et al., 2017).

One of the underrecognized feature of neural stimulation systems is thresholds for hyperpolarization and depolarization of the targeted neurons. Upper threshold for the depolarization of the ganglion neurons were studied by using charge-balanced biphasic pulses of various amplitude and phase duration (Meng et al., 2018), suggests that RGC upper threshold could block axonal transmission of the action potential in only under limited stimulation conditions. Localized membrane hyperpolarization of the stimulus electrode, electrical influence of voltage gated sodium channels, and the inhibitory effect of maximized stimulation rate in electric stimulation could lead to decreased depolarization threshold in the retinal ganglion neurons (T. Guo et al., 2019). Because of these complex neural processes, subretinal stimulation of the retina could be more reliable in chronic retinal stimulation systems.

For subretinal stimulation systems, pixel formation of the neural interfaces is the essential for the localized phosphene generation in the retina. Herewith ON and OFF classification of bipolar and ganglion cells (Werginz et al., 2015), color and luminance selective bipolar cells (Li & DeVries, 2006), and integrated behavior of horizontal, amacrine and various types of bipolar cells should be in consideration to design retinal prosthesis systems (Ho et al., 2020). The constructive nature of retinal information processing requires the deep understanding of induced 3D electrical field distribution for the optimal coupling in retina and neural stimulation framework for retinal signal processing (Werginz et al., 2020). Even in fine-tuned high-density 3D pixelated retinal prosthesis, principal components of integrated synaptic network of retina, such as ribbon synapses, will be affected and artificial visual processing will not achieve the levels before blindness (Moser et al., 2020). Because of those reasons, nanoparticle decorated tissue-like photoactive polymers should be main focus of investigations for restoration of vision rather than microscale pixelated photoelectrode based devices.

In nanoparticle-based strategies for optical stimulation of the retina, P3HT and Au-TiO₂ based structures are in the focus of interest. In a recent study, P3HT nanoparticles were subretinally injected in the rat retinas with retinitis pigmentosa and the subretinal injection of conjugated P3HT nanoparticles, promotes photoactivation of inner retinal neurons and leads to electrophysiological and behavioral response to light without any inflammatory process in retina (Maya-Vetencourt et al., 2020). Like this study, Tang et al. have demonstrated functional and behavioral rescue of the visual perception in daylight intensity levels with Au-TiO₂ nanowires in blind mice (Tang et al., 2018). Both these studies show remarkable contributions of nanoparticle-based approaches in retinal stimulation devices.

In this study, quantum dots based neural interfaces were investigated as novel candidates for the retinal stimulation systems. Photocapacitive, planar, subretinal design preferred because of biocompatible, easy, long term stable neural stimulation capacity of the retinal interfaces. High biocompatibility and effective neuromodulation capacity of the interfaces have demonstrated in all types of the quantum dots based neural and retinal interfaces. Unfortunately, good results in in vitro models of

neuromodulation could not be followed up with favorable in vivo application results. Both AlSb and PbS QDs based retinal interfaces, fail to stimulate degenerative retinas of the rats in safe light exposure limits, despite of their biocompatible and non-toxic composition in in vivo application. As alternative to these structures, InP QDs and PTB7-Th:PC71BM based interfaces will be tried for retinal stimulation, on account of their good in vitro electrophysiology and neural biocompatibility results. For future design of the retinal prostheses, high density pixelated structure with return and active electrodes, an infrastructure with low bending stiffness and young's moduli, long term stability of the photovoltaic surface even in liquid environment, integrative neural surface for better neural attachment, and directional steady capacitive current generation in low intensity light stimulation ($\sim 500 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$) should be implemented. All in vitro biocompatibility, which includes all cell types of central neural system, and electrophysiology studies, which includes single cell and multiple cell population measurements, should be conducted before, during, and after production, refinement, and validation of the design of the retinal stimulation systems. By this way, reproducible, completely biocompatible, high effective and behaviorally functional retinal prostheses could be made.

Chapter 5

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

In this study, quantum dots based neural and retinal interfaces were in the center of interest. This study has progressed from material production to in vivo studies. With the emphasis on quantum dots based neural interfaces, both future direction and emerging challenges have demonstrated, and fundamental concept of the retinal stimulation systems were investigated. The state-of-the-art in vivo and in vitro techniques shaped the current understanding about retinal stimulation systems in detail. In this highly interdisciplinary research area, this study helps to envision future of retinal prosthetics and manifests incoming challenges in nanoparticle based neural and retinal interfaces. Ideal retinal prosthesis should be porous for nutrition flow to keep healthy photoreceptor cells alive, flexible to match the unique curvature of the retina, wireless to decrease surgery related infections, highly pixelated to acquire normal visual acuity, soft to reduce tissue-electrode mismatch, capacitive for safe and repetitive electrostimulation, and removable to stop any adverse event during implantation. Toward this goal, multiplex structure with novel nanoparticles, such as quantum dots, should be combined in wide range. Integration of mesh-like structures or hydrogel based soft electronics could be innovative structural approaches for the retinal stimulation devices.

REFERENCES

- Abbott, C. J., et al. (2019). Effect of chronic electrical stimulation with a fully implantable electrode on photoreceptor survival in a retinal degeneration model. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*, 60(9), 4992-4992.
- Abbott, C. J., et al. (2018). Safety Studies for a 44-Channel Suprachoroidal Retinal Prosthesis: A Chronic Passive Study. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*, 59(3), 1410-1424. <https://doi.org/10.1167/iovs.17-23086>
- Abdallah, W., et al. (2018). Implantation of multiple suprachoroidal electrode arrays in rabbits. *J Curr Ophthalmol*, 30(1), 68-73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joco.2017.11.007>
- Ahuja, A. K., & Behrend, M. R. (2013). The Argus II retinal prosthesis: factors affecting patient selection for implantation. *Prog Retin Eye Res*, 36, 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.preteyeres.2013.01.002>
- Airaghi Leccardi, M. J. I., et al. (2020). Photovoltaic organic interface for neuronal stimulation in the near-infrared. *Communications Materials*, 1(1), 21. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43246-020-0023-4>
- Al-Majed, A. A., et al. (2004). Electrical Stimulation Accelerates and Enhances Expression of Regeneration-Associated Genes in Regenerating Rat Femoral Motoneurons. *Cellular and Molecular Neurobiology*, 24(3), 379-402. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:CEMN.0000022770.66463.f7>
- Alvarez, J. I., et al. (2013). Glial influence on the blood brain barrier. *Glia*, 61(12), 1939-1958. <https://doi.org/10.1002/glia.22575>
- Anselmo, A. C., & Mitragotri, S. (2016). Nanoparticles in the clinic. *Bioengineering & translational medicine*, 1(1), 10-29.

- Ayton, L. N., et al. (2020). An update on retinal prostheses. *Clinical Neurophysiology*, 131(6), 1383-1398.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinph.2019.11.029>
- Bahmani-Jalali, H., et al. (2018). Excitonic energy transfer within InP/ZnS quantum dot langmuir–blodgett assemblies. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 122(22), 11616-11622.
- Bahmani-Jalali, H., et al. (2018). Effective neural photostimulation using indium-Based type-II quantum dots. *ACS Nano*, 12(8), 8104-8114.
- Bahmani-Jalali, H., et al. (2019). Colloidal Aluminum Antimonide Quantum Dots. *Chemistry of Materials*, 31(13), 4743-4747.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.9b00905>
- Bahmani Jalali, H., et al. (2019). Biocompatible quantum funnels for neural photostimulation. *Nano Letters*, 19(9), 5975-5981.
- Barbruni, G. L., et al. (2020). Miniaturised Wireless Power Transfer Systems for Neurostimulation: A Review. *IEEE Transactions on biomedical circuits and systems*, 14(6), 1160-1178. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBCAS.2020.3038599>
- Bareket, L., et al. (2017). Progress in artificial vision through suprachoroidal retinal implants. *Journal of neural engineering*, 14(4), 045002.
- Barkhouse, D. A. R., et al. (2011). Depleted bulk heterojunction colloidal quantum dot photovoltaics. *Advanced Materials*, 23(28), 3134-3138.
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/adma.201101065>
- Barnett, M. W., & Larkman, P. M. (2007). The action potential. *Practical neurology*, 7(3), 192-197.
- Benav, H., et al. (2010). Restoration of useful vision up to letter recognition capabilities using subretinal microphotodiodes. *Conf Proc IEEE Eng Med Biol Soc*, 2010, 5919-5922. <https://doi.org/10.1109/iembs.2010.5627549>
- Bendali, A., et al. (2015). Synthetic 3D diamond-based electrodes for flexible retinal neuroprostheses: model, production and in vivo biocompatibility. *Biomaterials*, 67, 73-83.
- Benfenati, F., & Lanzani, G. (2021). Clinical translation of nanoparticles for neural stimulation. *Nature Reviews Materials*, 6(1), 1-4.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41578-020-00267-8>

- Bertschinger, D. R., et al. (2008). A review of in vivo animal studies in retinal prosthesis research. *Graefes Archive for Clinical and Experimental Ophthalmology*, 246(11), 1505-1517. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00417-008-0891-7>
- Beyeler, M., et al. (2017). pulse2percept: A Python-based simulation framework for bionic vision. *bioRxiv*, 148015. <https://doi.org/10.1101/148015>
- Bloch, E., et al. (2019). Advances in retinal prosthesis systems. *Therapeutic advances in ophthalmology*, 11, 2515841418817501.
- Bourne, R., et al. (2012). Global Burden of Visual Impairment and Blindness. *Archives of Ophthalmology*, 130(5), 645-647. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archophthalmol.2012.1032>
- Bui, B. V., & Fortune, B. (2004). Ganglion cell contributions to the rat full-field electroretinogram. *The Journal of physiology*, 555(1), 153-173.
- Busskamp, V., et al. (2012). Optogenetic therapy for retinitis pigmentosa. *Gene therapy*, 19(2), 169.
- Carnicer-Lombarte, A., et al. (2021). Foreign Body Reaction to Implanted Biomaterials and Its Impact in Nerve Neuroprosthetics [Systematic Review]. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 9(271). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2021.622524>
- Caspi, A., et al. (2016). Eye movements as a marker for visual prosthesis spatial mapping - A feasibility study using a blind patient implanted with the Argus II retinal prosthesis. *Conf Proc IEEE Eng Med Biol Soc*, 2016, 5443-5446. <https://doi.org/10.1109/embc.2016.7591958>
- Chader, G. J., et al. (2009). Artificial vision: needs, functioning, and testing of a retinal electronic prosthesis. *Prog Brain Res*, 175, 317-332. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0079-6123\(09\)17522-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0079-6123(09)17522-2)
- Chen, C., et al. (2019). Electrical stimulation as a novel tool for regulating cell behavior in tissue engineering. *Biomaterials Research*, 23(1), 25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40824-019-0176-8>
- Chen, R., et al. (2017). Neural recording and modulation technologies. *Nature Reviews Materials*, 2(2), 1-16.

-
- Chenais, N. A. L., et al. (2021). Photovoltaic retinal prosthesis restores high-resolution responses to single-pixel stimulation in blind retinas. *Communications Materials*, 2(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43246-021-00133-2>
- Chow, A. Y., et al. (2004). The artificial silicon retina microchip for the treatment of vision loss from retinitis pigmentosa. *Arch Ophthalmol*, 122(4), 460-469. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archoph.122.4.460>
- Chow, A. Y., et al. (2002). Subretinal implantation of semiconductor-based photodiodes: durability of novel implant designs. *J Rehabil Res Dev*, 39(3), 313-321.
- Chuang, A. T., et al. (2014). Retinal implants: a systematic review. *British Journal of Ophthalmology*, 98(7), 852-856. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjophthalmol-2013-303708>
- Cogan, S. F. (2008). Neural stimulation and recording electrodes. *Annu. Rev. Biomed. Eng.*, 10, 275-309.
- Cogan, S. F. (2008). Neural stimulation and recording electrodes. *Annu Rev Biomed Eng*, 10, 275-309. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.bioeng.10.061807.160518>
- Cowey, A., & Walsh, V. (2001). Tickling the brain: studying visual sensation, perception and cognition by transcranial magnetic stimulation. *Prog Brain Res*, 134, 411-425.
- Creel, D. J. (2019). Visually evoked potentials. *Handbook of clinical neurology*, 160, 501-522.
- Cuenca, N., et al. (2014). Cellular responses following retinal injuries and therapeutic approaches for neurodegenerative diseases. *Progress in Retinal and Eye Research*, 43, 17-75.
- D'Cruz, P. M., et al. (2000). Mutation of the receptor tyrosine kinase gene *Mertk* in the retinal dystrophic RCS rat. *Human Molecular Genetics*, 9(4), 645-651.
- da Cruz, L., et al. (2013). The Argus II epiretinal prosthesis system allows letter and word reading and long-term function in patients with profound vision loss. *Br J Ophthalmol*, 97(5), 632-636. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjophthalmol-2012-301525>

- da Cruz, L., et al. (2016). Five-Year Safety and Performance Results from the Argus II Retinal Prosthesis System Clinical Trial. *Ophthalmology*, 123(10), 2248-2254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ophtha.2016.06.049>
- da Cruz, L., et al. (2018). Phase 1 clinical study of an embryonic stem cell–derived retinal pigment epithelium patch in age-related macular degeneration. *Nature biotechnology*, 36(4), 328.
- Dagnelie, G. (2012). Retinal implants: emergence of a multidisciplinary field. *Current opinion in neurology*, 25(1), 67-75. <https://doi.org/10.1097/WCO.0b013e32834f02c3>
- Daiger, S., et al. (1998). Data services and software for identifying genes and mutations causing retinal degeneration. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*, 39(S295).
- Danis, R. P., & Davis, M. D. (2008). Proliferative diabetic retinopathy. In *Diabetic retinopathy* (pp. 29-65). Springer.
- Daschner, R., et al. (2018). Functionality and performance of the subretinal implant chip Alpha AMS. *Sens. Mater*, 30(2), 179-192.
- Davies, M., et al. (2007). Neurotoxic lesions of the rat perirhinal and postrhinal cortices and their impact on biconditional visual discrimination tasks. *Behavioural Brain Research*, 176(2), 274-283.
- Davies, M., et al. (2007). Neurotoxic lesions of the rat perirhinal and postrhinal cortices and their impact on biconditional visual discrimination tasks. *Behav Brain Res*, 176(2), 274-283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbr.2006.10.005>
- Deisseroth, K. (2011). Optogenetics. *Nature methods*, 8(1), 26.
- Delori, F. C., et al. (2007). Maximum permissible exposures for ocular safety (ANSI 2000), with emphasis on ophthalmic devices. *Journal of the Optical Society of America A*, 24(5), 1250-1265. <https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSAA.24.001250>
- Devatha, G., et al. (2017). Electrostatically driven resonance energy transfer in “cationic” biocompatible indium phosphide quantum dots. *Chemical science*, 8(5), 3879-3884.
- Dias, M. F., et al. (2018). Molecular genetics and emerging therapies for retinitis pigmentosa: Basic research and clinical perspectives. *Progress in Retinal and Eye Research*, 63, 107-131. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.preteyeres.2017.10.004>

- Dowling, J. (2009). Current and future prospects for optoelectronic retinal prostheses. *Eye*, 23(10), 1999-2005.
- Du, J., et al. (2018). Optimal electrical stimulation boosts stem cell therapy in nerve regeneration. *Biomaterials*, 181, 347-359.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2018.07.015>
- Duh, E. J., et al. (2017). Diabetic retinopathy: current understanding, mechanisms, and treatment strategies. *JCI Insight*, 2(14), e93751.
<https://doi.org/10.1172/jci.insight.93751>
- Eickenscheidt, M., et al. (2012). Electrical stimulation of retinal neurons in epiretinal and subretinal configuration using a multicapacitor array. *J Neurophysiol*, 107(10), 2742-2755. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.00909.2011>
- Fairfield, J. A. (2018). Nanostructured Materials for Neural Electrical Interfaces. *Advanced Functional Materials*, 28(12), 1701145.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201701145>
- Fernandes, R. A., et al. (2012). Artificial vision through neuronal stimulation. *Neurosci Lett*, 519(2), 122-128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2012.01.063>
- Flores, T., et al. (2019). Honeycomb-shaped electro-neural interface enables cellular-scale pixels in subretinal prosthesis. *Scientific reports*, 9(1), 10657.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-47082-y>
- Fujikado, T. (2017). Retinal prosthesis by suprachoroidal-transretinal stimulation (STS), Japanese approach. In *Artificial Vision* (pp. 139-150). Springer.
- Gauvin, M., et al. (2016). Assessing the contribution of the oscillatory potentials to the genesis of the photopic ERG with the discrete wavelet transform. *BioMed research international*, 2016.
- Gekeler, K., et al. (2018). Implantation, removal and replacement of subretinal electronic implants for restoration of vision in patients with retinitis pigmentosa. *Curr Opin Ophthalmol*, 29(3), 239-247.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/icu.0000000000000467>
- Ghodasra, D. H., et al. (2016). Worldwide Argus II implantation: recommendations to optimize patient outcomes. *BMC Ophthalmol*, 16, 52.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12886-016-0225-1>

- Goetz, G., & Palanker, D. (2016). Electronic approaches to restoration of sight. *Reports on Progress in Physics*, 79(9), 096701.
- Golabchi, A., et al. (2019). Zwitterionic polymer/polydopamine coating reduce acute inflammatory tissue responses to neural implants. *Biomaterials*, 225, 119519. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2019.119519>
- Gregori, N. Z., et al. (2018). Retinal Anatomy and Electrode Array Position in Retinitis Pigmentosa Patients After Argus II Implantation: An International Study. *Am J Ophthalmol*, 193, 87-99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajo.2018.06.012>
- Gulino, M., et al. (2019). Tissue Response to Neural Implants: The Use of Model Systems Toward New Design Solutions of Implantable Microelectrodes [Review]. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 13(689). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2019.00689>
- Guo, R., et al. (2019). Development and Application of Cochlear Implant-Based Electric-Acoustic Stimulation of Spiral Ganglion Neurons. *Acs Biomaterials Science & Engineering*, 5(12), 6735-6741. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsbiomaterials.9b01265>
- Guo, T., et al. (2019). Mediating Retinal Ganglion Cell Spike Rates Using High-Frequency Electrical Stimulation [Original Research]. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 13(413). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2019.00413>
- Ham, W. T., et al. (1976). Retinal sensitivity to damage from short wavelength light. *Nature*, 260(5547), 153-155. <https://doi.org/10.1038/260153a0>
- Hamel, C. (2006). Retinitis pigmentosa. *Orphanet journal of rare diseases*, 1(1), 1-12.
- Han, M., et al. (2021). Photovoltaic neurointerface based on aluminum antimonide nanocrystals. *Communications Materials*, 2(1), 19. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43246-021-00123-4>
- Han, M., et al. (2020). Organic Photovoltaic Pseudocapacitors for Neurostimulation. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, 12(38), 42997-43008.
- Hanitzsch, R. (1993). Cornea-Negative and Cornea-Positive Slow Components of the ERG and Light-induced Extracellular Potassium Changes. In W. Haschke, E. J. Speckmann, & A. I. Roitbak (Eds.), *Slow Potential Changes in the Brain* (pp. 203-218). Birkhäuser Boston. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4757-1379-4_18

- Hartong, D. T., et al. (2006). Retinitis pigmentosa. *The Lancet*, 368(9549), 1795-1809.
- Hau, S. K., et al. (2008). Air-stable inverted flexible polymer solar cells using zinc oxide nanoparticles as an electron selective layer. *Applied Physics Letters*, 92(25), 225.
- Hermann, J. K., & Capadona, J. R. (2018). Understanding the Role of Innate Immunity in the Response to Intracortical Microelectrodes. *Critical reviews in biomedical engineering*, 46(4), 341-367.
<https://doi.org/10.1615/CritRevBiomedEng.2018027166>
- Heynen, H., et al. (1985). Origin of the oscillatory potentials in the primate retina. *Vision research*, 25(10), 1365-1373.
- Ho, A. C., et al. (2015). Long-Term Results from an Epiretinal Prosthesis to Restore Sight to the Blind. *Ophthalmology*, 122(8), 1547-1554.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ophtha.2015.04.032>
- Ho, E., et al. (2019). Characteristics of prosthetic vision in rats with subretinal flat and pillar electrode arrays. *J Neural Eng*, 16(6), 066027.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1741-2552/ab34b3>
- Ho, E., et al. (2020). Decoding network-mediated retinal response to electrical stimulation: implications for fidelity of prosthetic vision. *Journal of neural engineering*.
- Hogan, M. K., et al. (2020). Neural Stimulation and Molecular Mechanisms of Plasticity and Regeneration: A Review [Systematic Review]. *Frontiers in Cellular Neuroscience*, 14(271). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncel.2020.00271>
- Hong, G., & Lieber, C. M. (2019). Novel electrode technologies for neural recordings. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 20(6), 330-345.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41583-019-0140-6>
- Hornig, R., et al. (2007). The IMI retinal implant system. In *Artificial sight* (pp. 111-128). Springer.
- Huang, T. W., et al. (2020). Vertical-junction Photodiodes for Smaller Pixels in Retinal Prostheses. *bioRxiv*.

- Humayun, M. S., et al. (2009). Preliminary 6 month results from the Argus II epiretinal prosthesis feasibility study. *Conf Proc IEEE Eng Med Biol Soc, 2009*, 4566-4568. <https://doi.org/10.1109/iembs.2009.5332695>
- Im, M., & Kim, S.-W. (2020). Neurophysiological and medical considerations for better-performing microelectronic retinal prostheses. *J. Neural Eng, 17*(3).
- Jacak, L., et al. (2013). *Quantum dots*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Jiang, Y., et al. (2018). Rational design of silicon structures for optically controlled multiscale biointerfaces. *Nature biomedical engineering, 2*(7), 508-521.
- Jin, Z., & Hildebrandt, N. (2012). Semiconductor quantum dots for in vitro diagnostics and cellular imaging. *Trends in biotechnology, 30*(7), 394-403.
- Johansson, U. E., et al. (2010). A battery of cell- and structure-specific markers for the adult porcine retina. *J Histochem Cytochem, 58*(4), 377-389. <https://doi.org/10.1369/jhc.2009.954933>
- Jonas, J. B., et al. (2010). Prevalence, awareness, control, and associations of arterial hypertension in a rural central India population: the Central India Eye and Medical Study. *American journal of hypertension, 23*(4), 347-350.
- Jorfi, M., et al. (2014). Progress towards biocompatible intracortical microelectrodes for neural interfacing applications. *Journal of neural engineering, 12*(1), 011001.
- Joseph, K., et al. (2021). *Transcriptional characterization of the glial response due to chronic neural implantation of flexible microprobes*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.05.31.446394>
- Kandel, E. R., et al. (2012). *Principles of Neural Science, Fifth Edition*. McGraw-Hill Education. <https://books.google.com.tr/books?id=Z2yVUTnIIQsC>
- Kannabiran, C. (2008). Retinitis pigmentosa: genetics and gene-based approaches to therapy. *Expert Review of Ophthalmology, 3*(4), 417-429.
- Karatum, O., et al. (2021). Nanoengineering InP Quantum Dot-based Photoactive Biointerfaces for Optical Control of Neurons. *Frontiers in Neuroscience, 15*, 724.
- Karatum, O., et al. (2019). Light-emitting devices based on type-II InP/ZnO quantum dots. *ACS photonics, 6*(4), 939-946.

- Kelly, S. K., & Rizzo, J. (2017). The Boston Retinal Implant. In *Artificial Vision* (pp. 85-97). Springer.
- Kern, T. S. (2007). Contributions of inflammatory processes to the development of the early stages of diabetic retinopathy. *Exp Diabetes Res*, 2007.
- Kozai, T. D., et al. (2015). Brain tissue responses to neural implants impact signal sensitivity and intervention strategies. *ACS Chem Neurosci*, 6(1), 48-67. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cn500256e>
- Kozielski, K. L., et al. (2021). Nonresonant powering of injectable nanoelectrodes enables wireless deep brain stimulation in freely moving mice. *Science advances*, 7(3), eabc4189. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abc4189>
- Lacour, S. P., et al. (2016). Materials and technologies for soft implantable neuroprostheses. *Nature Reviews Materials*, 1(10), 1-14.
- Lawand, N., et al. (2012). Thin titanium nitride films deposited using DC magnetron sputtering used for neural stimulation and sensing purposes. *Procedia Engineering*, 47, 726-729.
- Lee, S. W., et al. (2009). Development of Microelectrode Arrays for Artificial Retinal Implants Using Liquid Crystal Polymers. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*, 50(12), 5859-5866. <https://doi.org/10.1167/iovs.09-3743>
- Lei, X., & Liao, K. (2017). Understanding the influences of EEG reference: a large-scale brain network perspective. *Frontiers in neuroscience*, 11, 205.
- Li, J., et al. (2017). Insight into the interactions between nanoparticles and cells [10.1039/C6BM00714G]. *Biomaterials science*, 5(2), 173-189. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6BM00714G>
- Li, W., & DeVries, S. H. (2006). Bipolar cell pathways for color and luminance vision in a dichromatic mammalian retina. *Nature Neuroscience*, 9(5), 669-675. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn1686>
- Li, Z., et al. (2019). Polydopamine-functionalized black phosphorus quantum dots for cancer theranostics. *Applied Materials Today*, 15, 297-304.
- Lim, L. S., et al. (2012). Age-related macular degeneration. *The Lancet*, 379(9827), 1728-1738. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(12\)60282-7](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(12)60282-7)

- Linderholm, P., et al. (2013). Long-term in vivo impedance changes of subretinal microelectrodes implanted in dystrophic P23H rats. *Int J Artif Organs*, 36(9), 612-619. <https://doi.org/10.5301/ijao.5000213>
- Loizos, K., et al. (2018). Increasing electrical stimulation efficacy in degenerated retina: stimulus waveform design in a multiscale computational model. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, 26(6), 1111-1120.
- Lorach, H., et al. (2015). Photovoltaic restoration of sight with high visual acuity. *Nature medicine*, 21(5), 476.
- Lotti, F., et al. (2017). Invasive Intraneural Interfaces: Foreign Body Reaction Issues. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 11, 497-497. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2017.00497>
- Luo, Y. H.-L., & Da Cruz, L. (2016). The Argus® II retinal prosthesis system. *Progress in Retinal and Eye Research*, 50, 89-107.
- Luu, J., & Palczewski, K. (2018). Human aging and disease: Lessons from age-related macular degeneration. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(12), 2866-2872. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1721033115>
- Manfredi, G., et al. (2019). Photochemistry of organic retinal prostheses. *Annual review of physical chemistry*, 70, 99-121.
- Manthey, A. L., et al. (2017). Using Electrical Stimulation to Enhance the Efficacy of Cell Transplantation Therapies for Neurodegenerative Retinal Diseases: Concepts, Challenges, and Future Perspectives. *Cell Transplantation*, 26(6), 949-965. <https://doi.org/10.3727/096368917X694877>
- Mattsson, M.-O., et al. (2012). *Health Effects of Artificial Light*.
- Maya-Vetencourt, J. F., et al. (2017). A fully organic retinal prosthesis restores vision in a rat model of degenerative blindness. *Nature materials*, 16(6), 681-689.
- Maya-Vetencourt, J. F., et al. (2017). A fully organic retinal prosthesis restores vision in a rat model of degenerative blindness. *Nat Mater*, 16(6), 681-689. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat4874>

- Maya-Vetencourt, J. F., et al. (2020). Subretinally injected semiconducting polymer nanoparticles rescue vision in a rat model of retinal dystrophy. *Nature Nanotechnology*, 15(8), 698-708. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-020-0696-3>
- Meng, K., et al. (2018). Upper stimulation threshold for retinal ganglion cell activation. *Journal of neural engineering*, 15(4), 046012.
- Menzel-Severing, J., et al. (2012). Implantation and explantation of an active epiretinal visual prosthesis: 2-year follow-up data from the EPIRET3 prospective clinical trial. *Eye*, 26(4), 501-509.
- Meyer-Franke, A., et al. (1995). Characterization of the signaling interactions that promote the survival and growth of developing retinal ganglion cells in culture. *Neuron*, 15(4), 805-819. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0896-6273\(95\)90172-8](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0896-6273(95)90172-8)
- Michalet, X., et al. (2005). Quantum dots for live cells, in vivo imaging, and diagnostics. *Science*, 307(5709), 538-544.
- Mills, J. O., et al. (2017). Electronic retinal implants and artificial vision: journey and present. *Eye*, 31(10), 1383-1398. <https://doi.org/10.1038/eye.2017.65>
- Mitchell, P., et al. (2018). Age-related macular degeneration. *The Lancet*, 392(10153), 1147-1159.
- Moser, T., et al. (2020). Sensory Processing at Ribbon Synapses in the Retina and the Cochlea. *Physiological Reviews*, 100(1), 103-144. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00026.2018>
- Moshayedi, P., et al. (2014). The relationship between glial cell mechanosensitivity and foreign body reactions in the central nervous system. *Biomaterials*, 35(13), 3919-3925. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2014.01.038>
- Musarella, M. A., & MacDonald, I. M. (2011). Current Concepts in the Treatment of Retinitis Pigmentosa. *J Ophthalmol*, 2011, 753547. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2011/753547>
- Nayak, C. S., & Anilkumar, A. C. (2020). Eeg normal waveforms. *StatPearls [Internet]*.
- Nguyen, C. T., et al. (2016). Simultaneous recording of electroretinography and visual evoked potentials in anesthetized rats. *Journal of visualized experiments: JoVE*(113).

-
- Nguyen, C. T., et al. (2016). Simultaneous Recording of Electroretinography and Visual Evoked Potentials in Anesthetized Rats. *Journal of Visualized Experiments : JoVE*(113), 54158. <https://doi.org/10.3791/54158>
- Noell, W. K. (1954). The origin of the electroretinogram. *Am J Ophthalmol*, 38, 78-93.
- Noell, W. K., et al. (1966). Retinal Damage by Light in Rats. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*, 5(5), 450-473.
- Olmos de Koo, L. C., & Gregori, N. Z. (2016). The Argus II Retinal Prosthesis: A Comprehensive Review. *Int Ophthalmol Clin*, 56(4), 39-46. <https://doi.org/10.1097/iio.0000000000000144>
- Palanker, D., et al. (2020). Photovoltaic restoration of central vision in atrophic age-related macular degeneration. *Ophthalmology*, 127(8), 1097-1104.
- Palanker, D. V., et al. (2019). Restoration of sight in geographic atrophy using a photovoltaic subretinal prosthesis. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*, 60(9), 970-970.
- Pancrazio, J. J., et al. (2017). Thinking Small: Progress on Microscale Neurostimulation Technology. *Neuromodulation*, 20(8), 745-752. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ner.12716>
- Pappas, T. C., et al. (2007). Nanoscale engineering of a cellular interface with semiconductor nanoparticle films for photoelectric stimulation of neurons. *Nano Lett*, 7(2), 513-519. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl062513v>
- Paxinos, G., & Watson, C. (2006). *The rat brain in stereotaxic coordinates: hard cover edition*. Elsevier.
- Peachey, N. S., & Chow, A. Y. (1999). Subretinal implantation of semiconductor-based photodiodes: progress and challenges. *J Rehabil Res Dev*, 36(4), 371-376.
- Perlman, I. (2015). The electroretinogram: ERG by IDO Perlman. *Webvision: The Organization of the Retina and*.
- Prévot, P.-H., et al. (2020). Behavioural responses to a photovoltaic subretinal prosthesis implanted in non-human primates. *Nature Biomedical Engineering*, 4(2), 172-180.
- Prusky, G. T., et al. (2002). Variation in visual acuity within pigmented, and between pigmented and albino rat strains. *Behav Brain Res*, 136(2), 339-348.

- Prusky, G. T., et al. (2002). Variation in visual acuity within pigmented, and between pigmented and albino rat strains. *Behavioural Brain Research*, 136(2), 339-348.
- Quintana, Q., et al. (2016). Electroretinography: a biopotential to assess the function/dysfunction of the retina. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*,
- Rakoczy, E. P., et al. (2015). Gene therapy with recombinant adeno-associated vectors for neovascular age-related macular degeneration: 1 year follow-up of a phase 1 randomised clinical trial. *The Lancet*, 386(10011), 2395-2403.
[https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(15\)00345-1](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(15)00345-1)
- Ray, T. R., et al. (2019). Bio-Integrated Wearable Systems: A Comprehensive Review. *Chemical reviews*, 119(8), 5461-5533.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.8b00573>
- Sadtler, K., et al. (2016). Design, clinical translation and immunological response of biomaterials in regenerative medicine. *Nature Reviews Materials*, 1(7), 1-17.
- Schachat, A. P., et al. (2017). *Ryan's Retina E-Book*. Elsevier Health Sciences.
<https://books.google.com.tr/books?id=YWWwDgAAQBAJ>
- Schaffrath, K., et al. (2019). One-year safety and performance assessment of the Argus II retinal prosthesis: a postapproval study. *JAMA Ophthalmology*, 137(8), 896-902.
- Schatz, A., et al. (2011). Transcorneal electrical stimulation for patients with retinitis pigmentosa: a prospective, randomized, sham-controlled exploratory study. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*, 52(7), 4485-4496.
- Schoen, I., & Fromherz, P. (2008). Extracellular Stimulation of Mammalian Neurons Through Repetitive Activation of Na⁺ Channels by Weak Capacitive Currents on a Silicon Chip. *J Neurophysiol*, 100(1), 346-357.
<https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.90287.2008>
- Schubert, M. B., et al. (1999). Optimizing photodiode arrays for the use as retinal implants. *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical*, 74(1), 193-197.
[https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-4247\(98\)00313-6](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-4247(98)00313-6)
- Seitz, H., et al. (1998). Biocompatibility of polyethylene terephthalate (Trevira® hochfest) augmentation device in repair of the anterior cruciate ligament. *Biomaterials*, 19(1-3), 189-196.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0142961297002019?via%3Dihub>

Smith, J., et al. (2015). New and emerging technologies for the treatment of inherited retinal diseases: a horizon scanning review [Review]. *Eye*, 29, 1131.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/eye.2015.115>

Spooner, K. L., et al. (2018). The burden of neovascular age-related macular degeneration: a patient's perspective. *Clin Ophthalmol*, 12, 2483-2491.

<https://doi.org/10.2147/OPHTH.S185052>

Srivastava, S. B., et al. (2021). Bulk-heterojunction photocapacitors with high open-circuit voltage for low light intensity photostimulation of neurons. *Journal of Materials Chemistry C*, 9(5), 1755-1763.

Srivastava, S. B., et al. (2020). Efficient photocapacitors via ternary hybrid photovoltaic optimization for photostimulation of neurons. *Biomedical optics express*, 11(9), 5237-5248. <https://doi.org/10.1364/BOE.396068>

Stingl, K., et al. (2013). Artificial vision with wirelessly powered subretinal electronic implant alpha-IMS. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 280(1757), 20130077.

Stingl, K., et al. (2015). Subretinal visual implant alpha IMS—clinical trial interim report. *Vision Res*, 111, 149-160.

Stockton, R. A., & Slaughter, M. M. (1989). B-wave of the electroretinogram. A reflection of ON bipolar cell activity. *The Journal of general physiology*, 93(1), 101-122.

Tandon, N., et al. (2013). Biomimetic electrical stimulation platform for neural differentiation of retinal progenitor cells. *Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society. IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society. Annual International Conference, 2013*, 5666-5669. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EMBC.2013.6610836>

Tang, J., & Kern, T. S. (2011). Inflammation in diabetic retinopathy. *Progress in Retinal and Eye Research*, 30(5), 343-358.

<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.preteyeres.2011.05.002>

Tang, J., et al. (2018). Nanowire arrays restore vision in blind mice. *Nature Communications*, 9(1), 786. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-03212-0>

- Ting, D. S., et al. (2016). Diabetic retinopathy: global prevalence, major risk factors, screening practices and public health challenges: a review. *Clin Exp Ophthalmol*, 44(4), 260-277. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ceo.12696>
- Towle, V. L., et al. (2020). Postmortem investigation of a human cortical visual prosthesis that was implanted for 36 years. *Journal of neural engineering*, 17(4), 045010.
- Ungerleider, J. L., & Christman, K. L. (2014). Concise Review: Injectable Biomaterials for the Treatment of Myocardial Infarction and Peripheral Artery Disease: Translational Challenges and Progress. *STEM CELLS Translational Medicine*, 3(9), 1090-1099. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5966/sctm.2014-0049>
- Verbakel, S. K., et al. (2018). Non-syndromic retinitis pigmentosa. *Prog Retin Eye Res*, 66, 157-186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.preteyeres.2018.03.005>
- Verma, A., & Stellacci, F. (2010). Effect of surface properties on nanoparticle-cell interactions. *Small*, 6(1), 12-21. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.200901158>
- Wachtmeister, L. (1986). Spatial characteristics of the oscillatory potentials of the electroretinogram. *Acta ophthalmologica*, 64(6), 681-690.
- Wagner, A. M., et al. (2019). Quantum dots in biomedical applications. *Acta Biomaterialia*, 94, 44-63. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2019.05.022>
- Wang, K., et al. (2019). Light-Stimulated Synaptic Transistors Fabricated by a Facile Solution Process Based on Inorganic Perovskite Quantum Dots and Organic Semiconductors. *Small*, 15(11), 1900010. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.201900010>
- Wang, Y., & Guo, L. (2016). Nanomaterial-Enabled Neural Stimulation [Mini Review]. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 10(69). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2016.00069>
- Wei, W. (2018). Neural mechanisms of motion processing in the mammalian retina. *Annual review of vision science*, 4, 165-192.
- Weiland, J. D., & Humayun, M. S. (2014). Retinal prosthesis. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 61(5), 1412-1424.

- Weiland, J. D., et al. (2012). Smart image processing system for retinal prosthesis. 2012 Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society,
- Wellman, S. M., et al. (2018). A Materials Roadmap to Functional Neural Interface Design. *Advanced Functional Materials*, 28(12), 1701269.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201701269>
- Werginz, P., et al. (2015). Modeling the response of ON and OFF retinal bipolar cells during electric stimulation. *Vision Res*, 111, 170-181.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.visres.2014.12.002>
- Werginz, P., et al. (2020). On optimal coupling of the 'electronic photoreceptors' into the degenerate retina. *J Neural Eng*, 17(4), 045008.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1741-2552/aba0d2>
- Werner, J. S., & Chalupa, L. M. (2004). *The Visual Neurosciences*. MIT Press.
<https://books.google.com.tr/books?id=AN-sdYjcyvAC>
- WHO. (2019). *World report on vision*. World Health Organization.
<https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/328717>
- Wu, C.-Y., et al. (2018). *A CMOS 256-pixel Photovoltaics-powered Implantable Chip with Active Pixel Sensors and Iridium-oxide Electrodes for Subretinal Prostheses* (Vol. 30). <https://doi.org/10.18494/SAM.2018.1664>
- Yan, B., et al. (2016). Maintaining ocular safety with light exposure, focusing on devices for optogenetic stimulation. *Vision Res*, 121, 57-71.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.visres.2016.01.006>
- Yang, X., et al. (2019). Bioinspired neuron-like electronics. *Nature materials*, 18(5), 510-517. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41563-019-0292-9>
- Yıldız, E., et al. (2020). Effects of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus on Gene Expressions of Mouse Meibomian Glands. *Curr Eye Res*, 45(1), 72-80.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02713683.2019.1656750>
- Yonemura, D., & Kawasaki, K. (1979). New approaches to ophthalmic electrodiagnosis by retinal oscillatory potential, drug-induced responses from retinal pigment epithelium and cone potential. *Documenta Ophthalmologica*, 48(1), 163-222.

-
- Yoo, S., et al. (2019). Single-Cell Photothermal Neuromodulation for Functional Mapping of Neural Networks. *ACS Nano*, 13(1), 544-551.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.8b07277>
- Yu, H., et al. (2020). Noninvasive Electrical Stimulation Improves Photoreceptor Survival and Retinal Function in Mice with Inherited Photoreceptor Degeneration. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*, 61(4), 5-5.
<https://doi.org/10.1167/iovs.61.4.5>
- Yue, L., et al. (2016). Retinal stimulation strategies to restore vision: Fundamentals and systems. *Progress in Retinal and Eye Research*, 53, 21-47.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.preteyeres.2016.05.002>
- Zhang, J., et al. (2021). Conductive composite fiber with optimized alignment guides neural regeneration under electrical stimulation. *Advanced Healthcare Materials*, 10(3), 2000604.
- Zhao, Y., et al. (2011). A MEMS intraocular origami coil. 2011 16th International Solid-State Sensors, Actuators and Microsystems Conference,
- Zhu, W., et al. (2018). Enhanced neural stem cell functions in conductive annealed carbon nanofibrous scaffolds with electrical stimulation. *Nanomedicine: Nanotechnology, Biology and Medicine*, 14(7), 2485-2494.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nano.2017.03.018>
- Zimmerman, J. F., & Tian, B. (2018). Nongenetic Optical Methods for Measuring and Modulating Neuronal Response. *ACS Nano*, 12(5), 4086-4095.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.8b02758>
- Zrazhevskiy, P., et al. (2010). Designing multifunctional quantum dots for bioimaging, detection, and drug delivery. *Chemical Society Reviews*, 39(11), 4326-4354.
- Zrenner, E. (2002). Will Retinal Implants Restore Vision? *Science*, 295(5557), 1022-1025. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1067996>

HAYVAN DENEYLERİ YEREL ETİK KURUL KARARI

Toplantı Tarihi:	24.07.2018
Protokol No:	2018.HADYEK.018
Sorumlu Araştırmacı:	Afsun Şahin
Araştırma Başlığı:	Kuantum nokta temelli subretinal implant ile retinal distrofide görme yetisinin geri kazandırılması
Başlangıç tarihi:	25.07.2018
Hayvan türü ve sayıları:	16 adet RCS/Kyo Agouti Sıçan ve 16 adet Dark Agouti Sıçan

Koç Üniversitesi Etik Kurulu'na değerlendirilmek üzere başvuruda bulunduğunuz yukarıda künyesi yazılı projenizin başvuru dosyası ve ilgili belgeleri, Üniversitemiz "Hayvan DeneYleri Yerel Etik Kurulu" tarafından araştırmanın gerekçe, amaç, yaklaşım ve yöntemleri dikkate alınarak incelenmiştir.

Üniversite Senatosunun 5 Şubat 2016 tarih ve 2016/2 sayılı oturumunda kabul edilen "Hayvan DeneYleri Yerel Etik Kurulu (HADYEK) yönergesi" uyarınca yapılan inceleme sonucunda çalışmanın gerçekleştirilmesinde etik ve bilimsel sakınca bulunmadığına karar verilmiştir. Araştırmaya yukarıda verilen başlangıç tarihi itibarıyla başlayabilirsiniz.

Notlar:

- Araştırma başlangıç tarihinin gecikmesi durumunda Etik Kurul'a başvurularak tarihlerin değiştirilmesi gereklidir.
- Etik Kurul incelemesi ve onayı olmadan bu araştırmada kullanılan prosedürler, formlar ya da protokollerde herhangi bir değişiklik yapılamaz.

Saygılarımla,

Prof. Dr. Hakan S. Orer
Başkan

Rumelifeneri Yolu Sarıyer 34450 İstanbul T: 0212 338 10 00 F: 0212 338 12 05 www.ku.edu.tr

ETHICS COMMITTEE DECISION

Meeting Date:	12.06.2019
Protocol No:	2019.HADYEK.023
Principal Investigator	Sedat Nizamoğlu
Title:	Investigation of effects of PbS quantum dots based photoactive polymers on primary neuron culture under various range of light frequencies and intensities
Start Date:	15.06.2019
Duration of The Approval:	1 year (with a possible extension)

The research proposal with the title and protocol number given above and the supporting material have been thoroughly examined by the Animal Experiments Local Ethics Committee with regards to its aims, purpose, approach and methods.

The Committee reviewed the research proposal and approved the study protocol. You may begin your research on the start date listed above.

Best Regards,

Hakan S. Orer
Chairman

NB: This is the official translation of the original committee decision

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HAYVAN DENEYLERİ YEREL ETİK KURUL KARARI

Toplantı Tarihi:	29.05.2020
Protokol No:	2020.HADYEK.017
Sorumlu Araştırmacı:	Erdost Yıldız
Araştırma Başlığı:	Subretinal protez bağımlı fotoreseptör dejenerasyonunun davranışsal, elektrofizyolojik ve histolojik olarak incelenmesi
Başlangıç tarihi:	30.05.2020
Hayvan türü ve sayıları:	Sıçan (Wistar Albino): 48 adet

Koç Üniversitesi Etik Kurulu'na değerlendirilmek üzere başvuruda bulunduğunuz yukarıda künyesi yazılı projenizin başvuru dosyası ve ilgili belgeleri, Üniversitemiz "**Hayvan Deneyleri Yerel Etik Kurulu**" tarafından araştırmanın gereke, amaç, yaklaşım ve yöntemleri dikkate alınarak incelenmiştir.

Üniversite Senatosunun 5 Şubat 2016 tarih ve 2016/2 sayılı oturumunda kabul edilen "Hayvan Deneyleri Yerel Etik Kurulu (HADYEK) yönergesi" uyarınca yapılan inceleme sonucunda çalışmanın gerçekleştirilmesinde etik ve bilimsel sakınca bulunmadığına karar verilmiştir. Araştırmaya yukarıda verilen başlangıç tarihi itibarıyla başlayabilirsiniz.

Notlar:

- Araştırma başlangıç tarihinin gecikmesi durumunda Etik Kurul'a başvurularak tarihlerin değiştirilmesi gereklidir.
- Etik Kurul incelemesi ve onayı olmadan bu çalışmada kullanılan prosedürler, formlar ya da protokollerde herhangi bir değişiklik yapılamaz.

Saygılarımla,

Prof. Dr. Hakan S. Orer
Başkan

E-İMZALIDIR

<p>KUTTAM KOÇ UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER FOR TRANSLATIONAL MEDICINE</p>	Protocol: Primary Hippocampal Neuron Isolation
	Name: Erdost YILDIZ, MD
	Department: Neuroscience
	Date: 16.05.2021

All experimental procedure has been approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committees of Koç University according to Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on Protection of Animals Used for Scientific Purposes and the Republic of Turkey 5199 Animal Protection Law, Article 9 and 17. In this protocol, embryonic rats between 15th – 18th (E15-E18) days of a pregnant rat will be used. Two methods have commonly used to detect the exact pregnancy day in pregnant rats. The first method is observing the vaginal plaque of the female rat, which will occur on the mating day. The day the plaque occurs is considered as E0. The second method is by monitoring the weight of the pregnant rat. From first day (E0) to seventh day (E7), rat will gain approximately 10.5 grams. From seventh day (E7) to fifteenth day (E15), pregnant rat will gain approximately 21 grams. And from fifteenth day to end of the pregnancy, the rat will gain ~38 grams. Total weigh gain during pregnancy will be around 71 grams. When the total weight gain from coitus to two-weeks later is more than 30 grams of the embryo is considered as E15.(Paronis et al., 2014)

Chemicals & Media (Prepare in advance)

- **Coated Glass Coverslips¹**
 - Poly-D-lysine (PDL)/Poly-L-lysine(PLL) coated
 - *or* PDL(*or* PLL)/Laminin coated
 - *or* Matrigel coated
- **Dissection and Transport Solution**
 - 100 mL HBSS
 - 1.5 g Sucrose (final conc. 43.8 mM)
 - 0.6 g D-Glucose (final conc. 33.3 mM)
 - Filter through 0.2 µm filter and store at 2-8 °C
- **Trypsin/DNase-I Mix**
 - 5 mL 1x Trypsin (0.25%)
 - 100 µL of DNase-I (1500 Units/mg)
- **Complete DMEM/F-12 Medium:**
 - 500 mL Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium/Nutrient Mixture F-12 (DMEM/F-12)
 - 50 mL Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (final conc. 10%)
 - 5 mL of 100x Penicillin-Streptomycin (PS) (final conc. 1%)
- **Feeding Neurobasal Medium (NBM):**
 - 500 mL Neurobasal Medium
 - 10 mL B27 Supplement (final conc. 2%)
 - 5 mL of 200mM or 100x L-glutamine (final conc. 1%)
 - 5 mL of 100x PS (final conc. 1%)
- **Plating Neurobasal Medium (NBM):**
 - 100 mL Feeding NBM
 - 70 µL of 10 mM β-Mercaptoethanol stock solution (final conc. 10 µM)

¹ The coatings will affect the morphology of the neurons. While neurons were clustering in Matrigel, individual neurons will be observed in PLL or PDL coatings. Concentration of the coatings also will affect attachment percentage of the neurons.

- 100 μ L of 25 mM Glutamate stock solution (final conc. 25 μ M)
- **DIV3 AraC Medium**
 - 50 mL Feeding NBM
 - 10 μ L of 10 mM Cytarabine (AraC) stock solution (final conc. 2 μ M)

Methods

1. Apply cervical dislocation to the pregnant rat under anesthesia.
2. Wipe the abdominal area with alcohol.
3. Remove and transfer the embryos to a petri dish with ice-cold **Transport Solution**.²
4. Remove embryos' brains and transfer to another petri dish with ice-cold **Transport Solution**.
5. Remove the meninges on the cortex, to avoid fibroblasts in the culture, and transfer the extracted whole brains to another petri dish with ice-cold **Transport Solution**.³
6. After removal of meninges, the hemispheres will be separated by cutting from corpus callosum. In the inner side of the brain; striatum, hippocampus, and cortex will be seen from bottom to top.
7. Brain will be hold from the cortex and the striatum and hippocampus will be removed from the hemispheres and will be transferred to the 15 ml centrifuge tube which contains 10 ml ice-cold **Transport Solution**.

From this point, procedure will be handled under sterile GLP conditions in a laminar flow hood.

8. Aspirate and discard the supernatant carefully and wash the tissues with **ice-cold HBSS** two times.
9. Aspirate the last HBSS from the 15 ml centrifuge tube.⁴
10. Add 5 mL **Trypsin/DNase-I Mix** to the cortex tissue and incubate 20 minutes at 37 °C. Make 3-4 times upside down to better digestion.
11. After incubation, add 8 mL Complete DMEM/F12 to inhibit digestion and centrifuge the tube for 3 minutes at 300g.
12. Aspirate the supernatant and wash the pellet 2x with 10 mL **Complete DMEM/F-12 medium**.
13. After removing the supernatant, add 5 mL **Plating NBM** to the pellet and triturate with a 10 mL plastic pipette, until the solution is homogenous.
14. Run the cell solution through a **70 μ m cell strainer** into a 50 mL tube and add 5 mL **Plating NBM** to clean debris on the cell strainer.
15. Count the neural cells:
 - a. Add 10 μ L of cell solution to 10 μ L **Trypan blue solution** to observe alive cells and add 10 μ L of the cell solution to both sides of the hemacytometer.
 - b. Count the living cells that are present within the 4 squares. Then, $(\text{Counted cells}/4) \times 10^4 = \# \times 2 \times 10^4$ Cells/mL of the actual cell solution in the 10 mL cell solution.
 - c. Plate cells with 100,000 cells/cm². (for a 6-wellplate ~500,000 cell/well in 3 mL medium/well).
 - d. Cells should be seeded on **poly-D-lysine, poly-L-lysine, Matrigel or PDL/laminin** coated culture dishes.
16. After plating cell, place well plates in a sterile incubator at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ and **do not move the plate during the following 3 days.**
17. At day 3, add **DIV3 AraC Medium** to the seeded cells by 50% media change, which will bring the AraC concentration to 1 μ M.⁵

² All surgical procedures done on embryos should be performed in ice-cold to slow down the metabolism and to keep cell viability. Also, after dissection of tissue, it is advised to keep transport no longer than max. 3 hours in ice-cold Transport Solution before culture.

³ Removing the meninges from the cortex is highly important to allow homogenous neuron culture growth.

⁴ Do not use any suction system during the procedure, you will immediately lose all hippocampal tissue.

-
18. On the 4th day, 24 hours after the application of AraC medium, the entire cell medium is returned to **feeding NBM**.
 19. Half of the old medium should be replaced with **feeding NBM** every 3-4 days. On day 7-10 neurons will become mature. The hippocampal neurons will live around 21 days if cell culture conditions are stable. This hippocampal neurons could be used in various in vitro electrophysiological studies.(Han et al., 2021)

References

- Han, M., Bahmani Jalali, H., Yildiz, E., Qureshi, M. H., Şahin, A., & Nizamoglu, S. (2021). Photovoltaic neurointerface based on aluminum antimonide nanocrystals. *Communications Materials*, 2(1), 19. doi:10.1038/s43246-021-00123-4
- Paronis, E., Samara, A., Polyzos, A., Spyropoulos, C., & Kostomitsopoulos, N. G. (2014). Maternal weight as an alternative determinant of the gestational day of Wistar rats housed in individually-ventilated cages. *Laboratory Animals*, 49(3), 188-195. doi:10.1177/0023677214562846

⁵ AraC will stop the growth of the glial cells in the culture medium. Pipetting should be done very slowly and carefully at this stage and the cell plates should not be shaken. The cells should not stay dry long times. Primary neurons will be died easily.

KUTTAM <small>KOÇ UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER FOR TRANSLATIONAL MEDICINE</small>	Protocol: Primary Retinal Müller Glia Isolation
	Name: Erdost YILDIZ, MD
	Department: Neuroscience
	Date: 16.05.2021

All experimental procedure has been approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committees of Koç University according to Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on Protection of Animals Used for Scientific Purposes and the Republic of Turkey 5199 Animal Protection Law, Article 9 and 17. In this protocol, the newborn rats in postnatal day 1 to 3 (P1-P3) have been used. The offspring of the pigmented rats are more feasible for pure retinal Müller glia isolation, because the removal of retinal pigment epithelium is easier in the pigmented rat strains.

Chemicals & Media (Prepare in advance)

- **Coated Glass Coverslips**
 - Poly-D-lysine (PDL)/Poly-L-lysine(PLL) coated (50 µg/ml)
 - *or* PDL(*or* PLL) with Laminin (10 µg/ml) coated
 - *or* Gelatin coated (0.1%)
- **Dissection and Transport Solution**
 - 100 mL HBSS
 - 1.5 g Sucrose (final conc. 43.8 mM)
 - 0.6 g D-Glucose (final conc. 33.3 mM)
 - Filter through 0.2 µm filter and store at 2-8 °C
- **Papain/DNAse-I Mix**
 - 10 mL HBSS
 - 10 mg Papain (20 U/mL)
 - 200 µL of DNAse-I (2000 U/mL)
- **Complete DMEM+FBS Medium (cDMEM):**
 - 500 mL Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM)
 - 50 mL Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (final conc. 10%)
 - 5 mL of 100x Penicillin-Streptomycin (PS) (final conc. 1%)

Methods

1. Apply cervical dislocation to the newborn rats under anesthesia.
2. Enucleate the eyeballs of the rats and transfer them to a petri dish with ice-cold **Transport Solution**.⁶
3. Remove the corneas from the eyeballs by cutting from the corneoscleral junctions.
4. Remove iris, lens and vitreous without touching to the retina.⁷
5. Cut the eye cup from four sides to form a cross. By this way, removal of the sclera and retinal pigment epithelium will be easier.
6. Remove the retina from the eye cup via blunt dissection from subretinal space. Then cut the optic nerve to free retina from the eye cup.
7. After the removal of retina, the retinas should be transferred to the 15 ml centrifuge tube which contains 10 ml ice-cold **Transport Solution** via plastic Pasteur pipette.

⁶ All surgical procedures done on embryos should be performed in ice-cold to slow down the metabolism and to keep cell viability. Also, after dissection of tissue, it is advised to keep transport no longer than max. 3 hours in ice-cold Transport Solution before culture.

⁷ Vitreous is an adhesive tissue. Because of this, it should be removed slowly from edges without hard pulling. After removal of vitreous, sclera and retinal pigment epithelium should be removed.

From this point, procedure will be handled under sterile GLP conditions in a laminar flow hood.

8. Aspire and discard the supernatant carefully and wash the tissues with **ice-cold HBSS** two times.⁸
9. Aspire HBSS from the 15 ml centrifuge tube and add 5 mL **Papain/DNase-I Mix** to the retinal tissue
10. Incubate the retina in the digestion mixture for 30 minutes at 37 °C with shaking.
11. After incubation, add 8 mL **cdMEM** to inhibit digestion and centrifuge the tube for 5 minutes at 300g.
12. Aspire the supernatant and wash the pellet with 10 mL **cdMEM**.
13. After removing the supernatant, add 5 mL **cdMEM** to the pellet and triturate with a 10 mL plastic pipette, until the solution is homogenous.
14. Count the glial cells:
 - a. Add 10 µL of cell solution to 10 µL **Trypan blue** to observe alive cells and add 10 µL of the cell solution to both sides of the hemacytometer.
 - b. Count the living cells that are present within the 4 squares. Then, (Counted cells/4)*10= # x 2x10⁴ Cells/mL of the actual cell solution in the 10 mL cell solution.
 - c. Plate cells with 100.000 cells/cm². (for a 6-wellplate ~500.000 cell/well in 3 mL medium/well).
 - d. Cells should be seeded on **poly-D-lysine, poly-L-lysine, Gelatin or PDL + Laminin** coated culture dishes.⁹
15. After plating cell, place well plates in a sterile incubator at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ and **do not move the plate for the following day for better attachment.**
16. After day 1, completely change the cell media with **cdMEM**.

Half of the old medium should be replaced with **cdMEM** every 3 days to feed the cells. On day 7, Müller glia will become mature. The retinal Müller glia could subculture up to 5 passages if cell culture conditions are stable. The characterization of the Müller glia could be made with immunofluorescence co-staining with the two of the following antibodies: glutamine synthetase (GS), glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), p75NTR, Vimentin, and CRALBP (Pereiro et al., 2020).

Reference

Pereiro, X., Ruzafa, N., Acera, A., Urcola, A., & Vecino, E. (2020). Optimization of a Method to Isolate and Culture Adult Porcine, Rats and Mice Müller Glia in Order to Study Retinal Diseases. *Frontiers in Cellular Neuroscience*, 14(7).

doi:10.3389/fncel.2020.00007

⁸ Do not use any suction system during the procedure, you will immediately lose all retinal tissue.

⁹ To distribute the retinal Müller glia without counting, the cells from one retina could be seeded on 8 wells of the 24-well plate.

KUTTAM

 KOÇ UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER
 FOR TRANSLATIONAL MEDICINE

Protocol: Primary Cardiac Myocyte Isolation

Name: Erdost YILDIZ, MD

Department: Neuroscience

Date: 16.05.2021

All experimental procedure has been approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committees of Koç University according to Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on Protection of Animals Used for Scientific Purposes and the Republic of Turkey 5199 Animal Protection Law, Article 9 and 17. In this protocol, embryonic rats between 15th – 18th (E15-E18) days of a pregnant rat will be used. Two methods have commonly used to detect the exact pregnancy day in pregnant rats. The first method is observing the vaginal plaque of the female rat, which will occur on the mating day. The day the plaque occurs is considered as E0. The second method is by monitoring the weight of the pregnant rat. From first day (E0) to seventh day (E7), rat will gain approximately 10.5 grams. From seventh day (E7) to fifteenth day (E15), pregnant rat will gain approximately 21 grams. And from fifteenth day to end of the pregnancy, the rat will gain ~38 grams. Total weight gain during pregnancy will be around 71 grams. When the total weight gain from coitus to two-weeks later is more than 30 grams of the embryo is considered as E15.(Paronis et al., 2014)

Chemicals & Media (Prepare in advance)

- **Coated Glass Coverslips**
 - Collagen (Type I) coated
 - *or* Poly-D-lysine (PDL)/Poly-L-lysine(PLL) coated
 - *or* Matrigel coated
- **Transport Solution¹⁰**
 - 500 mL Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium/Nutrient Mixture F-12 (DMEM/F-12)
 - 5 mL of 100x Penicillin-Streptomycin (PS) (final conc. 1%)
 - Filter through 0.2 µm filter and store at 2-8 °C
- **Trypsin/Collagenase Mixture**
 - 5 mL 1x Trypsin (final conc. 0.25%)
 - 100 µL of DNase-I (1500 Units/mg)
 - 5 mg Collagenase Type IV (final conc. 0.1%)¹¹
 - 2.75 mg CaCl₂ (final conc. 5mM)
- **Complete DMEM/F-12 Medium:**
 - 500 mL Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium/Nutrient Mixture F-12 (DMEM/F-12)
 - 50 mL Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (final conc. 10%)
 - 5 mL of 100x Penicillin-Streptomycin (PS) (final conc. 1%)
- **Plating Medium**
 - 100 mL Complete DMEM/F-12 Medium
 - 100 µL of 10 mM Cytarabine (AraC) stock solution (final conc. 10 µM)

¹⁰ The calcium paradox of the heart is a unique phenomenon of the cardiac muscle cells. Absence or overabundance of Ca²⁺ in the cell culture media will lead to dramatic negative alterations in myocardial muscle cells during isolation process. Because of this paradox, Ca²⁺ levels in the cell culture media should be checked. Ca²⁺ levels should be equal in physiological levels for all the cell culture media.(Piper, 2000)

¹¹ Other types of the collagenase could be used but concentration should be changed.

Methods

1. Apply cervical dislocation to the pregnant rat under anesthesia.
2. Wipe the abdominal area with alcohol.
3. Remove and transfer the embryos to a petri dish with ice-cold **Transport Solution**.¹²
4. Remove embryos' bodies and transfer to another petri dish with ice-cold **Transport Solution**.
5. Cut the thoracic cages of the embryos to observe heart and lungs and remove ribs, sternum, and thymus to create space for the heart.
6. By holding from the aortic arc, remove the whole hearts and transfer them to another petri dish with ice-cold **Transport Solution**.
7. The hearts should be cut to four parts to divide atria and ventricles.¹³
8. The cardiac tissues will be transferred to the 15 ml centrifuge tube which contains 10 ml ice-cold **Transport Solution**.

From this point, procedure will be handled under sterile GLP conditions in a laminar flow hood.

9. Aspirate and discard the supernatant carefully and wash the tissues with **ice-cold Transport Solution** two times.
10. Aspirate the supernatant from the 15 ml centrifuge tube.¹⁴
11. Add 5 mL **Trypsin/Collagenase Mixture** to the cardiac tissue and incubate 20 minutes at 37 °C. Make 3-4 times upside down to better digestion.
12. After incubation, add 8 mL Complete DMEM/F12 to inhibit digestion and centrifuge the tube for 3 minutes at 300g.
13. Aspirate the supernatant and wash the pellet 2x with 10 mL **Complete DMEM/F-12 medium**.
14. After removing the supernatant, add 5 mL **Plating Medium** to the pellet and triturate with a 10 mL plastic pipette ten (10) times and transfer the supernatant to new 50 mL centrifuge tube.
15. Repeat 14. step two times to the tissue remnants in the 15 ml centrifuge tube to increase the number of isolated cardiac myocytes.
16. Count the cardiac myocytes:
 - a. Add 10 µL of cell solution to 10 µL **Trypan blue solution** to observe alive cells and add 10 µL of the cell solution to both sides of the hemacytometer.
 - b. Count the living cells that are present within the 4 squares. Then, $(\text{Counted cells}/4) \times 10 = \# \times 2 \times 10^4$ Cells/mL of the actual cell solution in the 10 mL cell solution.
 - c. Plate cells with 100,000 cells/cm². (for a 6-wellplate ~500,000 cell/well in 3 mL medium/well).
 - d. Cells should be seeded on **collagen, poly-D-lysine, poly-L-lysine, or Matrigel** coated culture dishes.
17. After plating cell, place well plates in a sterile incubator at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ and **do not move the plate during the following 2 days.**¹⁵
18. At day 2, change the old media with the **Complete DMEM/F-12 Medium**.

¹² All surgical procedures done on embryos should be performed in ice-cold to slow down the metabolism and to keep cell viability. Also, after dissection of tissue, it is advised to keep transport no longer than max. 3 hours in ice-cold Transport Solution before culture.

¹³ Excessive blood leads to decreased cell viability in cardiac myocyte cell culture. Minimizing the blood exposure on the tissue will create better results in the myocyte isolation procedure.

¹⁴ Do not use any suction system during the procedure, you will immediately lose all cardiac tissue.

¹⁵ AraC will stop the growth of other mesenchymal cells in the culture medium. Pipetting should be done very slowly and carefully at this stage and the cell plates should not be shaken. The cells should not stay dry long times. Primary cardiac myocytes are very sensitive and will be died easily.

-
19. Half of the old medium should be replaced with **Complete DMEM/F-12 Medium** every 2-3 days. On day 7-10, cardiac myocytes will become mature, and the muscle cell contractions will be seen. The cardiac myocytes will live around 21 days and can be passaged with **0.05% Trypsin-EDTA** if cell culture conditions are stable.

References

- Paronis, E., Samara, A., Polyzos, A., Spyropoulos, C., & Kostomitsopoulos, N. G. (2014). Maternal weight as an alternative determinant of the gestational day of Wistar rats housed in individually-ventilated cages. *Laboratory Animals*, 49(3), 188-195. doi:10.1177/0023677214562846
- Piper, H. M. (2000). The calcium paradox revisited: an artefact of great heuristic value. *Cardiovasc Res*, 45(1), 123-127. doi:10.1016/s0008-6363(99)00304-1